

Table S2: Gene set enrichment analysis of RNA-seq studies comparing Ala92-Dio and Thr92-Dio2 iBAT.

Gene set	Description	Type	Enrichment score	P-value	FDR step up	Rich factor	Genes in set
GO:0043229	intracellular organelle	cellular_component	621.11	1.80E-270	3.84E-266	8.51E-01	9595
GO:0043226	organelle	cellular_component	594.81	4.78E-259	5.10E-255	8.47E-01	9774
GO:0043231	intracellular membrane-bounded organelle	cellular_component	593.81	1.29E-258	9.16E-255	8.64E-01	8328
GO:0043227	membrane-bounded organelle	cellular_component	578.86	4.01E-252	2.14E-248	8.56E-01	8853
GO:0044237	cellular metabolic process	biological_process	354.61	9.91E-155	4.22E-151	8.72E-01	5590
GO:0008152	metabolic process	biological_process	343.37	7.54E-150	2.68E-146	8.61E-01	6235
GO:0071704	organic substance metabolic process	biological_process	289.69	1.55E-126	4.71E-123	8.58E-01	5793
GO:0044238	primary metabolic process	biological_process	281.72	4.46E-123	1.19E-119	8.61E-01	5454
GO:0005634	nucleus	cellular_component	268.23	3.22E-117	7.63E-114	8.64E-01	5088
GO:0006807	nitrogen compound metabolic process	biological_process	264.13	1.95E-115	4.15E-112	8.64E-01	5035
GO:0043170	macromolecule metabolic process	biological_process	248.22	1.58E-108	3.06E-105	8.69E-01	4460
GO:0110165	cellular anatomical entity	cellular_component	231.96	1.83E-101	3.26E-98	7.85E-01	13444
GO:0034641	cellular nitrogen compound metabolic process	biological_process	214.96	4.42E-94	7.25E-91	9.02E-01	2550
GO:0044260	cellular macromolecule metabolic process	biological_process	210.84	2.71E-92	4.13E-89	8.77E-01	3502
GO:0009987	cellular process	biological_process	197.82	1.23E-86	1.75E-83	8.02E-01	10515
GO:0005654	nucleoplasm	cellular_component	186.93	6.59E-82	8.78E-79	8.93E-01	2531
GO:0005739	mitochondrion	cellular_component	184.79	5.58E-81	7.00E-78	9.27E-01	1617
GO:0032991	protein-containing complex	cellular_component	181.64	1.31E-79	1.55E-76	8.51E-01	4616
GO:0006139	nucleobase-containing compound metabolic process	biological_process	178.71	2.43E-78	2.73E-75	9.07E-01	2029
GO:0046483	heterocycle metabolic process	biological_process	174.40	1.82E-76	1.94E-73	9.01E-01	2143
GO:0005737	cytoplasm	cellular_component	172.01	1.99E-75	2.02E-72	8.34E-01	5791
GO:0005488	binding	molecular_function	166.73	3.88E-73	3.76E-70	7.98E-01	10542
GO:0016070	RNA metabolic process	biological_process	166.42	5.29E-73	4.90E-70	9.47E-01	1148
GO:1901363	heterocyclic compound binding	molecular_function	166.19	6.68E-73	5.94E-70	8.50E-01	4334
GO:0006725	cellular aromatic compound metabolic process	biological_process	163.84	7.01E-72	5.98E-69	8.95E-01	2189
GO:0005829	cytosol	cellular_component	163.41	1.08E-71	8.87E-69	8.76E-01	2895
GO:0097159	organic cyclic compound binding	molecular_function	163.25	1.27E-71	1.00E-68	8.49E-01	4397
GO:0090304	nucleic acid metabolic process	biological_process	163.09	1.49E-71	1.13E-68	9.16E-01	1649
GO:0003824	catalytic activity	molecular_function	152.45	6.17E-67	4.54E-64	8.40E-01	4847
GO:1901360	organic cyclic compound metabolic process	biological_process	150.86	3.05E-66	2.16E-63	8.85E-01	2345
GO:0003676	nucleic acid binding	molecular_function	143.18	6.57E-63	4.52E-60	8.73E-01	2676
GO:0044267	cellular protein metabolic process	N/A	139.10	3.89E-61	2.59E-58	8.80E-01	2353
GO:1901564	organonitrogen compound metabolic process	biological_process	129.96	3.62E-57	2.34E-54	8.48E-01	3696
GO:1902494	catalytic complex	cellular_component	129.69	4.76E-57	2.99E-54	9.20E-01	1271
GO:0003723	RNA binding	molecular_function	127.09	6.40E-56	3.90E-53	9.36E-01	1007
GO:0019538	protein metabolic process	biological_process	119.94	8.11E-53	4.80E-50	8.58E-01	2957
GO:0006396	RNA processing	biological_process	117.93	6.10E-52	3.51E-49	9.59E-01	708
GO:0019222	regulation of metabolic process	biological_process	116.64	2.22E-51	1.25E-48	8.28E-01	4977
GO:0031323	regulation of cellular metabolic process	biological_process	109.78	2.10E-48	1.15E-45	8.29E-01	4654
GO:0043412	macromolecule modification	biological_process	108.20	1.02E-47	5.46E-45	8.70E-01	2190
GO:0080090	regulation of primary metabolic process	biological_process	104.78	3.12E-46	1.62E-43	8.29E-01	4464
GO:0051171	regulation of nitrogen compound metabolic process	biological_process	101.42	8.99E-45	4.56E-42	8.30E-01	4335

GO:0060255	regulation of macromolecule metabolic process	biological_process	101.19	1.13E-44	5.63E-42	8.27E-01	4555
GO:0046907	intracellular transport	biological_process	99.57	5.71E-44	2.77E-41	9.13E-01	1086
GO:0043228	non-membrane-bounded organelle	cellular_component	99.02	9.96E-44	4.72E-41	8.51E-01	2794
GO:0043232	intracellular non-membrane-bounded organelle	cellular_component	97.91	2.99E-43	1.39E-40	8.51E-01	2772
GO:1990904	ribonucleoprotein complex	cellular_component	97.45	4.74E-43	2.15E-40	9.49E-01	665
GO:0019899	enzyme binding	molecular_function	94.99	5.56E-42	2.47E-39	8.64E-01	2162
GO:0009058	biosynthetic process	biological_process	92.12	9.81E-41	4.27E-38	8.75E-01	1747
GO:0044271	cellular nitrogen compound biosynthetic process	biological_process	91.60	1.65E-40	7.04E-38	9.12E-01	1004
GO:0010468	regulation of gene expression	biological_process	91.34	2.15E-40	8.97E-38	8.41E-01	3185
GO:0006464	cellular protein modification process	N/A	90.29	6.15E-40	2.47E-37	8.65E-01	2035
GO:0036211	protein modification process	biological_process	90.29	6.15E-40	2.47E-37	8.65E-01	2035
GO:0044249	cellular biosynthetic process	biological_process	87.58	9.18E-39	3.62E-36	8.78E-01	1586
GO:1901576	organic substance biosynthetic process	biological_process	86.43	2.92E-38	1.13E-35	8.74E-01	1676
GO:0044248	cellular catabolic process	biological_process	85.79	5.51E-38	2.10E-35	8.94E-01	1225
GO:1990234	transferase complex	cellular_component	85.26	9.35E-38	3.50E-35	9.33E-01	714
GO:0044265	cellular macromolecule catabolic process	biological_process	83.66	4.67E-37	1.72E-34	9.42E-01	622
GO:0009056	catabolic process	biological_process	83.41	5.96E-37	2.15E-34	8.82E-01	1420
GO:0009889	regulation of biosynthetic process	biological_process	83.13	7.91E-37	2.81E-34	8.39E-01	3059
GO:0010556	regulation of macromolecule biosynthetic process	biological_process	83.10	8.14E-37	2.85E-34	8.42E-01	2873
GO:0031090	organelle membrane	cellular_component	82.16	2.08E-36	7.15E-34	8.75E-01	1565
GO:2000112	regulation of cellular macromolecule biosynthetic process	biological_process	82.12	2.16E-36	7.30E-34	8.43E-01	2794
GO:0051641	cellular localization	biological_process	81.85	2.84E-36	9.47E-34	8.69E-01	1733
GO:0009057	macromolecule catabolic process	biological_process	81.42	4.38E-36	1.44E-33	9.28E-01	724
GO:0031326	regulation of cellular biosynthetic process	biological_process	80.65	9.41E-36	3.04E-33	8.39E-01	2998
GO:0071840	cellular component organization or biogenesis	biological_process	78.96	5.11E-35	1.63E-32	8.22E-01	4174
GO:0019219	regulation of nucleobase-containing compound metabolic process	biological_process	77.74	1.73E-34	5.43E-32	8.40E-01	2848
GO:0016071	mRNA metabolic process	biological_process	76.28	7.42E-34	2.29E-31	9.53E-01	493
GO:0034470	ncRNA processing	biological_process	75.77	1.25E-33	3.79E-31	9.85E-01	330
GO:0015833	peptide transport	biological_process	75.21	2.18E-33	6.55E-31	8.90E-01	1139
GO:0009059	macromolecule biosynthetic process	biological_process	74.82	3.22E-33	9.54E-31	9.08E-01	878
GO:0015031	protein transport	biological_process	74.68	3.70E-33	1.08E-30	8.91E-01	1119
GO:0034660	ncRNA metabolic process	biological_process	74.52	4.34E-33	1.25E-30	9.70E-01	394
GO:0005730	nucleolus	cellular_component	73.93	7.84E-33	2.23E-30	9.25E-01	683
GO:0042886	amide transport	biological_process	73.88	8.21E-33	2.30E-30	8.88E-01	1160
GO:0005515	protein binding	molecular_function	73.67	1.01E-32	2.79E-30	7.96E-01	7568
GO:1901575	organic substance catabolic process	biological_process	73.36	1.38E-32	3.77E-30	8.85E-01	1202
GO:0045184	establishment of protein localization	biological_process	73.29	1.48E-32	4.00E-30	8.85E-01	1196
GO:0033036	macromolecule localization	biological_process	71.92	5.85E-32	1.56E-29	8.63E-01	1717
GO:0051252	regulation of RNA metabolic process	biological_process	71.40	9.79E-32	2.58E-29	8.40E-01	2619
GO:0071705	nitrogen compound transport	biological_process	71.39	9.90E-32	2.58E-29	8.74E-01	1393
GO:0016043	cellular component organization	biological_process	69.40	7.25E-31	1.86E-28	8.19E-01	4093
GO:0043167	ion binding	molecular_function	69.32	7.87E-31	2.00E-28	8.13E-01	4726
GO:0016740	transferase activity	molecular_function	69.26	8.34E-31	2.09E-28	8.51E-01	2033
GO:0008104	protein localization	biological_process	69.02	1.06E-30	2.64E-28	8.61E-01	1698

GO:0034645	cellular macromolecule biosynthetic process	biological_process	66.88	8.98E-30	2.20E-27	9.07E-01	789
GO:0033554	cellular response to stress	biological_process	65.89	2.43E-29	5.90E-27	8.74E-01	1295
GO:0009894	regulation of catabolic process	biological_process	63.32	3.18E-28	7.61E-26	9.03E-01	795
GO:0009892	negative regulation of metabolic process	biological_process	61.82	1.43E-27	3.38E-25	8.39E-01	2349
GO:0031966	mitochondrial membrane	cellular_component	61.41	2.15E-27	5.03E-25	9.29E-01	538
GO:0009893	positive regulation of metabolic process	biological_process	60.98	3.28E-27	7.59E-25	8.27E-01	3043
GO:0006412	translation	biological_process	59.70	1.18E-26	2.72E-24	9.82E-01	271
GO:0140098	catalytic activity, acting on RNA	molecular_function	59.51	1.43E-26	3.25E-24	9.69E-01	318
GO:2001141	regulation of RNA biosynthetic process	biological_process	59.48	1.48E-26	3.31E-24	8.37E-01	2388
GO:0098798	mitochondrial protein complex	cellular_component	59.31	1.74E-26	3.87E-24	9.85E-01	259
GO:1903506	regulation of nucleic acid-templated transcription	biological_process	59.23	1.90E-26	4.17E-24	8.37E-01	2386
GO:0019866	organelle inner membrane	cellular_component	58.45	4.14E-26	9.01E-24	9.46E-01	411
GO:0006355	regulation of transcription, DNA-templated	biological_process	58.23	5.14E-26	1.11E-23	8.36E-01	2378
GO:0031324	negative regulation of cellular metabolic process	biological_process	57.80	7.91E-26	1.69E-23	8.42E-01	2096
GO:0005743	mitochondrial inner membrane	cellular_component	56.99	1.78E-25	3.77E-23	9.50E-01	382
GO:0016604	nuclear body	cellular_component	56.22	3.83E-25	8.01E-23	9.08E-01	655
GO:0031329	regulation of cellular catabolic process	biological_process	56.19	3.95E-25	8.18E-23	9.08E-01	661
GO:0006518	peptide metabolic process	biological_process	55.98	4.87E-25	9.99E-23	9.47E-01	393
GO:0051603	proteolysis involved in cellular protein catabolic process	biological_process	55.50	7.91E-25	1.61E-22	9.27E-01	504
GO:0031325	positive regulation of cellular metabolic process	biological_process	55.19	1.08E-24	2.17E-22	8.27E-01	2794
GO:0071702	organic substance transport	biological_process	54.75	1.67E-24	3.33E-22	8.52E-01	1615
GO:0010605	negative regulation of macromolecule metabolic process	biological_process	54.68	1.80E-24	3.55E-22	8.39E-01	2115
GO:0006996	organelle organization	biological_process	54.59	1.95E-24	3.82E-22	8.43E-01	1940
GO:0051172	negative regulation of nitrogen compound metabolic process	biological_process	54.54	2.05E-24	3.97E-22	8.43E-01	1925
GO:0010604	positive regulation of macromolecule metabolic process	biological_process	53.82	4.25E-24	8.16E-22	8.26E-01	2782
GO:0006397	mRNA processing	biological_process	53.52	5.72E-24	1.09E-21	9.47E-01	375
GO:0043043	peptide biosynthetic process	biological_process	53.32	6.99E-24	1.32E-21	9.68E-01	285
GO:0070647	protein modification by small protein conjugation or removal	biological_process	53.07	8.93E-24	1.67E-21	9.17E-01	545
GO:0043632	modification-dependent macromolecule catabolic process	biological_process	53.06	9.01E-24	1.67E-21	9.31E-01	452
GO:0006886	intracellular protein transport	biological_process	52.46	1.65E-23	3.04E-21	9.02E-01	672
GO:0051716	cellular response to stimulus	biological_process	52.05	2.47E-23	4.50E-21	8.32E-01	2365
GO:0019941	modification-dependent protein catabolic process	biological_process	51.09	6.46E-23	1.17E-20	9.30E-01	443
GO:0051173	positive regulation of nitrogen compound metabolic process	biological_process	50.41	1.27E-22	2.28E-20	8.26E-01	2636
GO:0043603	cellular amide metabolic process	biological_process	50.18	1.62E-22	2.87E-20	9.09E-01	581
GO:0043604	amide biosynthetic process	biological_process	49.92	2.09E-22	3.68E-20	9.43E-01	367
GO:0018130	heterocycle biosynthetic process	biological_process	49.82	2.30E-22	4.02E-20	9.00E-01	658
GO:0050794	regulation of cellular process	biological_process	48.76	6.70E-22	1.16E-19	7.86E-01	7891
GO:0006511	ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process	biological_process	48.71	7.03E-22	1.21E-19	9.28E-01	432
GO:0016192	vesicle-mediated transport	biological_process	48.20	1.17E-21	2.00E-19	8.77E-01	910

GO:0051020	GTPase binding	molecular_function	47.89	1.59E-21	2.70E-19	9.17E-01	494
GO:0051246	regulation of protein metabolic process	biological_process	47.67	1.97E-21	3.32E-19	8.29E-01	2346
GO:0034654	nucleobase-containing compound biosynthetic process	biological_process	47.56	2.21E-21	3.68E-19	9.03E-01	598
GO:1901265	nucleoside phosphate binding	molecular_function	47.17	3.27E-21	5.36E-19	8.38E-01	1857
GO:0000166	nucleotide binding	molecular_function	47.17	3.27E-21	5.36E-19	8.38E-01	1857
GO:0003677	DNA binding	molecular_function	45.40	1.92E-20	3.12E-18	8.41E-01	1707
GO:0016072	rRNA metabolic process	biological_process	45.37	1.97E-20	3.19E-18	9.85E-01	197
GO:0048523	negative regulation of cellular process	biological_process	45.02	2.81E-20	4.50E-18	8.07E-01	3974
GO:0048519	negative regulation of biological process	biological_process	44.74	3.72E-20	5.92E-18	8.03E-01	4399
GO:0032268	regulation of cellular protein metabolic process	N/A	43.65	1.10E-19	1.74E-17	8.28E-01	2179
GO:0010608	postranscriptional regulation of gene expression	biological_process	43.61	1.15E-19	1.81E-17	9.28E-01	388
GO:0006364	rRNA processing	biological_process	43.47	1.32E-19	2.06E-17	9.84E-01	190
GO:0008380	RNA splicing	biological_process	43.37	1.46E-19	2.25E-17	9.49E-01	294
GO:0048193	Golgi vesicle transport	biological_process	43.02	2.07E-19	3.18E-17	9.69E-01	227
GO:0006357	regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II	biological_process	42.93	2.27E-19	3.46E-17	8.40E-01	1653
GO:0009890	negative regulation of biosynthetic process	biological_process	42.60	3.15E-19	4.76E-17	8.51E-01	1300
GO:0019438	aromatic compound biosynthetic process	biological_process	41.80	7.03E-19	1.06E-16	8.88E-01	660
GO:0051128	regulation of cellular component organization	biological_process	41.67	7.96E-19	1.19E-16	8.24E-01	2301
GO:0003712	transcription coregulator activity	molecular_function	41.59	8.65E-19	1.28E-16	9.16E-01	431
GO:0140096	catalytic activity, acting on a protein	molecular_function	41.33	1.13E-18	1.66E-16	8.33E-01	1875
GO:0010558	negative regulation of macromolecule biosynthetic process	biological_process	41.06	1.47E-18	2.14E-16	8.52E-01	1218
GO:0005794	Golgi apparatus	cellular_component	41.06	1.48E-18	2.14E-16	8.55E-01	1152
GO:0031327	negative regulation of cellular biosynthetic process	biological_process	40.35	3.00E-18	4.32E-16	8.50E-01	1263
GO:0010629	negative regulation of gene expression	biological_process	40.34	3.02E-18	4.32E-16	8.44E-01	1417
GO:0005681	spliceosomal complex	cellular_component	39.91	4.63E-18	6.58E-16	9.79E-01	187
GO:0045935	positive regulation of nucleobase-containing compound metabolic process	biological_process	39.69	5.80E-18	8.19E-16	8.40E-01	1539
GO:0046872	metal ion binding	molecular_function	39.26	8.87E-18	1.24E-15	8.13E-01	2989
GO:0006399	tRNA metabolic process	biological_process	39.09	1.06E-17	1.47E-15	9.88E-01	163
GO:2000113	negative regulation of cellular macromolecule biosynthetic process	biological_process	39.06	1.08E-17	1.50E-15	8.51E-01	1188
GO:0044085	cellular component biogenesis	biological_process	38.68	1.59E-17	2.19E-15	1.00E+00	136
GO:0031267	small GTPase binding	molecular_function	38.32	2.29E-17	3.13E-15	9.15E-01	402
GO:0005783	endoplasmic reticulum	cellular_component	38.14	2.73E-17	3.71E-15	8.43E-01	1365
GO:0048522	positive regulation of cellular process	biological_process	38.12	2.79E-17	3.76E-15	7.98E-01	4526
GO:0033043	regulation of organelle organization	biological_process	38.00	3.15E-17	4.23E-15	8.50E-01	1190
GO:0044281	small molecule metabolic process	biological_process	37.60	4.69E-17	6.26E-15	8.48E-01	1217
GO:0036094	small molecule binding	molecular_function	37.56	4.90E-17	6.49E-15	8.23E-01	2146
GO:1901362	organic cyclic compound biosynthetic process	biological_process	37.48	5.27E-17	6.93E-15	8.74E-01	745
GO:0031625	ubiquitin protein ligase binding	molecular_function	37.38	5.83E-17	7.63E-15	9.40E-01	283
GO:0022607	cellular component assembly	biological_process	37.23	6.80E-17	8.84E-15	8.32E-01	1701
GO:0032446	protein modification by small protein conjugation	biological_process	37.17	7.22E-17	9.32E-15	9.07E-01	440
GO:0008134	transcription factor binding	molecular_function	36.91	9.34E-17	1.20E-14	8.81E-01	648
GO:0010628	positive regulation of gene expression	biological_process	36.69	1.16E-16	1.48E-14	8.32E-01	1682

GO:0043169	cation binding	molecular_function	36.60	1.28E-16	1.62E-14	8.10E-01	3050
GO:0016607	nuclear speck	cellular_component	35.57	3.58E-16	4.51E-14	9.31E-01	303
GO:0034248	regulation of cellular amide metabolic process	biological_process	35.41	4.17E-16	5.24E-14	9.17E-01	362
GO:0051179	localization	biological_process	35.33	4.53E-16	5.62E-14	8.05E-01	3382
GO:0016787	hydrolase activity	molecular_function	35.33	4.53E-16	5.62E-14	8.23E-01	2041
GO:1901566	organonitrogen compound biosynthetic process	biological_process	35.30	4.67E-16	5.76E-14	8.71E-01	731
GO:0035639	purine ribonucleoside triphosphate binding	molecular_function	35.28	4.75E-16	5.82E-14	8.34E-01	1574
GO:0022613	ribonucleoprotein complex biogenesis	biological_process	35.25	4.90E-16	5.97E-14	1.00E+00	124
GO:0017076	purine nucleotide binding	molecular_function	35.21	5.11E-16	6.19E-14	8.32E-01	1645
GO:0070727	cellular macromolecule localization	biological_process	35.15	5.43E-16	6.54E-14	8.60E-01	899
GO:0017016	Ras GTPase binding	N/A	35.12	5.56E-16	6.67E-14	9.12E-01	386
GO:0006417	regulation of translation	biological_process	35.01	6.27E-16	7.47E-14	9.27E-01	314
GO:0032553	ribonucleotide binding	molecular_function	34.79	7.77E-16	9.20E-14	8.31E-01	1646
GO:0005768	endosome	cellular_component	34.67	8.77E-16	1.03E-13	8.69E-01	743
GO:0055114	oxidation-reduction process	biological_process	34.46	1.09E-15	1.27E-13	8.77E-01	644
GO:0051254	positive regulation of RNA metabolic process	biological_process	34.16	1.46E-15	1.70E-13	8.38E-01	1386
GO:0030163	protein catabolic process	biological_process	34.12	1.51E-15	1.75E-13	9.14E-01	362
GO:0034613	cellular protein localization	N/A	34.02	1.68E-15	1.93E-13	8.59E-01	891
GO:0006401	RNA catabolic process	biological_process	34.02	1.69E-15	1.93E-13	9.92E-01	133
GO:0044877	protein-containing complex binding	molecular_function	33.99	1.74E-15	1.98E-13	8.41E-01	1292
GO:0009896	positive regulation of catabolic process	biological_process	33.97	1.77E-15	2.01E-13	9.05E-01	411
GO:0032555	purine ribonucleotide binding	molecular_function	33.88	1.94E-15	2.19E-13	8.30E-01	1633
GO:0016567	protein ubiquitination	biological_process	33.83	2.04E-15	2.29E-13	9.07E-01	398
GO:0045934	negative regulation of nucleobase-containing compound metabolic process	biological_process	33.79	2.11E-15	2.36E-13	8.44E-01	1197
GO:0010557	positive regulation of macromolecule biosynthetic process	biological_process	33.76	2.17E-15	2.41E-13	8.32E-01	1551
GO:0065007	biological regulation	biological_process	33.56	2.66E-15	2.94E-13	7.77E-01	8846
GO:0050789	regulation of biological process	biological_process	33.53	2.73E-15	3.00E-13	7.79E-01	8403
GO:0044389	ubiquitin-like protein ligase binding	molecular_function	33.46	2.94E-15	3.21E-13	9.27E-01	300
GO:0031647	regulation of protein stability	biological_process	33.12	4.13E-15	4.49E-13	9.36E-01	264
GO:0048518	positive regulation of biological process	biological_process	33.00	4.64E-15	5.02E-13	7.92E-01	5068
GO:0033365	protein localization to organelle	biological_process	32.37	8.71E-15	9.38E-13	8.85E-01	531
GO:0032774	RNA biosynthetic process	biological_process	32.12	1.12E-14	1.20E-12	9.19E-01	320
GO:0009891	positive regulation of biosynthetic process	biological_process	32.11	1.14E-14	1.21E-12	8.28E-01	1664
GO:0005840	ribosome	cellular_component	32.10	1.15E-14	1.22E-12	9.58E-01	192
GO:0031331	positive regulation of cellular catabolic process	biological_process	32.00	1.26E-14	1.33E-12	9.13E-01	345
GO:0043168	anion binding	molecular_function	31.72	1.67E-14	1.76E-12	8.14E-01	2394
GO:0043233	organelle lumen	cellular_component	31.71	1.70E-14	1.76E-12	9.26E-01	285
GO:0070013	intracellular organelle lumen	cellular_component	31.71	1.70E-14	1.76E-12	9.26E-01	285
GO:0031974	membrane-enclosed lumen	cellular_component	31.71	1.70E-14	1.76E-12	9.26E-01	285
GO:0051253	negative regulation of RNA metabolic process	biological_process	31.70	1.71E-14	1.76E-12	8.45E-01	1101
GO:0031328	positive regulation of cellular biosynthetic process	biological_process	31.61	1.88E-14	1.92E-12	8.28E-01	1631
GO:0006974	cellular response to DNA damage stimulus	biological_process	31.56	1.96E-14	2.00E-12	8.72E-01	642
GO:0008047	enzyme activator activity	molecular_function	31.35	2.43E-14	2.47E-12	8.98E-01	421
GO:0016569	covalent chromatin modification	biological_process	31.20	2.81E-14	2.84E-12	9.19E-01	309

GO:0044391	ribosomal subunit	cellular_component	31.12	3.05E-14	3.06E-12	9.54E-01	196
GO:0051248	negative regulation of protein metabolic process	biological_process	30.88	3.90E-14	3.90E-12	8.53E-01	909
GO:0000375	RNA splicing, via transesterification reactions	biological_process	30.72	4.57E-14	4.55E-12	9.74E-01	152
GO:0043021	ribonucleoprotein complex binding	molecular_function	30.59	5.17E-14	5.13E-12	9.79E-01	142
GO:0010498	proteasomal protein catabolic process	biological_process	30.51	5.60E-14	5.53E-12	9.23E-01	286
	RNA splicing, via transesterification reactions with bulged						
GO:0000377	adenosine as nucleophile	biological_process	30.46	5.92E-14	5.79E-12	9.74E-01	151
GO:0000398	mRNA splicing, via spliceosome	biological_process	30.46	5.92E-14	5.79E-12	9.74E-01	151
GO:0034655	nucleobase-containing compound catabolic process	biological_process	29.97	9.61E-14	9.35E-12	9.44E-01	214
GO:0006793	phosphorus metabolic process	biological_process	29.89	1.04E-13	1.01E-11	8.29E-01	1492
GO:1902680	positive regulation of RNA biosynthetic process	biological_process	29.80	1.14E-13	1.10E-11	8.35E-01	1300
GO:0016570	histone modification	biological_process	29.78	1.17E-13	1.12E-11	9.17E-01	302
GO:1903508	positive regulation of nucleic acid-templated transcription	biological_process	29.69	1.28E-13	1.22E-11	8.34E-01	1299
GO:0045893	positive regulation of transcription, DNA-templated	biological_process	29.35	1.79E-13	1.71E-11	8.34E-01	1296
GO:0006796	phosphate-containing compound metabolic process	biological_process	29.17	2.15E-13	2.04E-11	8.29E-01	1471
GO:1903827	regulation of cellular protein localization	N/A	29.11	2.28E-13	2.14E-11	8.79E-01	528
	proteasome-mediated ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic						
GO:0043161	process	biological_process	29.11	2.28E-13	2.14E-11	9.25E-01	266
GO:0140101	catalytic activity, acting on a tRNA	molecular_function	28.74	3.29E-13	3.08E-11	9.91E-01	114
GO:0006325	chromatin organization	biological_process	28.43	4.48E-13	4.17E-11	8.73E-01	573
GO:0042176	regulation of protein catabolic process	biological_process	28.38	4.75E-13	4.40E-11	9.00E-01	369
GO:0006810	transport	biological_process	28.12	6.12E-13	5.65E-11	8.05E-01	2770
GO:0030554	adenyl nucleotide binding	molecular_function	28.08	6.41E-13	5.89E-11	8.31E-01	1342
GO:0018205	peptidyl-lysine modification	biological_process	28.05	6.55E-13	5.99E-11	9.34E-01	227
GO:0042254	ribosome biogenesis	biological_process	27.83	8.17E-13	7.44E-11	1.00E+00	98
GO:0032269	negative regulation of cellular protein metabolic process	N/A	27.78	8.62E-13	7.82E-11	8.51E-01	850
GO:0006402	mRNA catabolic process	biological_process	27.64	9.95E-13	8.99E-11	9.91E-01	110
GO:1903362	regulation of cellular protein catabolic process	N/A	27.45	1.19E-12	1.07E-10	9.29E-01	238
GO:0072594	establishment of protein localization to organelle	biological_process	27.32	1.36E-12	1.22E-10	9.20E-01	264
GO:0006508	proteolysis	biological_process	27.23	1.49E-12	1.33E-10	8.48E-01	886
GO:0003682	chromatin binding	molecular_function	27.20	1.53E-12	1.36E-10	8.75E-01	527
GO:0016197	endosomal transport	biological_process	27.18	1.58E-12	1.40E-10	9.47E-01	187
GO:0043933	protein-containing complex subunit organization	biological_process	27.00	1.88E-12	1.66E-10	8.41E-01	1023
GO:1902679	negative regulation of RNA biosynthetic process	biological_process	26.98	1.92E-12	1.68E-10	8.41E-01	1013
GO:1903507	negative regulation of nucleic acid-templated transcription	biological_process	26.98	1.92E-12	1.68E-10	8.41E-01	1013
GO:0009451	RNA modification	biological_process	26.90	2.07E-12	1.80E-10	9.77E-01	128
GO:0032559	adenyl ribonucleotide binding	molecular_function	26.89	2.10E-12	1.82E-10	8.29E-01	1331
GO:1901565	organonitrogen compound catabolic process	biological_process	26.83	2.22E-12	1.91E-10	8.68E-01	584
GO:0005524	ATP binding	molecular_function	26.83	2.23E-12	1.92E-10	8.31E-01	1278
GO:0019637	organophosphate metabolic process	biological_process	26.69	2.57E-12	2.20E-10	8.63E-01	636
GO:0010638	positive regulation of organelle organization	biological_process	26.66	2.65E-12	2.26E-10	8.71E-01	556
GO:0015931	nucleobase-containing compound transport	biological_process	26.54	2.99E-12	2.54E-10	9.53E-01	169
GO:0022618	ribonucleoprotein complex assembly	biological_process	26.51	3.06E-12	2.59E-10	9.57E-01	161

GO:0045892	negative regulation of transcription, DNA-templated	biological_process	26.50	3.09E-12	2.61E-10	8.40E-01	1009
GO:0140110	transcription regulator activity	molecular_function	26.35	3.60E-12	3.02E-10	8.35E-01	1144
GO:0097367	carbohydrate derivative binding	molecular_function	26.31	3.75E-12	3.14E-10	8.16E-01	1898
GO:0071826	ribonucleoprotein complex subunit organization	biological_process	26.30	3.79E-12	3.16E-10	9.52E-01	168
GO:0051234	establishment of localization	biological_process	26.23	4.06E-12	3.37E-10	8.02E-01	2897
GO:0098800	inner mitochondrial membrane protein complex	cellular_component	26.12	4.55E-12	3.76E-10	9.76E-01	125
GO:0008033	tRNA processing	biological_process	25.79	6.31E-12	5.19E-10	9.82E-01	114
GO:0003735	structural constituent of ribosome	molecular_function	25.79	6.33E-12	5.19E-10	9.56E-01	158
GO:0019787	ubiquitin-like protein transferase activity	molecular_function	25.77	6.43E-12	5.25E-10	8.92E-01	378
GO:1901698	response to nitrogen compound	biological_process	25.76	6.53E-12	5.31E-10	8.63E-01	619
GO:0030234	enzyme regulator activity	molecular_function	25.61	7.57E-12	6.14E-10	8.48E-01	818
GO:0050821	protein stabilization	biological_process	25.58	7.74E-12	6.25E-10	9.52E-01	165
GO:0004842	ubiquitin-protein transferase activity	molecular_function	25.50	8.40E-12	6.76E-10	8.94E-01	359
GO:0034622	cellular protein-containing complex assembly	N/A	25.37	9.57E-12	7.67E-10	8.64E-01	590
GO:0000151	ubiquitin ligase complex	cellular_component	25.26	1.07E-11	8.51E-10	9.12E-01	273
GO:0007005	mitochondrion organization	biological_process	25.21	1.12E-11	8.94E-10	9.10E-01	279
GO:0060589	nucleoside-triphosphatase regulator activity	molecular_function	25.17	1.17E-11	9.31E-10	9.09E-01	285
GO:0003713	transcription coactivator activity	molecular_function	25.08	1.29E-11	1.02E-09	9.21E-01	240
GO:0140297	DNA-binding transcription factor binding	molecular_function	24.74	1.79E-11	1.41E-09	8.95E-01	343
GO:0007033	vacuole organization	biological_process	24.72	1.84E-11	1.44E-09	9.82E-01	110
GO:0000956	nuclear-transcribed mRNA catabolic process	biological_process	24.70	1.88E-11	1.47E-09	1.00E+00	87
GO:0006979	response to oxidative stress	biological_process	24.59	2.09E-11	1.63E-09	9.08E-01	282
GO:0016788	hydrolase activity, acting on ester bonds	molecular_function	24.39	2.55E-11	1.98E-09	8.59E-01	625
GO:0006888	endoplasmic reticulum to Golgi vesicle-mediated transport	biological_process	24.33	2.72E-11	2.10E-09	9.90E-01	98
GO:0060341	regulation of cellular localization	biological_process	23.86	4.35E-11	3.35E-09	8.48E-01	764
GO:0051247	positive regulation of protein metabolic process	biological_process	23.74	4.92E-11	3.77E-09	8.21E-01	1460
GO:0016241	regulation of macroautophagy	biological_process	23.65	5.36E-11	4.09E-09	9.81E-01	106
GO:0051236	establishment of RNA localization	biological_process	23.60	5.61E-11	4.26E-09	9.57E-01	141
GO:0008757	S-adenosylmethionine-dependent methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	23.60	5.61E-11	4.26E-09	9.57E-01	141
GO:0097708	intracellular vesicle	cellular_component	23.32	7.45E-11	5.64E-09	8.20E-01	1465
GO:0050657	nucleic acid transport	biological_process	23.12	9.12E-11	6.85E-09	9.57E-01	139
GO:0050658	RNA transport	biological_process	23.12	9.12E-11	6.85E-09	9.57E-01	139
GO:0031410	cytoplasmic vesicle	cellular_component	23.03	9.93E-11	7.43E-09	8.20E-01	1462
GO:0098805	whole membrane	N/A	22.92	1.11E-10	8.29E-09	8.60E-01	578
GO:0065003	protein-containing complex assembly	biological_process	22.90	1.13E-10	8.42E-09	8.39E-01	895
GO:0008144	drug binding	molecular_function	22.87	1.17E-10	8.66E-09	8.20E-01	1451
GO:0008168	methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	22.79	1.26E-10	9.31E-09	9.31E-01	189
GO:0000122	negative regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II	biological_process	22.73	1.35E-10	9.89E-09	8.47E-01	750
GO:0000785	chromatin	cellular_component	22.45	1.78E-10	1.30E-08	8.76E-01	420
GO:0003729	mRNA binding	molecular_function	22.44	1.80E-10	1.31E-08	9.11E-01	246
GO:0033108	mitochondrial respiratory chain complex assembly	biological_process	22.42	1.83E-10	1.33E-08	1.00E+00	79
GO:0031982	vesicle	cellular_component	22.34	1.98E-10	1.43E-08	8.17E-01	1561
GO:0006351	transcription, DNA-templated	biological_process	22.33	2.00E-10	1.44E-08	9.05E-01	264

	regulation of proteolysis involved in cellular protein catabolic process							
GO:1903050	process	biological_process	22.33	2.01E-10	1.44E-08	9.23E-01	207	
GO:0010506	regulation of autophagy	biological_process	22.05	2.66E-10	1.91E-08	9.10E-01	244	
GO:0016741	transferase activity, transferring one-carbon groups	molecular_function	22.04	2.67E-10	1.91E-08	9.25E-01	199	
GO:0032259	methylation	biological_process	21.79	3.45E-10	2.46E-08	9.06E-01	255	
GO:1901135	carbohydrate derivative metabolic process	biological_process	21.70	3.75E-10	2.67E-08	8.55E-01	595	
GO:0032270	positive regulation of cellular protein metabolic process	N/A	21.70	3.78E-10	2.68E-08	8.21E-01	1355	
GO:0005759	mitochondrial matrix	cellular_component	21.67	3.87E-10	2.73E-08	9.60E-01	125	
GO:0010243	response to organonitrogen compound	biological_process	21.65	3.95E-10	2.78E-08	8.57E-01	574	
GO:0042802	identical protein binding	molecular_function	21.64	3.99E-10	2.80E-08	8.12E-01	1768	
GO:0031400	negative regulation of protein modification process	biological_process	21.63	4.04E-10	2.82E-08	8.61E-01	527	
GO:0030684	preribosome	cellular_component	21.57	4.30E-10	3.00E-08	1.00E+00	76	
GO:0061695	transferase complex, transferring phosphorus-containing groups	cellular_component	21.56	4.35E-10	3.02E-08	9.26E-01	190	
GO:0042393	histone binding	molecular_function	21.50	4.59E-10	3.18E-08	9.29E-01	183	
GO:0080135	regulation of cellular response to stress	biological_process	21.43	4.93E-10	3.41E-08	8.51E-01	644	
GO:0046700	heterocycle catabolic process	biological_process	21.41	5.03E-10	3.45E-08	9.05E-01	253	
GO:0031301	integral component of organelle membrane	cellular_component	21.41	5.04E-10	3.45E-08	8.96E-01	289	
GO:0097659	nucleic acid-templated transcription	biological_process	21.38	5.17E-10	3.53E-08	9.02E-01	265	
GO:0006259	DNA metabolic process	biological_process	21.19	6.29E-10	4.29E-08	8.55E-01	586	
GO:0007034	vacuolar transport	biological_process	21.18	6.32E-10	4.29E-08	9.59E-01	123	
GO:0005622	intracellular	cellular_component	21.17	6.39E-10	4.33E-08	8.68E-01	455	
GO:0008219	cell death	biological_process	21.14	6.61E-10	4.46E-08	8.49E-01	667	
GO:1901699	cellular response to nitrogen compound	biological_process	21.12	6.70E-10	4.50E-08	8.84E-01	345	
GO:0005684	U2-type spliceosomal complex	cellular_component	21.04	7.32E-10	4.91E-08	9.88E-01	86	
GO:0012501	programmed cell death	biological_process	20.93	8.11E-10	5.42E-08	8.51E-01	630	
GO:0098588	bounding membrane of organelle	cellular_component	20.91	8.27E-10	5.51E-08	8.42E-01	760	
GO:0010941	regulation of cell death	biological_process	20.87	8.60E-10	5.71E-08	8.16E-01	1485	
GO:0061136	regulation of proteasomal protein catabolic process	biological_process	20.86	8.70E-10	5.76E-08	9.28E-01	180	
GO:0005773	vacuole	cellular_component	20.85	8.78E-10	5.80E-08	8.71E-01	426	
GO:0006281	DNA repair	biological_process	20.83	9.02E-10	5.94E-08	8.72E-01	415	
GO:0000209	protein polyubiquitination	biological_process	20.82	9.08E-10	5.96E-08	9.31E-01	173	
GO:0044270	cellular nitrogen compound catabolic process	biological_process	20.66	1.07E-09	6.98E-08	9.04E-01	249	
GO:0043543	protein acylation	biological_process	20.61	1.12E-09	7.31E-08	9.40E-01	151	
GO:0044403	symbiotic process	biological_process	20.58	1.15E-09	7.50E-08	9.37E-01	158	
GO:0045182	translation regulator activity	molecular_function	20.45	1.32E-09	8.53E-08	9.58E-01	120	
GO:0005856	cytoskeleton	cellular_component	20.44	1.32E-09	8.55E-08	8.19E-01	1351	
GO:0019439	aromatic compound catabolic process	biological_process	20.28	1.56E-09	1.00E-07	9.00E-01	259	
GO:0019900	kinase binding	molecular_function	20.23	1.64E-09	1.05E-07	8.40E-01	769	
GO:0010508	positive regulation of autophagy	biological_process	20.21	1.68E-09	1.08E-07	9.58E-01	119	
GO:0043414	macromolecule methylation	biological_process	20.19	1.71E-09	1.09E-07	9.16E-01	203	
GO:0019843	rRNA binding	molecular_function	20.15	1.78E-09	1.13E-07	1.00E+00	71	
GO:0031399	regulation of protein modification process	biological_process	20.14	1.79E-09	1.13E-07	8.13E-01	1573	
GO:0051130	positive regulation of cellular component organization	biological_process	20.14	1.80E-09	1.14E-07	8.24E-01	1133	

GO:0031300	intrinsic component of organelle membrane	cellular_component	20.12	1.83E-09	1.15E-07	8.85E-01	322
GO:0016032	viral process	biological_process	20.01	2.05E-09	1.29E-07	9.64E-01	110
GO:0006091	generation of precursor metabolites and energy	biological_process	19.94	2.18E-09	1.37E-07	9.06E-01	233
GO:0044798	nuclear transcription factor complex	N/A	19.88	2.32E-09	1.45E-07	9.23E-01	182
GO:0045944	positive regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II	biological_process	19.78	2.56E-09	1.60E-07	8.28E-01	1016
GO:0070646	protein modification by small protein removal	biological_process	19.76	2.63E-09	1.63E-07	9.63E-01	109
GO:0042221	response to chemical	biological_process	19.74	2.68E-09	1.66E-07	8.04E-01	2073
GO:0006605	protein targeting	biological_process	19.70	2.79E-09	1.73E-07	9.35E-01	154
GO:0051726	regulation of cell cycle	biological_process	19.69	2.80E-09	1.73E-07	8.32E-01	910
GO:0070887	cellular response to chemical stimulus	biological_process	19.69	2.81E-09	1.73E-07	8.16E-01	1412
GO:1902493	acetyltransferase complex	cellular_component	19.67	2.86E-09	1.74E-07	9.78E-01	91
GO:0031248	protein acetyltransferase complex	cellular_component	19.67	2.86E-09	1.74E-07	9.78E-01	91
GO:0006915	apoptotic process	biological_process	19.56	3.19E-09	1.94E-07	8.50E-01	594
GO:0044087	regulation of cellular component biogenesis	biological_process	19.40	3.77E-09	2.29E-07	8.32E-01	888
GO:1903311	regulation of mRNA metabolic process	biological_process	19.38	3.84E-09	2.33E-07	9.04E-01	230
GO:0019901	protein kinase binding	molecular_function	19.29	4.18E-09	2.53E-07	8.43E-01	687
GO:0018193	peptidyl-amino acid modification	biological_process	19.27	4.26E-09	2.56E-07	8.44E-01	662
GO:0006914	autophagy	biological_process	19.27	4.29E-09	2.56E-07	9.17E-01	192
GO:0035770	ribonucleoprotein granule	cellular_component	19.27	4.29E-09	2.56E-07	9.17E-01	192
GO:0061919	process utilizing autophagic mechanism	biological_process	19.27	4.29E-09	2.56E-07	9.17E-01	192
GO:0061629	RNA polymerase II-specific DNA-binding transcription factor binding	molecular_function	19.23	4.45E-09	2.65E-07	8.94E-01	265
GO:0032868	response to insulin	biological_process	18.99	5.65E-09	3.35E-07	9.56E-01	114
GO:0034708	methyltransferase complex	cellular_component	18.99	5.65E-09	3.35E-07	9.56E-01	114
GO:0051186	cofactor metabolic process	biological_process	18.96	5.82E-09	3.44E-07	8.83E-01	315
GO:0140030	modification-dependent protein binding	molecular_function	18.85	6.51E-09	3.84E-07	9.41E-01	136
GO:0016772	transferase activity, transferring phosphorus-containing groups	molecular_function	18.84	6.54E-09	3.84E-07	8.33E-01	854
GO:0090407	organophosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	18.75	7.17E-09	4.20E-07	8.78E-01	336
GO:2001233	regulation of apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	18.74	7.29E-09	4.26E-07	8.70E-01	385
GO:0033044	regulation of chromosome organization	biological_process	18.67	7.76E-09	4.52E-07	8.75E-01	352
GO:1905368	peptidase complex	cellular_component	18.62	8.17E-09	4.75E-07	9.77E-01	87
GO:0010033	response to organic substance	biological_process	18.62	8.19E-09	4.75E-07	8.09E-01	1682
GO:2000058	regulation of ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process	biological_process	18.60	8.36E-09	4.83E-07	9.33E-01	149
GO:0015935	small ribosomal subunit	cellular_component	18.58	8.52E-09	4.91E-07	9.87E-01	77
GO:0019904	protein domain specific binding	molecular_function	18.53	8.92E-09	5.13E-07	8.39E-01	720
GO:0016482	cytosolic transport	biological_process	18.46	9.61E-09	5.51E-07	9.45E-01	127
GO:0005085	guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity	molecular_function	18.40	1.02E-08	5.82E-07	9.12E-01	194
GO:0018394	peptidyl-lysine acetylation	biological_process	18.37	1.05E-08	5.96E-07	9.68E-01	95
GO:0019783	ubiquitin-like protein-specific protease activity	molecular_function	18.37	1.05E-08	5.96E-07	9.68E-01	95
GO:0006475	internal protein amino acid acetylation	biological_process	18.37	1.05E-08	5.96E-07	9.68E-01	95
GO:0043067	regulation of programmed cell death	biological_process	18.27	1.17E-08	6.60E-07	8.15E-01	1350
GO:0017137	Rab GTPase binding	N/A	18.20	1.24E-08	7.01E-07	9.29E-01	154
GO:0070469	respirasome	cellular_component	18.15	1.31E-08	7.34E-07	1.00E+00	64

GO:0034976	response to endoplasmic reticulum stress regulation of proteasomal ubiquitin-dependent protein	biological_process	18.01	1.51E-08	8.45E-07	9.11E-01	192
GO:0032434	catabolic process	biological_process	18.00	1.52E-08	8.51E-07	9.44E-01	125
GO:0030695	GTPase regulator activity	molecular_function	17.94	1.61E-08	9.01E-07	8.94E-01	246
GO:0005096	GTPase activator activity	molecular_function	17.89	1.70E-08	9.44E-07	8.99E-01	228
GO:0035091	phosphatidylinositol binding	molecular_function	17.89	1.70E-08	9.44E-07	9.01E-01	222
GO:0001510	RNA methylation	biological_process	17.87	1.73E-08	9.61E-07	1.00E+00	63
GO:0090079	translation regulator activity, nucleic acid binding	molecular_function	17.86	1.75E-08	9.64E-07	9.68E-01	93
GO:0043209	myelin sheath	cellular_component	17.83	1.81E-08	9.98E-07	9.19E-01	172
GO:0051028	mRNA transport	biological_process	17.78	1.90E-08	1.05E-06	9.60E-01	101
GO:1903320	regulation of protein modification by small protein conjugation or removal	biological_process	17.71	2.03E-08	1.11E-06	8.99E-01	227
GO:0018393	internal peptidyl-lysine acetylation	biological_process	17.61	2.25E-08	1.23E-06	9.67E-01	92
GO:0016050	vesicle organization	biological_process	17.53	2.43E-08	1.32E-06	9.04E-01	208
GO:0071310	cellular response to organic substance	biological_process	17.51	2.48E-08	1.35E-06	8.19E-01	1143
GO:0006473	protein acetylation	biological_process	17.40	2.77E-08	1.50E-06	9.48E-01	115
GO:0055086	nucleobase-containing small molecule metabolic process	biological_process	17.35	2.91E-08	1.57E-06	8.66E-01	381
GO:0043022	ribosome binding	molecular_function	17.30	3.06E-08	1.65E-06	1.00E+00	61
GO:0040012	regulation of locomotion	biological_process	17.29	3.10E-08	1.67E-06	8.26E-01	925
GO:0010821	regulation of mitochondrion organization	biological_process	17.27	3.15E-08	1.69E-06	9.34E-01	136
GO:0006400	tRNA modification	biological_process	17.22	3.31E-08	1.77E-06	9.86E-01	72
GO:0019318	hexose metabolic process	biological_process	17.17	3.50E-08	1.87E-06	9.47E-01	114
GO:0005813	centrosome	cellular_component	17.15	3.55E-08	1.89E-06	8.52E-01	494
GO:1901653	cellular response to peptide	biological_process	17.14	3.59E-08	1.91E-06	9.26E-01	149
GO:2001252	positive regulation of chromosome organization	biological_process	17.09	3.80E-08	2.01E-06	9.12E-01	181
GO:0036464	cytoplasmic ribonucleoprotein granule	cellular_component	17.09	3.80E-08	2.01E-06	9.12E-01	181
GO:1990204	oxidoreductase complex	cellular_component	17.07	3.85E-08	2.03E-06	9.53E-01	106
GO:0000123	histone acetyltransferase complex	cellular_component	17.05	3.92E-08	2.07E-06	9.75E-01	81
GO:0051169	nuclear transport	biological_process	17.04	3.98E-08	2.08E-06	9.09E-01	187
GO:0006913	nucleocytoplasmic transport	biological_process	17.04	3.98E-08	2.08E-06	9.09E-01	187
GO:0048037	cofactor binding	molecular_function	17.02	4.07E-08	2.12E-06	8.59E-01	426
GO:0008173	RNA methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	17.02	4.07E-08	2.12E-06	1.00E+00	60
GO:0034250	positive regulation of cellular amide metabolic process	biological_process	16.87	4.70E-08	2.45E-06	9.29E-01	141
GO:0016491	oxidoreductase activity	molecular_function	16.86	4.75E-08	2.47E-06	8.41E-01	617
GO:0043254	regulation of protein-containing complex assembly	biological_process	16.83	4.90E-08	2.53E-06	8.61E-01	409
GO:1901137	carbohydrate derivative biosynthetic process	biological_process	16.81	5.00E-08	2.58E-06	8.81E-01	285
GO:0071013	catalytic step 2 spliceosome	cellular_component	16.79	5.09E-08	2.62E-06	9.75E-01	80
GO:0008080	N-acetyltransferase activity	molecular_function	16.79	5.09E-08	2.62E-06	9.75E-01	80
GO:0045732	positive regulation of protein catabolic process	biological_process	16.79	5.12E-08	2.62E-06	9.00E-01	210
GO:0006790	sulfur compound metabolic process	biological_process	16.65	5.86E-08	3.00E-06	8.94E-01	227
GO:0044093	positive regulation of molecular function	biological_process	16.61	6.14E-08	3.13E-06	8.12E-01	1317
GO:0016573	histone acetylation	biological_process	16.60	6.16E-08	3.14E-06	9.66E-01	88
GO:0065009	regulation of molecular function	biological_process	16.59	6.21E-08	3.15E-06	7.98E-01	2185
GO:0071417	cellular response to organonitrogen compound	biological_process	16.55	6.46E-08	3.27E-06	8.75E-01	311

GO:0006950	response to stress	biological_process	16.52	6.72E-08	3.40E-06	7.97E-01	2320
GO:0061659	ubiquitin-like protein ligase activity	molecular_function	16.51	6.78E-08	3.42E-06	8.92E-01	232
GO:0009895	negative regulation of catabolic process	biological_process	16.49	6.91E-08	3.48E-06	8.80E-01	283
GO:0019693	ribose phosphate metabolic process	biological_process	16.41	7.46E-08	3.74E-06	8.89E-01	243
GO:0034212	peptide N-acetyltransferase activity	molecular_function	16.41	7.46E-08	3.74E-06	9.86E-01	69
GO:0006839	mitochondrial transport	biological_process	16.41	7.49E-08	3.74E-06	9.41E-01	118
GO:0071375	cellular response to peptide hormone stimulus	biological_process	16.36	7.86E-08	3.92E-06	9.51E-01	103
GO:0050790	regulation of catalytic activity	biological_process	16.33	8.13E-08	4.04E-06	8.06E-01	1608
GO:0042594	response to starvation	biological_process	16.30	8.31E-08	4.12E-06	9.24E-01	145
GO:0098803	respiratory chain complex	cellular_component	16.27	8.57E-08	4.23E-06	9.74E-01	78
GO:0032869	cellular response to insulin stimulus	biological_process	16.27	8.57E-08	4.23E-06	9.74E-01	78
GO:0006457	protein folding	biological_process	16.23	8.91E-08	4.39E-06	9.28E-01	138
GO:0042981	regulation of apoptotic process	biological_process	16.21	9.12E-08	4.48E-06	8.11E-01	1326
GO:0032386	regulation of intracellular transport	biological_process	16.20	9.19E-08	4.50E-06	8.71E-01	325
GO:0000323	lytic vacuole	cellular_component	16.20	9.21E-08	4.50E-06	8.63E-01	373
GO:0005764	lysosome	cellular_component	16.20	9.21E-08	4.50E-06	8.63E-01	373
GO:0015934	large ribosomal subunit	cellular_component	16.17	9.53E-08	4.64E-06	9.35E-01	124
GO:0101005	ubiquitinyl hydrolase activity	molecular_function	16.10	1.02E-07	4.93E-06	9.65E-01	86
GO:0007041	lysosomal transport	biological_process	16.10	1.02E-07	4.93E-06	9.65E-01	86
GO:0016579	protein deubiquitination	biological_process	16.07	1.05E-07	5.09E-06	9.57E-01	94
GO:0045727	positive regulation of translation	biological_process	15.96	1.17E-07	5.67E-06	9.40E-01	116
GO:0061630	ubiquitin protein ligase activity	molecular_function	15.95	1.18E-07	5.70E-06	8.92E-01	223
GO:0008022	protein C-terminus binding	molecular_function	15.92	1.22E-07	5.85E-06	8.94E-01	217
GO:0030027	lamellipodium	cellular_component	15.89	1.25E-07	6.00E-06	9.17E-01	156
GO:0043436	oxoacid metabolic process	biological_process	15.86	1.29E-07	6.17E-06	8.35E-01	667
GO:0036459	thiol-dependent ubiquitinyl hydrolase activity	N/A	15.85	1.31E-07	6.24E-06	9.65E-01	85
GO:1905897	regulation of response to endoplasmic reticulum stress	biological_process	15.75	1.44E-07	6.83E-06	9.74E-01	76
GO:0008135	translation factor activity, RNA binding	molecular_function	15.75	1.44E-07	6.83E-06	9.74E-01	76
GO:1903364	positive regulation of cellular protein catabolic process	N/A	15.60	1.68E-07	7.96E-06	9.26E-01	135
GO:0090575	RNA polymerase II transcription factor complex	cellular_component	15.58	1.72E-07	8.13E-06	9.19E-01	148
GO:0005769	early endosome	cellular_component	15.57	1.73E-07	8.18E-06	8.93E-01	215
GO:0005777	peroxisome	cellular_component	15.51	1.84E-07	8.67E-06	9.34E-01	121
GO:0035257	nuclear hormone receptor binding	N/A	15.47	1.91E-07	8.95E-06	9.22E-01	141
GO:0090305	nucleic acid phosphodiester bond hydrolysis	biological_process	15.42	2.02E-07	9.47E-06	9.49E-01	99
GO:0016874	ligase activity	molecular_function	15.39	2.07E-07	9.70E-06	9.25E-01	134
GO:0016239	positive regulation of macroautophagy	biological_process	15.33	2.20E-07	1.03E-05	9.85E-01	65
GO:0006352	DNA-templated transcription, initiation	biological_process	15.31	2.24E-07	1.04E-05	1.00E+00	54
GO:1903828	negative regulation of cellular protein localization	biological_process	15.28	2.30E-07	1.07E-05	9.38E-01	113
GO:0031330	negative regulation of cellular catabolic process	biological_process	15.17	2.57E-07	1.19E-05	8.87E-01	230
GO:0050662	coenzyme binding	molecular_function	15.15	2.63E-07	1.22E-05	8.80E-01	258
GO:0019752	carboxylic acid metabolic process	biological_process	15.12	2.70E-07	1.25E-05	8.35E-01	636
GO:0022604	regulation of cell morphogenesis	biological_process	15.12	2.71E-07	1.25E-05	8.47E-01	478
GO:0005770	late endosome	cellular_component	15.09	2.78E-07	1.28E-05	9.14E-01	152

GO:0051129	negative regulation of cellular component organization	biological_process	15.06	2.87E-07	1.31E-05	8.32E-01	679
GO:1901701	cellular response to oxygen-containing compound	biological_process	15.01	3.01E-07	1.38E-05	8.35E-01	635
GO:0005815	microtubule organizing center	cellular_component	14.98	3.13E-07	1.43E-05	8.38E-01	581
GO:0017038	protein import	biological_process	14.97	3.15E-07	1.44E-05	9.24E-01	132
GO:0006753	nucleoside phosphate metabolic process	biological_process	14.96	3.18E-07	1.45E-05	8.66E-01	322
GO:1902903	regulation of supramolecular fiber organization	biological_process	14.90	3.39E-07	1.54E-05	8.62E-01	348
GO:0009966	regulation of signal transduction	biological_process	14.89	3.40E-07	1.54E-05	7.93E-01	2413
GO:0006082	organic acid metabolic process	biological_process	14.87	3.48E-07	1.57E-05	8.31E-01	682
GO:0006366	transcription by RNA polymerase II	biological_process	14.86	3.53E-07	1.59E-05	9.20E-01	138
GO:2000145	regulation of cell motility	biological_process	14.84	3.57E-07	1.61E-05	8.22E-01	867
GO:0006163	purine nucleotide metabolic process	biological_process	14.79	3.78E-07	1.70E-05	8.83E-01	239
GO:0008234	cysteine-type peptidase activity	molecular_function	14.77	3.86E-07	1.73E-05	9.17E-01	144
GO:0004518	nuclease activity	molecular_function	14.77	3.87E-07	1.73E-05	9.03E-01	175
GO:0006413	translational initiation	biological_process	14.74	3.95E-07	1.76E-05	1.00E+00	52
GO:0009259	ribonucleotide metabolic process	biological_process	14.73	4.02E-07	1.79E-05	8.84E-01	233
GO:0030334	regulation of cell migration	biological_process	14.65	4.36E-07	1.94E-05	8.23E-01	832
GO:0032880	regulation of protein localization	biological_process	14.56	4.75E-07	2.11E-05	8.18E-01	962
GO:0099023	vesicle tethering complex	cellular_component	14.52	4.93E-07	2.18E-05	9.84E-01	62
GO:1905037	autophagosome organization	biological_process	14.52	4.93E-07	2.18E-05	9.84E-01	62
GO:0120114	Sm-like protein family complex	cellular_component	14.46	5.23E-07	2.30E-05	9.72E-01	71
GO:0005667	transcription factor complex	cellular_component	14.44	5.34E-07	2.35E-05	8.63E-01	329
GO:0016407	acetyltransferase activity	molecular_function	14.41	5.51E-07	2.42E-05	9.41E-01	102
GO:0007030	Golgi organization	biological_process	14.40	5.60E-07	2.45E-05	9.36E-01	109
GO:0046983	protein dimerization activity	molecular_function	14.37	5.75E-07	2.51E-05	8.23E-01	815
GO:0016817	hydrolase activity, acting on acid anhydrides	molecular_function	14.34	5.92E-07	2.58E-05	8.27E-01	739
GO:0016818	hydrolase activity, acting on acid anhydrides, in phosphorus-containing anhydrides	molecular_function	14.34	5.92E-07	2.58E-05	8.27E-01	739
GO:0030162	regulation of proteolysis	biological_process	14.30	6.16E-07	2.67E-05	8.37E-01	575
GO:1902275	regulation of chromatin organization	biological_process	14.28	6.30E-07	2.73E-05	8.93E-01	196
GO:0000049	tRNA binding	molecular_function	14.25	6.45E-07	2.78E-05	9.84E-01	61
GO:1905369	endopeptidase complex	cellular_component	14.25	6.45E-07	2.78E-05	9.84E-01	61
GO:0061733	peptide-lysine-N-acetyltransferase activity	molecular_function	14.25	6.45E-07	2.78E-05	9.84E-01	61
GO:0043085	positive regulation of catalytic activity	biological_process	14.25	6.46E-07	2.78E-05	8.16E-01	991
GO:0032006	regulation of TOR signaling	biological_process	14.25	6.50E-07	2.79E-05	9.47E-01	94
GO:0046390	ribose phosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	14.20	6.78E-07	2.90E-05	9.30E-01	115
GO:0048471	perinuclear region of cytoplasm	cellular_component	14.20	6.79E-07	2.90E-05	8.36E-01	579
GO:0071011	precatalytic spliceosome	cellular_component	14.18	6.98E-07	2.97E-05	1.00E+00	50
GO:1902532	negative regulation of intracellular signal transduction	biological_process	14.14	7.22E-07	3.07E-05	8.44E-01	475
GO:0016462	pyrophosphatase activity	molecular_function	14.14	7.24E-07	3.07E-05	8.26E-01	737
GO:0042579	microbody	cellular_component	14.14	7.24E-07	3.07E-05	9.22E-01	128
GO:0031396	regulation of protein ubiquitination	biological_process	14.10	7.50E-07	3.17E-05	8.92E-01	195
GO:0007006	mitochondrial membrane organization	biological_process	14.02	8.19E-07	3.46E-05	9.46E-01	93
GO:0000315	organellar large ribosomal subunit	cellular_component	13.99	8.44E-07	3.53E-05	9.83E-01	60
GO:0000502	proteasome complex	cellular_component	13.99	8.44E-07	3.53E-05	9.83E-01	60

GO:0030532	small nuclear ribonucleoprotein complex	cellular_component	13.99	8.44E-07	3.53E-05	9.83E-01	60
GO:0005762	mitochondrial large ribosomal subunit	cellular_component	13.99	8.44E-07	3.53E-05	9.83E-01	60
GO:1901361	organic cyclic compound catabolic process	biological_process	13.94	8.80E-07	3.68E-05	8.69E-01	283
GO:0033157	regulation of intracellular protein transport	biological_process	13.89	9.26E-07	3.84E-05	8.86E-01	211
GO:0045271	respiratory chain complex I	cellular_component	13.89	9.27E-07	3.84E-05	1.00E+00	49
GO:0030964	NADH dehydrogenase complex	cellular_component	13.89	9.27E-07	3.84E-05	1.00E+00	49
GO:0005747	mitochondrial respiratory chain complex I	cellular_component	13.89	9.27E-07	3.84E-05	1.00E+00	49
GO:0051099	positive regulation of binding	biological_process	13.87	9.47E-07	3.92E-05	8.96E-01	182
GO:0004843	thiol-dependent ubiquitin-specific protease activity	molecular_function	13.86	9.54E-07	3.94E-05	9.61E-01	77
GO:0044255	cellular lipid metabolic process	biological_process	13.83	9.87E-07	4.07E-05	8.29E-01	672
GO:0009117	nucleotide metabolic process	biological_process	13.81	1.01E-06	4.14E-05	8.63E-01	314
GO:0043565	sequence-specific DNA binding	molecular_function	13.79	1.02E-06	4.20E-05	8.18E-01	921
GO:0032182	ubiquitin-like protein binding	molecular_function	13.78	1.03E-06	4.23E-05	9.46E-01	92
GO:0004402	histone acetyltransferase activity	molecular_function	13.72	1.10E-06	4.51E-05	9.83E-01	59
GO:0051188	cofactor biosynthetic process	biological_process	13.69	1.14E-06	4.65E-05	9.07E-01	151
GO:1902531	regulation of intracellular signal transduction	biological_process	13.68	1.15E-06	4.68E-05	8.05E-01	1407
GO:0017048	Rho GTPase binding	N/A	13.67	1.16E-06	4.73E-05	9.04E-01	157
GO:0005198	structural molecule activity	molecular_function	13.66	1.17E-06	4.75E-05	8.43E-01	466
GO:0005774	vacuolar membrane	cellular_component	13.57	1.27E-06	5.17E-05	9.13E-01	138
GO:0009267	cellular response to starvation	biological_process	13.52	1.34E-06	5.43E-05	9.20E-01	125
GO:0006405	RNA export from nucleus	biological_process	13.44	1.46E-06	5.89E-05	9.70E-01	67
GO:0004527	exonuclease activity	molecular_function	13.37	1.56E-06	6.29E-05	9.60E-01	75
GO:0042803	protein homodimerization activity	molecular_function	13.36	1.58E-06	6.34E-05	8.33E-01	581
GO:0071005	U2-type precatalytic spliceosome	cellular_component	13.32	1.64E-06	6.57E-05	1.00E+00	47
GO:0003714	transcription corepressor activity	molecular_function	13.31	1.65E-06	6.62E-05	8.96E-01	173
GO:0001067	regulatory region nucleic acid binding	molecular_function	13.27	1.72E-06	6.89E-05	8.22E-01	780
GO:0031667	response to nutrient levels	biological_process	13.22	1.82E-06	7.26E-05	8.70E-01	262
GO:0000045	autophagosome assembly	biological_process	13.18	1.88E-06	7.48E-05	9.82E-01	57
GO:0001098	basal transcription machinery binding	molecular_function	13.18	1.88E-06	7.48E-05	9.82E-01	57
GO:0001099	basal RNA polymerase II transcription machinery binding	molecular_function	13.18	1.88E-06	7.48E-05	9.82E-01	57
GO:0008270	zinc ion binding	molecular_function	13.13	1.99E-06	7.88E-05	8.33E-01	574
GO:0003727	single-stranded RNA binding	molecular_function	13.13	1.99E-06	7.89E-05	9.59E-01	74
GO:0009150	purine ribonucleotide metabolic process	biological_process	13.10	2.05E-06	8.08E-05	8.79E-01	223
GO:0035097	histone methyltransferase complex	cellular_component	13.09	2.06E-06	8.12E-05	9.44E-01	89
GO:0046914	transition metal ion binding	molecular_function	13.05	2.14E-06	8.42E-05	8.21E-01	773
GO:0032981	mitochondrial respiratory chain complex I assembly	biological_process	13.04	2.17E-06	8.52E-05	1.00E+00	46
GO:0010257	NADH dehydrogenase complex assembly	biological_process	13.04	2.17E-06	8.52E-05	1.00E+00	46
GO:0005975	carbohydrate metabolic process	biological_process	13.02	2.21E-06	8.62E-05	8.54E-01	355
GO:0006732	coenzyme metabolic process	biological_process	13.02	2.21E-06	8.62E-05	8.91E-01	183
GO:0006629	lipid metabolic process	biological_process	13.02	2.21E-06	8.63E-05	8.18E-01	852
GO:0034504	protein localization to nucleus	biological_process	12.95	2.38E-06	9.27E-05	9.08E-01	141
GO:0030176	integral component of endoplasmic reticulum membrane	cellular_component	12.92	2.44E-06	9.47E-05	9.27E-01	109
GO:0009260	ribonucleotide biosynthetic process	biological_process	12.92	2.44E-06	9.47E-05	9.27E-01	109
GO:0045936	negative regulation of phosphate metabolic process	biological_process	12.91	2.49E-06	9.60E-05	8.38E-01	499

GO:0010563	negative regulation of phosphorus metabolic process	biological_process	12.91	2.49E-06	9.60E-05	8.38E-01	499
GO:0044212	transcription regulatory region DNA binding	N/A	12.90	2.51E-06	9.66E-05	8.21E-01	776
GO:0051082	unfolded protein binding	molecular_function	12.86	2.59E-06	9.97E-05	9.43E-01	88
GO:1903829	positive regulation of cellular protein localization	biological_process	12.79	2.79E-06	1.07E-04	8.63E-01	291
GO:0035556	intracellular signal transduction	biological_process	12.78	2.82E-06	1.08E-04	8.07E-01	1197
GO:1990928	response to amino acid starvation	biological_process	12.76	2.89E-06	1.10E-04	1.00E+00	45
GO:0051427	hormone receptor binding	molecular_function	12.74	2.93E-06	1.12E-04	8.99E-01	158
GO:0005925	focal adhesion	cellular_component	12.73	2.95E-06	1.13E-04	9.01E-01	152
GO:0008276	protein methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	12.71	3.01E-06	1.15E-04	9.50E-01	80
GO:0009055	electron transfer activity	molecular_function	12.67	3.13E-06	1.19E-04	9.69E-01	64
GO:0072521	purine-containing compound metabolic process	biological_process	12.67	3.15E-06	1.19E-04	8.66E-01	269
GO:0097525	spliceosomal snRNP complex	cellular_component	12.65	3.21E-06	1.22E-04	9.82E-01	55
GO:0050684	regulation of mRNA processing	biological_process	12.60	3.39E-06	1.28E-04	9.10E-01	133
GO:0072522	purine-containing compound biosynthetic process	biological_process	12.60	3.39E-06	1.28E-04	9.21E-01	114
GO:1901652	response to peptide	biological_process	12.58	3.43E-06	1.29E-04	8.70E-01	247
GO:0016747	transferase activity, transferring acyl groups other than amino-acyl groups	molecular_function	12.57	3.49E-06	1.31E-04	8.82E-01	203
GO:0031072	heat shock protein binding	molecular_function	12.57	3.49E-06	1.31E-04	9.06E-01	139
GO:0016853	isomerase activity	molecular_function	12.55	3.54E-06	1.33E-04	9.03E-01	145
GO:0090150	establishment of protein localization to membrane	biological_process	12.55	3.55E-06	1.33E-04	9.01E-01	151
GO:0060548	negative regulation of cell death	biological_process	12.53	3.61E-06	1.35E-04	8.15E-01	902
GO:0042177	negative regulation of protein catabolic process	biological_process	12.51	3.70E-06	1.38E-04	9.17E-01	120
GO:0000428	DNA-directed RNA polymerase complex	cellular_component	12.47	3.83E-06	1.43E-04	1.00E+00	44
GO:0031965	nuclear membrane	cellular_component	12.46	3.86E-06	1.43E-04	8.77E-01	219
GO:0042326	negative regulation of phosphorylation	biological_process	12.44	3.94E-06	1.46E-04	8.43E-01	421
GO:0022900	electron transport chain	biological_process	12.39	4.15E-06	1.54E-04	9.58E-01	71
GO:0034599	cellular response to oxidative stress	biological_process	12.38	4.21E-06	1.56E-04	8.97E-01	156
GO:0034249	negative regulation of cellular amide metabolic process	biological_process	12.38	4.22E-06	1.56E-04	9.06E-01	138
GO:0007346	regulation of mitotic cell cycle	biological_process	12.36	4.29E-06	1.58E-04	8.36E-01	499
GO:0031967	organelle envelope	cellular_component	12.34	4.39E-06	1.61E-04	8.88E-01	179
GO:0031975	envelope	cellular_component	12.34	4.39E-06	1.61E-04	8.88E-01	179
GO:0045444	fat cell differentiation	biological_process	12.31	4.52E-06	1.65E-04	9.16E-01	119
GO:0046488	phosphatidylinositol metabolic process	biological_process	12.31	4.52E-06	1.65E-04	9.16E-01	119
GO:0032549	ribonucleoside binding	molecular_function	12.29	4.62E-06	1.69E-04	8.53E-01	334
GO:0042147	retrograde transport, endosome to Golgi	biological_process	12.24	4.82E-06	1.76E-04	9.49E-01	78
GO:0031984	organelle subcompartment	cellular_component	12.23	4.88E-06	1.78E-04	8.68E-01	250
GO:0051270	regulation of cellular component movement	biological_process	12.21	4.99E-06	1.81E-04	8.13E-01	935
GO:0031056	regulation of histone modification	biological_process	12.20	5.04E-06	1.83E-04	8.97E-01	155
GO:0007264	small GTPase mediated signal transduction	biological_process	12.19	5.07E-06	1.83E-04	8.63E-01	271
GO:0043038	amino acid activation	biological_process	12.19	5.09E-06	1.84E-04	1.00E+00	43
GO:0055029	nuclear DNA-directed RNA polymerase complex	cellular_component	12.19	5.09E-06	1.84E-04	1.00E+00	43
GO:0005996	monosaccharide metabolic process	biological_process	12.19	5.10E-06	1.84E-04	9.05E-01	137
GO:0032436	positive regulation of proteasomal ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process	biological_process	12.18	5.13E-06	1.84E-04	9.41E-01	85

GO:0008170	N-methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	12.18	5.13E-06	1.84E-04	9.41E-01	85
GO:0004386	helicase activity	molecular_function	12.18	5.14E-06	1.84E-04	9.02E-01	143
GO:0004540	ribonuclease activity	molecular_function	12.18	5.14E-06	1.84E-04	9.35E-01	92
GO:0006897	endocytosis	biological_process	12.15	5.26E-06	1.88E-04	8.62E-01	276
GO:0000118	histone deacetylase complex	cellular_component	12.15	5.29E-06	1.88E-04	9.57E-01	70
GO:0031123	RNA 3'-end processing	biological_process	12.15	5.29E-06	1.88E-04	9.57E-01	70
GO:0071495	cellular response to endogenous stimulus	biological_process	12.11	5.50E-06	1.95E-04	8.33E-01	521
GO:0000790	nuclear chromatin	N/A	12.09	5.61E-06	1.99E-04	8.64E-01	265
GO:1901800	positive regulation of proteasomal protein catabolic process	biological_process	12.08	5.66E-06	2.00E-04	9.24E-01	105
GO:0001933	negative regulation of protein phosphorylation	biological_process	12.08	5.68E-06	2.00E-04	8.47E-01	378
GO:0030029	actin filament-based process	biological_process	12.08	5.68E-06	2.00E-04	8.47E-01	378
GO:0001882	nucleoside binding	molecular_function	12.00	6.15E-06	2.17E-04	8.51E-01	342
GO:0045862	positive regulation of proteolysis	biological_process	11.96	6.39E-06	2.25E-04	8.55E-01	311
GO:0009991	response to extracellular stimulus	biological_process	11.95	6.47E-06	2.27E-04	8.60E-01	285
GO:0070585	protein localization to mitochondrion	biological_process	11.91	6.70E-06	2.35E-04	9.67E-01	61
GO:0047485	protein N-terminus binding	molecular_function	11.91	6.74E-06	2.36E-04	9.15E-01	117
GO:1903052	positive regulation of proteolysis involved in cellular protein catabolic process	biological_process	11.91	6.74E-06	2.36E-04	9.15E-01	117
GO:0043039	tRNA aminoacylation	biological_process	11.90	6.76E-06	2.36E-04	1.00E+00	42
GO:0005801	cis-Golgi network	cellular_component	11.90	6.76E-06	2.36E-04	1.00E+00	42
GO:0032550	purine ribonucleoside binding	molecular_function	11.89	6.83E-06	2.37E-04	8.52E-01	331
GO:0051348	negative regulation of transferase activity	biological_process	11.89	6.85E-06	2.38E-04	8.69E-01	237
GO:0016667	oxidoreductase activity, acting on a sulfur group of donors	molecular_function	11.85	7.15E-06	2.48E-04	9.81E-01	52
GO:0051345	positive regulation of hydrolase activity	biological_process	11.85	7.16E-06	2.48E-04	8.36E-01	470
GO:0051168	nuclear export	biological_process	11.79	7.57E-06	2.62E-04	9.28E-01	97
GO:0009968	negative regulation of signal transduction	biological_process	11.79	7.61E-06	2.63E-04	8.08E-01	1062
GO:0043434	response to peptide hormone	biological_process	11.78	7.64E-06	2.63E-04	8.82E-01	187
GO:0036503	ERAD pathway	biological_process	11.78	7.68E-06	2.64E-04	9.47E-01	76
GO:1990542	mitochondrial transmembrane transport	biological_process	11.78	7.68E-06	2.64E-04	9.47E-01	76
GO:0030055	cell-substrate junction	cellular_component	11.73	8.04E-06	2.74E-04	8.90E-01	164
GO:0072329	monocarboxylic acid catabolic process	biological_process	11.73	8.06E-06	2.74E-04	9.40E-01	83
GO:0048524	positive regulation of viral process	biological_process	11.73	8.06E-06	2.74E-04	9.40E-01	83
GO:0006006	glucose metabolic process	biological_process	11.73	8.06E-06	2.74E-04	9.40E-01	83
GO:0006892	post-Golgi vesicle-mediated transport	biological_process	11.73	8.06E-06	2.74E-04	9.40E-01	83
GO:0019207	kinase regulator activity	molecular_function	11.72	8.14E-06	2.77E-04	8.84E-01	181
GO:0051098	regulation of binding	biological_process	11.72	8.17E-06	2.77E-04	8.47E-01	365
GO:0017148	negative regulation of translation	biological_process	11.66	8.61E-06	2.91E-04	9.10E-01	122
GO:0001650	fibrillar center	cellular_component	11.66	8.61E-06	2.91E-04	9.10E-01	122
GO:0005525	GTP binding	molecular_function	11.65	8.73E-06	2.95E-04	8.52E-01	324
GO:0043484	regulation of RNA splicing	biological_process	11.64	8.85E-06	2.98E-04	9.06E-01	128
GO:0001883	purine nucleoside binding	molecular_function	11.63	8.93E-06	3.01E-04	8.50E-01	334
GO:0034198	cellular response to amino acid starvation	biological_process	11.62	8.98E-06	3.02E-04	1.00E+00	41
GO:0003690	double-stranded DNA binding	molecular_function	11.61	9.07E-06	3.04E-04	8.16E-01	799

GO:2000060	positive regulation of ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process	biological_process	11.58	9.37E-06	3.14E-04	9.27E-01	96
GO:0006164	purine nucleotide biosynthetic process	biological_process	11.58	9.39E-06	3.14E-04	9.17E-01	109
GO:0006997	nucleus organization	biological_process	11.54	9.70E-06	3.24E-04	9.47E-01	75
GO:0042578	phosphoric ester hydrolase activity	molecular_function	11.53	9.81E-06	3.27E-04	8.52E-01	318
GO:0010008	endosome membrane	cellular_component	11.49	1.02E-05	3.40E-04	8.85E-01	174
GO:0010594	regulation of endothelial cell migration	biological_process	11.46	1.06E-05	3.51E-04	8.97E-01	145
GO:0022904	respiratory electron transport chain	biological_process	11.42	1.09E-05	3.62E-04	9.55E-01	67
GO:0000932	P-body	cellular_component	11.42	1.09E-05	3.62E-04	9.55E-01	67
GO:0090734	site of DNA damage	cellular_component	11.42	1.09E-05	3.62E-04	9.55E-01	67
GO:0070482	response to oxygen levels	biological_process	11.39	1.13E-05	3.74E-04	8.83E-01	179
GO:0016458	gene silencing	biological_process	11.37	1.15E-05	3.79E-04	9.17E-01	108
GO:0016875	ligase activity, forming carbon-oxygen bonds	molecular_function	11.34	1.19E-05	3.92E-04	1.00E+00	40
GO:0004812	aminoacyl-tRNA ligase activity	molecular_function	11.34	1.19E-05	3.92E-04	1.00E+00	40
GO:0006890	retrograde vesicle-mediated transport, Golgi to endoplasmic reticulum	biological_process	11.34	1.19E-05	3.92E-04	1.00E+00	40
GO:0010942	positive regulation of cell death	biological_process	11.32	1.21E-05	3.97E-04	8.22E-01	656
GO:0031593	polyubiquitin modification-dependent protein binding	molecular_function	11.32	1.22E-05	3.97E-04	9.80E-01	50
GO:0010823	negative regulation of mitochondrion organization	biological_process	11.32	1.22E-05	3.97E-04	9.80E-01	50
GO:0030522	intracellular receptor signaling pathway	biological_process	11.31	1.22E-05	3.99E-04	9.46E-01	74
GO:0030433	ubiquitin-dependent ERAD pathway	biological_process	11.18	1.39E-05	4.53E-04	9.55E-01	66
GO:0031461	cullin-RING ubiquitin ligase complex	cellular_component	11.17	1.41E-05	4.58E-04	8.90E-01	155
GO:0070063	RNA polymerase binding	molecular_function	11.16	1.43E-05	4.62E-04	9.66E-01	58
GO:0098732	macromolecule deacylation	biological_process	11.16	1.43E-05	4.62E-04	9.66E-01	58
GO:0035601	protein deacylation	biological_process	11.16	1.43E-05	4.62E-04	9.66E-01	58
GO:0090501	RNA phosphodiester bond hydrolysis	biological_process	11.16	1.43E-05	4.62E-04	9.66E-01	58
GO:0009628	response to abiotic stimulus	biological_process	11.15	1.43E-05	4.62E-04	8.16E-01	766
GO:0043068	positive regulation of programmed cell death	biological_process	11.11	1.49E-05	4.81E-04	8.24E-01	602
GO:1901981	phosphatidylinositol phosphate binding	molecular_function	11.10	1.51E-05	4.87E-04	8.95E-01	143
GO:0043535	regulation of blood vessel endothelial cell migration	biological_process	11.09	1.53E-05	4.93E-04	9.31E-01	87
GO:0023051	regulation of signaling	biological_process	11.06	1.57E-05	5.06E-04	7.84E-01	2755
GO:0030490	maturation of SSU-rRNA	biological_process	11.05	1.58E-05	5.07E-04	1.00E+00	39
GO:0006418	tRNA aminoacylation for protein translation	biological_process	11.05	1.58E-05	5.07E-04	1.00E+00	39
GO:0060590	ATPase regulator activity	molecular_function	11.05	1.58E-05	5.07E-04	1.00E+00	39
GO:0009152	purine ribonucleotide biosynthetic process	biological_process	11.05	1.59E-05	5.08E-04	9.20E-01	100
GO:0062197	cellular response to chemical stress	biological_process	11.05	1.60E-05	5.08E-04	8.78E-01	188
GO:1901700	response to oxygen-containing compound	biological_process	10.99	1.69E-05	5.39E-04	8.09E-01	961
GO:0017111	nucleoside-triphosphatase activity	molecular_function	10.97	1.71E-05	5.44E-04	8.19E-01	685
GO:0046486	glycerolipid metabolic process	biological_process	10.96	1.74E-05	5.51E-04	8.60E-01	257
GO:0009719	response to endogenous stimulus	biological_process	10.95	1.76E-05	5.57E-04	8.18E-01	708
GO:0072655	establishment of protein localization to mitochondrion	biological_process	10.91	1.83E-05	5.78E-04	9.65E-01	57
GO:1903902	positive regulation of viral life cycle	biological_process	10.91	1.83E-05	5.78E-04	9.65E-01	57
GO:0005776	autophagosome	cellular_component	10.91	1.83E-05	5.78E-04	9.65E-01	57

GO:0005793	endoplasmic reticulum-Golgi intermediate compartment	cellular_component	10.91	1.83E-05	5.78E-04	9.65E-01	57
GO:0016779	nucleotidyltransferase activity	molecular_function	10.89	1.86E-05	5.84E-04	9.07E-01	118
GO:1990837	sequence-specific double-stranded DNA binding	molecular_function	10.87	1.91E-05	6.00E-04	8.17E-01	721
GO:0030036	actin cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	10.86	1.92E-05	6.01E-04	8.45E-01	343
GO:0043130	ubiquitin binding	molecular_function	10.85	1.94E-05	6.08E-04	9.44E-01	72
GO:0043087	regulation of GTPase activity	biological_process	10.84	1.96E-05	6.12E-04	8.55E-01	282
GO:0009165	nucleotide biosynthetic process	biological_process	10.83	1.99E-05	6.20E-04	8.89E-01	153
GO:0051338	regulation of transferase activity	biological_process	10.82	2.00E-05	6.24E-04	8.14E-01	799
GO:0071806	protein transmembrane transport	biological_process	10.79	2.06E-05	6.42E-04	9.79E-01	48
GO:0044419	interspecies interaction between organisms	biological_process	10.78	2.08E-05	6.45E-04	8.63E-01	240
GO:0010646	regulation of cell communication	biological_process	10.78	2.08E-05	6.45E-04	7.84E-01	2741
GO:0003697	single-stranded DNA binding	molecular_function	10.77	2.10E-05	6.49E-04	9.14E-01	105
GO:0000959	mitochondrial RNA metabolic process	biological_process	10.77	2.10E-05	6.51E-04	1.00E+00	38
GO:0051174	regulation of phosphorus metabolic process	biological_process	10.75	2.13E-05	6.59E-04	7.97E-01	1485
GO:0043065	positive regulation of apoptotic process	biological_process	10.73	2.19E-05	6.75E-04	8.23E-01	598
GO:0031227	intrinsic component of endoplasmic reticulum membrane	cellular_component	10.70	2.25E-05	6.93E-04	9.06E-01	117
GO:0019220	regulation of phosphate metabolic process	biological_process	10.69	2.28E-05	7.00E-04	7.96E-01	1484
GO:0048284	organelle fusion	biological_process	10.66	2.36E-05	7.24E-04	9.29E-01	85
GO:0016410	N-acyltransferase activity	molecular_function	10.64	2.39E-05	7.34E-04	9.18E-01	98
GO:0006497	protein lipidation	biological_process	10.61	2.46E-05	7.53E-04	9.36E-01	78
GO:0035966	response to topologically incorrect protein	biological_process	10.61	2.46E-05	7.53E-04	9.36E-01	78
GO:0031669	cellular response to nutrient levels	biological_process	10.60	2.49E-05	7.60E-04	8.83E-01	163
GO:2001234	negative regulation of apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	10.57	2.58E-05	7.86E-04	8.68E-01	212
GO:0003743	translation initiation factor activity	molecular_function	10.52	2.69E-05	8.16E-04	9.79E-01	47
GO:0030880	RNA polymerase complex	cellular_component	10.52	2.69E-05	8.16E-04	9.79E-01	47
GO:0065002	intracellular protein transmembrane transport	biological_process	10.52	2.69E-05	8.16E-04	9.79E-01	47
GO:0006479	protein methylation	biological_process	10.51	2.72E-05	8.23E-04	9.05E-01	116
GO:0008213	protein alkylation	biological_process	10.51	2.72E-05	8.23E-04	9.05E-01	116
GO:0005088	Ras guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity	N/A	10.51	2.73E-05	8.26E-04	9.02E-01	122
GO:0003899	DNA-directed 5'-3' RNA polymerase activity	molecular_function	10.48	2.80E-05	8.44E-04	1.00E+00	37
GO:0032922	circadian regulation of gene expression	biological_process	10.47	2.85E-05	8.60E-04	9.52E-01	63
GO:0030258	lipid modification	biological_process	10.44	2.94E-05	8.84E-04	8.83E-01	162
GO:0098796	membrane protein complex	cellular_component	10.29	3.38E-05	1.02E-03	8.07E-01	943
GO:0016310	phosphorylation	biological_process	10.28	3.42E-05	1.03E-03	8.10E-01	852
GO:0001525	angiogenesis	biological_process	10.28	3.45E-05	1.03E-03	8.57E-01	252
GO:0001666	response to hypoxia	biological_process	10.27	3.46E-05	1.04E-03	8.82E-01	161
GO:0031334	positive regulation of protein-containing complex assembly	biological_process	10.27	3.46E-05	1.04E-03	8.67E-01	210
GO:0042645	mitochondrial nucleoid	cellular_component	10.26	3.50E-05	1.04E-03	9.78E-01	46
GO:0007032	endosome organization	biological_process	10.26	3.50E-05	1.04E-03	9.78E-01	46
GO:0009295	nucleoid	cellular_component	10.26	3.50E-05	1.04E-03	9.78E-01	46
GO:1904949	ATPase complex	cellular_component	10.23	3.62E-05	1.07E-03	9.28E-01	83
GO:0016209	antioxidant activity	molecular_function	10.23	3.62E-05	1.07E-03	9.52E-01	62
GO:0030117	membrane coat	cellular_component	10.23	3.62E-05	1.07E-03	9.52E-01	62

GO:0006650	glycerophospholipid metabolic process	biological_process	10.23	3.62E-05	1.07E-03	8.69E-01	199
GO:0016791	phosphatase activity	molecular_function	10.22	3.64E-05	1.08E-03	8.60E-01	236
GO:0032040	small-subunit processome	cellular_component	10.20	3.71E-05	1.10E-03	1.00E+00	36
GO:0036293	response to decreased oxygen levels	biological_process	10.18	3.79E-05	1.12E-03	8.80E-01	166
GO:0017053	transcriptional repressor complex	cellular_component	10.17	3.83E-05	1.13E-03	9.34E-01	76
GO:0051493	regulation of cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	10.17	3.85E-05	1.13E-03	8.25E-01	526
GO:1905269	positive regulation of chromatin organization	biological_process	10.15	3.91E-05	1.15E-03	9.07E-01	108
GO:0042325	regulation of phosphorylation	biological_process	10.15	3.92E-05	1.15E-03	7.97E-01	1352
GO:0098791	Golgi subcompartment	cellular_component	10.15	3.92E-05	1.15E-03	8.62E-01	225
GO:0010632	regulation of epithelial cell migration	biological_process	10.13	4.01E-05	1.17E-03	8.66E-01	209
GO:0010648	negative regulation of cell communication	biological_process	10.10	4.09E-05	1.20E-03	8.01E-01	1156
GO:0016236	macroautophagy	biological_process	10.00	4.55E-05	1.32E-03	9.78E-01	45
GO:0022627	cytosolic small ribosomal subunit	cellular_component	10.00	4.55E-05	1.32E-03	9.78E-01	45
GO:0008333	endosome to lysosome transport	biological_process	10.00	4.55E-05	1.32E-03	9.78E-01	45
GO:0051536	iron-sulfur cluster binding	molecular_function	9.99	4.58E-05	1.33E-03	9.51E-01	61
GO:0051540	metal cluster binding	molecular_function	9.99	4.58E-05	1.33E-03	9.51E-01	61
GO:0030374	nuclear receptor transcription coactivator activity	molecular_function	9.99	4.58E-05	1.33E-03	9.51E-01	61
GO:0005643	nuclear pore	cellular_component	9.99	4.58E-05	1.33E-03	9.51E-01	61
GO:0016922	nuclear receptor binding	molecular_function	9.96	4.74E-05	1.37E-03	9.07E-01	107
GO:0006644	phospholipid metabolic process	biological_process	9.95	4.76E-05	1.37E-03	8.53E-01	265
GO:0003725	double-stranded RNA binding	molecular_function	9.95	4.77E-05	1.37E-03	9.33E-01	75
GO:0061013	regulation of mRNA catabolic process	biological_process	9.95	4.78E-05	1.37E-03	9.03E-01	113
GO:0022603	regulation of anatomical structure morphogenesis	biological_process	9.95	4.78E-05	1.37E-03	8.05E-01	961
GO:0070491	repressing transcription factor binding	N/A	9.94	4.84E-05	1.39E-03	9.41E-01	68
GO:0017112	Rab guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity	N/A	9.92	4.93E-05	1.41E-03	1.00E+00	35
GO:0000184	nuclear-transcribed mRNA catabolic process, nonsense-mediated decay	biological_process	9.92	4.93E-05	1.41E-03	1.00E+00	35
GO:1990391	DNA repair complex	cellular_component	9.92	4.93E-05	1.41E-03	1.00E+00	35
GO:1902115	regulation of organelle assembly	biological_process	9.83	5.37E-05	1.53E-03	8.69E-01	191
GO:0051052	regulation of DNA metabolic process	biological_process	9.81	5.51E-05	1.57E-03	8.40E-01	349
GO:0045335	phagocytic vesicle	cellular_component	9.80	5.53E-05	1.57E-03	9.26E-01	81
GO:1903363	negative regulation of cellular protein catabolic process	N/A	9.80	5.53E-05	1.57E-03	9.26E-01	81
GO:0032204	regulation of telomere maintenance	biological_process	9.80	5.53E-05	1.57E-03	9.26E-01	81
GO:1901293	nucleoside phosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	9.78	5.64E-05	1.60E-03	8.80E-01	158
GO:0023057	negative regulation of signaling	biological_process	9.77	5.74E-05	1.62E-03	8.00E-01	1160
GO:0043966	histone H3 acetylation	biological_process	9.73	5.92E-05	1.67E-03	9.77E-01	44
GO:0045646	regulation of erythrocyte differentiation	biological_process	9.73	5.92E-05	1.67E-03	9.77E-01	44
GO:0080171	lytic vacuole organization	biological_process	9.73	5.92E-05	1.67E-03	9.77E-01	44
GO:0031952	regulation of protein autophosphorylation	biological_process	9.73	5.92E-05	1.67E-03	9.77E-01	44
GO:0007040	lysosome organization	biological_process	9.73	5.92E-05	1.67E-03	9.77E-01	44
GO:0010822	positive regulation of mitochondrion organization	biological_process	9.73	5.93E-05	1.67E-03	9.32E-01	74
GO:2001235	positive regulation of apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	9.71	6.07E-05	1.70E-03	8.74E-01	174
GO:0005635	nuclear envelope	cellular_component	9.70	6.13E-05	1.72E-03	8.77E-01	163
GO:0009790	embryo development	biological_process	9.69	6.18E-05	1.73E-03	8.39E-01	348
GO:0044283	small molecule biosynthetic process	biological_process	9.68	6.26E-05	1.75E-03	8.35E-01	387

GO:2001020	regulation of response to DNA damage stimulus	biological_process	9.65	6.43E-05	1.79E-03	8.63E-01	211
GO:1903146	regulation of autophagy of mitochondrion	biological_process	9.63	6.55E-05	1.82E-03	1.00E+00	34
GO:0030120	vesicle coat	cellular_component	9.63	6.55E-05	1.82E-03	1.00E+00	34
GO:0030518	intracellular steroid hormone receptor signaling pathway	biological_process	9.63	6.55E-05	1.82E-03	1.00E+00	34
GO:0071496	cellular response to external stimulus	biological_process	9.62	6.66E-05	1.85E-03	8.61E-01	216
GO:0070925	organelle assembly	biological_process	9.59	6.87E-05	1.90E-03	8.29E-01	444
GO:0042826	histone deacetylase binding	molecular_function	9.58	6.92E-05	1.91E-03	9.01E-01	111
GO:0045185	maintenance of protein location	biological_process	9.58	6.92E-05	1.91E-03	9.05E-01	105
GO:0098852	lytic vacuole membrane	cellular_component	9.58	6.92E-05	1.91E-03	9.05E-01	105
GO:0005765	lysosomal membrane	cellular_component	9.58	6.92E-05	1.91E-03	9.05E-01	105
GO:0019001	guanyl nucleotide binding	molecular_function	9.57	6.99E-05	1.92E-03	8.39E-01	342
GO:0032561	guanyl ribonucleotide binding	molecular_function	9.57	6.99E-05	1.92E-03	8.39E-01	342
GO:0045454	cell redox homeostasis	biological_process	9.52	7.35E-05	2.02E-03	9.49E-01	59
GO:0000139	Golgi membrane	cellular_component	9.49	7.53E-05	2.07E-03	8.71E-01	178
GO:0032007	negative regulation of TOR signaling	biological_process	9.47	7.70E-05	2.11E-03	9.77E-01	43
GO:0009108	coenzyme biosynthetic process	biological_process	9.44	7.98E-05	2.18E-03	9.13E-01	92
GO:0008654	phospholipid biosynthetic process	biological_process	9.42	8.13E-05	2.22E-03	8.85E-01	139
GO:0043069	negative regulation of programmed cell death	biological_process	9.41	8.17E-05	2.23E-03	8.09E-01	800
GO:0048814	regulation of dendrite morphogenesis	biological_process	9.39	8.36E-05	2.28E-03	9.04E-01	104
GO:0044092	negative regulation of molecular function	biological_process	9.38	8.43E-05	2.29E-03	8.07E-01	845
GO:1903322	positive regulation of protein modification by small protein conjugation or removal	biological_process	9.36	8.62E-05	2.34E-03	8.87E-01	133
GO:0003674	molecular_function	molecular_function	9.35	8.66E-05	2.35E-03	7.57E-01	14938
GO:0017004	cytochrome complex assembly	biological_process	9.35	8.70E-05	2.35E-03	1.00E+00	33
GO:0006356	regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase I	biological_process	9.35	8.70E-05	2.35E-03	1.00E+00	33
GO:0008175	tRNA methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	9.35	8.70E-05	2.35E-03	1.00E+00	33
GO:0005811	lipid droplet	cellular_component	9.30	9.16E-05	2.48E-03	9.31E-01	72
GO:0032388	positive regulation of intracellular transport	biological_process	9.29	9.25E-05	2.50E-03	8.68E-01	182
GO:0051701	interaction with host	biological_process	9.28	9.29E-05	2.50E-03	9.48E-01	58
GO:1990841	promoter-specific chromatin binding	molecular_function	9.28	9.29E-05	2.50E-03	9.48E-01	58
GO:0098573	intrinsic component of mitochondrial membrane	cellular_component	9.26	9.53E-05	2.56E-03	9.38E-01	65
GO:0032870	cellular response to hormone stimulus	biological_process	9.23	9.81E-05	2.64E-03	8.61E-01	208
GO:0043175	RNA polymerase core enzyme binding	molecular_function	9.21	1.00E-04	2.67E-03	9.76E-01	42
GO:1902562	H4 histone acetyltransferase complex	cellular_component	9.21	1.00E-04	2.67E-03	9.76E-01	42
GO:1903573	negative regulation of response to endoplasmic reticulum stress	biological_process	9.21	1.00E-04	2.67E-03	9.76E-01	42
GO:0140296	general transcription initiation factor binding	molecular_function	9.21	1.00E-04	2.67E-03	9.76E-01	42
GO:0032092	positive regulation of protein binding	biological_process	9.21	1.00E-04	2.67E-03	9.07E-01	97
GO:0015980	energy derivation by oxidation of organic compounds	biological_process	9.20	1.01E-04	2.69E-03	9.03E-01	103
GO:0043487	regulation of RNA stability	biological_process	9.20	1.01E-04	2.69E-03	9.03E-01	103
GO:0048585	negative regulation of response to stimulus	biological_process	9.18	1.03E-04	2.75E-03	7.94E-01	1407
GO:0070603	SWI/SNF superfamily-type complex	cellular_component	9.17	1.04E-04	2.75E-03	9.23E-01	78
GO:0043393	regulation of protein binding	biological_process	9.17	1.04E-04	2.75E-03	8.58E-01	218
GO:0042054	histone methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	9.17	1.04E-04	2.76E-03	9.60E-01	50

GO:0032784	regulation of DNA-templated transcription, elongation	biological_process	9.17	1.04E-04	2.76E-03	9.60E-01	50
GO:0035861	site of double-strand break	cellular_component	9.17	1.04E-04	2.76E-03	9.60E-01	50
GO:0016301	kinase activity	molecular_function	9.16	1.05E-04	2.77E-03	8.12E-01	701
GO:0016311	dephosphorylation	biological_process	9.16	1.06E-04	2.78E-03	8.63E-01	197
GO:0000976	transcription regulatory region sequence-specific DNA binding	molecular_function	9.11	1.11E-04	2.91E-03	8.12E-01	682
GO:0016363	nuclear matrix	cellular_component	9.09	1.13E-04	2.96E-03	9.17E-01	84
GO:0033673	negative regulation of kinase activity	biological_process	9.09	1.13E-04	2.96E-03	8.60E-01	207
GO:0044089	positive regulation of cellular component biogenesis	biological_process	9.08	1.14E-04	2.98E-03	8.24E-01	477
GO:0043200	response to amino acid	biological_process	9.08	1.14E-04	2.98E-03	9.30E-01	71
GO:0019867	outer membrane	cellular_component	9.07	1.15E-04	3.00E-03	8.74E-01	159
GO:0031968	organelle outer membrane	cellular_component	9.07	1.15E-04	3.00E-03	8.74E-01	159
GO:0043628	ncRNA 3'-end processing	biological_process	9.07	1.15E-04	3.00E-03	1.00E+00	32
GO:0004532	exoribonuclease activity	molecular_function	9.07	1.15E-04	3.00E-03	1.00E+00	32
GO:0005669	transcription factor TFIID complex	cellular_component	9.07	1.15E-04	3.00E-03	1.00E+00	32
GO:0006367	transcription initiation from RNA polymerase II promoter	biological_process	9.07	1.15E-04	3.00E-03	1.00E+00	32
GO:0051054	positive regulation of DNA metabolic process	biological_process	8.98	1.26E-04	3.27E-03	8.61E-01	201
GO:0016746	transferase activity, transferring acyl groups	molecular_function	8.98	1.26E-04	3.27E-03	8.53E-01	232
GO:0070972	protein localization to endoplasmic reticulum	biological_process	8.95	1.30E-04	3.36E-03	9.76E-01	41
GO:0006406	mRNA export from nucleus	biological_process	8.95	1.30E-04	3.36E-03	9.76E-01	41
GO:0061650	ubiquitin-like protein conjugating enzyme activity	molecular_function	8.95	1.30E-04	3.36E-03	9.76E-01	41
GO:0120036	plasma membrane bounded cell projection organization	biological_process	8.92	1.33E-04	3.44E-03	8.17E-01	569
GO:0070936	protein K48-linked ubiquitination	biological_process	8.92	1.33E-04	3.44E-03	9.59E-01	49
GO:2001242	regulation of intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	8.92	1.34E-04	3.45E-03	8.73E-01	158
GO:0006338	chromatin remodeling	biological_process	8.92	1.34E-04	3.45E-03	8.91E-01	119
GO:0030335	positive regulation of cell migration	biological_process	8.86	1.42E-04	3.64E-03	8.20E-01	517
GO:0051336	regulation of hydrolase activity	biological_process	8.82	1.48E-04	3.79E-03	8.06E-01	824
GO:0044272	sulfur compound biosynthetic process	biological_process	8.81	1.49E-04	3.82E-03	9.37E-01	63
GO:0032592	integral component of mitochondrial membrane	cellular_component	8.81	1.49E-04	3.82E-03	9.37E-01	63
GO:0031668	cellular response to extracellular stimulus	biological_process	8.80	1.50E-04	3.84E-03	8.64E-01	184
GO:0016073	snRNA metabolic process	biological_process	8.78	1.53E-04	3.90E-03	1.00E+00	31
GO:0016896	exoribonuclease activity, producing 5'-phosphomonoesters	molecular_function	8.78	1.53E-04	3.90E-03	1.00E+00	31
GO:0097526	spliceosomal tri-snRNP complex	cellular_component	8.78	1.53E-04	3.90E-03	1.00E+00	31
GO:0030488	tRNA methylation	biological_process	8.78	1.53E-04	3.90E-03	1.00E+00	31
GO:0005484	SNAP receptor activity	molecular_function	8.78	1.53E-04	3.90E-03	1.00E+00	31
GO:0009141	nucleoside triphosphate metabolic process	biological_process	8.69	1.68E-04	4.26E-03	9.15E-01	82
GO:0016574	histone ubiquitination	biological_process	8.69	1.69E-04	4.26E-03	9.75E-01	40
GO:0044088	regulation of vacuole organization	biological_process	8.69	1.69E-04	4.26E-03	9.75E-01	40
GO:0032456	endocytic recycling	biological_process	8.69	1.69E-04	4.26E-03	9.75E-01	40
GO:0003724	RNA helicase activity	molecular_function	8.68	1.70E-04	4.29E-03	9.58E-01	48
GO:0006476	protein deacetylation	biological_process	8.68	1.70E-04	4.29E-03	9.58E-01	48
GO:0008408	3'-5' exonuclease activity	molecular_function	8.68	1.70E-04	4.29E-03	9.58E-01	48

GO:0019902	phosphatase binding	molecular_function	8.68	1.71E-04	4.30E-03	8.58E-01	204
GO:0110053	regulation of actin filament organization	biological_process	8.67	1.71E-04	4.30E-03	8.46E-01	260
	negative regulation of proteolysis involved in cellular protein						
GO:1903051	catabolic process	biological_process	8.65	1.75E-04	4.37E-03	9.28E-01	69
GO:0009062	fatty acid catabolic process	biological_process	8.65	1.75E-04	4.37E-03	9.28E-01	69
GO:0014743	regulation of muscle hypertrophy	biological_process	8.65	1.75E-04	4.37E-03	9.28E-01	69
	regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor						
GO:0017015	signaling pathway	biological_process	8.64	1.77E-04	4.42E-03	9.04E-01	94
GO:0048024	regulation of mRNA splicing, via spliceosome	biological_process	8.64	1.77E-04	4.42E-03	9.04E-01	94
GO:0051170	import into nucleus	biological_process	8.64	1.77E-04	4.42E-03	9.04E-01	94
GO:0070848	response to growth factor	biological_process	8.60	1.84E-04	4.60E-03	8.53E-01	224
GO:0120161	regulation of cold-induced thermogenesis	biological_process	8.59	1.86E-04	4.63E-03	8.81E-01	134
GO:0071230	cellular response to amino acid stimulus	biological_process	8.59	1.86E-04	4.63E-03	9.35E-01	62
GO:0030218	erythrocyte differentiation	biological_process	8.58	1.87E-04	4.65E-03	9.45E-01	55
GO:0016887	ATPase activity	molecular_function	8.53	1.98E-04	4.92E-03	8.29E-01	381
GO:0019887	protein kinase regulator activity	molecular_function	8.52	2.00E-04	4.95E-03	8.73E-01	150
GO:0044743	protein transmembrane import into intracellular organelle	biological_process	8.50	2.04E-04	5.01E-03	1.00E+00	30
GO:0046540	U4/U6 x U5 tri-snRNP complex	cellular_component	8.50	2.04E-04	5.01E-03	1.00E+00	30
GO:0000314	organellar small ribosomal subunit	cellular_component	8.50	2.04E-04	5.01E-03	1.00E+00	30
GO:0005763	mitochondrial small ribosomal subunit	cellular_component	8.50	2.04E-04	5.01E-03	1.00E+00	30
GO:0033558	protein deacetylase activity	molecular_function	8.50	2.04E-04	5.01E-03	1.00E+00	30
GO:0062125	regulation of mitochondrial gene expression	biological_process	8.50	2.04E-04	5.01E-03	1.00E+00	30
	negative regulation of protein modification by small protein						
GO:1903321	conjugation or removal	biological_process	8.49	2.06E-04	5.05E-03	9.14E-01	81
GO:0046034	ATP metabolic process	biological_process	8.49	2.06E-04	5.07E-03	8.95E-01	105
GO:0010769	regulation of cell morphogenesis involved in differentiation	biological_process	8.48	2.07E-04	5.09E-03	8.38E-01	303
	positive regulation of cell morphogenesis involved in						
GO:0010770	differentiation	biological_process	8.45	2.13E-04	5.23E-03	8.65E-01	171
GO:0043488	regulation of mRNA stability	biological_process	8.45	2.14E-04	5.23E-03	9.03E-01	93
GO:0006986	response to unfolded protein	biological_process	8.44	2.16E-04	5.27E-03	9.26E-01	68
GO:0010611	regulation of cardiac muscle hypertrophy	biological_process	8.44	2.16E-04	5.27E-03	9.26E-01	68
GO:0006635	fatty acid beta-oxidation	biological_process	8.43	2.17E-04	5.30E-03	9.57E-01	47
GO:0009411	response to UV	biological_process	8.43	2.19E-04	5.30E-03	8.80E-01	133
GO:0043401	steroid hormone mediated signaling pathway	biological_process	8.43	2.19E-04	5.30E-03	9.74E-01	39
GO:0072595	maintenance of protein localization in organelle	biological_process	8.43	2.19E-04	5.30E-03	9.74E-01	39
GO:0097747	RNA polymerase activity	molecular_function	8.43	2.19E-04	5.30E-03	9.74E-01	39
GO:0034062	5'-3' RNA polymerase activity	molecular_function	8.43	2.19E-04	5.30E-03	9.74E-01	39
GO:0099080	supramolecular complex	cellular_component	8.41	2.22E-04	5.38E-03	8.04E-01	850
GO:0032787	monocarboxylic acid metabolic process	biological_process	8.40	2.24E-04	5.43E-03	8.29E-01	375
GO:0071345	cellular response to cytokine stimulus	biological_process	8.39	2.28E-04	5.52E-03	8.26E-01	413
GO:0140097	catalytic activity, acting on DNA	molecular_function	8.38	2.30E-04	5.57E-03	8.62E-01	181
GO:0006612	protein targeting to membrane	biological_process	8.37	2.32E-04	5.60E-03	9.34E-01	61
GO:0050775	positive regulation of dendrite morphogenesis	biological_process	8.35	2.36E-04	5.66E-03	9.44E-01	54
GO:0004521	endoribonuclease activity	molecular_function	8.35	2.36E-04	5.66E-03	9.44E-01	54

GO:0031228	intrinsic component of Golgi membrane	cellular_component	8.35	2.36E-04	5.66E-03	9.44E-01	54
GO:0040029	regulation of gene expression, epigenetic	biological_process	8.35	2.37E-04	5.69E-03	8.77E-01	138
GO:0050660	flavin adenine dinucleotide binding	molecular_function	8.35	2.37E-04	5.69E-03	9.19E-01	74
GO:0043549	regulation of kinase activity	biological_process	8.32	2.44E-04	5.85E-03	8.09E-01	695
GO:0051056	regulation of small GTPase mediated signal transduction	biological_process	8.31	2.47E-04	5.91E-03	8.45E-01	252
GO:0072657	protein localization to membrane	biological_process	8.28	2.54E-04	6.07E-03	8.29E-01	369
GO:0000302	response to reactive oxygen species	biological_process	8.27	2.55E-04	6.08E-03	8.74E-01	143
GO:1902911	protein kinase complex	cellular_component	8.26	2.58E-04	6.15E-03	9.02E-01	92
GO:0044665	MLL1/2 complex	cellular_component	8.22	2.70E-04	6.40E-03	1.00E+00	29
GO:0071339	MLL1 complex	cellular_component	8.22	2.70E-04	6.40E-03	1.00E+00	29
GO:0000175	3'-5'-exoribonuclease activity	molecular_function	8.22	2.70E-04	6.40E-03	1.00E+00	29
GO:0000470	maturation of LSU-rRNA	biological_process	8.22	2.70E-04	6.40E-03	1.00E+00	29
GO:0003954	NADH dehydrogenase activity	molecular_function	8.22	2.70E-04	6.40E-03	1.00E+00	29
GO:0004407	histone deacetylase activity	molecular_function	8.22	2.70E-04	6.40E-03	1.00E+00	29
GO:0007007	inner mitochondrial membrane organization	biological_process	8.22	2.70E-04	6.40E-03	1.00E+00	29
GO:0031519	PcG protein complex	cellular_component	8.19	2.77E-04	6.56E-03	9.57E-01	46
GO:0010639	negative regulation of organelle organization	biological_process	8.17	2.82E-04	6.65E-03	8.29E-01	368
GO:0031398	positive regulation of protein ubiquitination	biological_process	8.17	2.82E-04	6.65E-03	8.90E-01	109
GO:1903432	regulation of TORC1 signaling	biological_process	8.17	2.84E-04	6.66E-03	9.74E-01	38
GO:0032008	positive regulation of TOR signaling	biological_process	8.17	2.84E-04	6.66E-03	9.74E-01	38
GO:0061631	ubiquitin conjugating enzyme activity	molecular_function	8.17	2.84E-04	6.66E-03	9.74E-01	38
GO:0008360	regulation of cell shape	biological_process	8.15	2.88E-04	6.75E-03	8.69E-01	153
GO:0019216	regulation of lipid metabolic process	biological_process	8.14	2.91E-04	6.83E-03	8.37E-01	300
GO:0001221	transcription cofactor binding	molecular_function	8.12	2.97E-04	6.95E-03	9.43E-01	53
GO:0005741	mitochondrial outer membrane	cellular_component	8.06	3.16E-04	7.41E-03	8.71E-01	147
GO:0007010	cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	8.05	3.19E-04	7.46E-03	8.04E-01	782
GO:0034440	lipid oxidation	biological_process	8.02	3.30E-04	7.70E-03	9.24E-01	66
GO:0045859	regulation of protein kinase activity	biological_process	8.01	3.31E-04	7.73E-03	8.11E-01	609
GO:0001932	regulation of protein phosphorylation	biological_process	7.99	3.38E-04	7.86E-03	7.93E-01	1225
GO:0001701	in utero embryonic development	biological_process	7.99	3.38E-04	7.86E-03	8.38E-01	284
GO:0050773	regulation of dendrite development	biological_process	7.98	3.41E-04	7.92E-03	8.61E-01	173
GO:0043066	negative regulation of apoptotic process	biological_process	7.98	3.43E-04	7.97E-03	8.04E-01	781
GO:0061025	membrane fusion	biological_process	7.95	3.52E-04	8.16E-03	8.92E-01	102
GO:0044282	small molecule catabolic process	biological_process	7.95	3.54E-04	8.20E-03	8.43E-01	254
GO:0098876	vesicle-mediated transport to the plasma membrane	biological_process	7.94	3.56E-04	8.23E-03	9.17E-01	72
GO:0031397	negative regulation of protein ubiquitination	biological_process	7.94	3.56E-04	8.23E-03	9.17E-01	72
GO:0090174	organelle membrane fusion	biological_process	7.94	3.56E-04	8.23E-03	9.17E-01	72
GO:0006515	protein quality control for misfolded or incompletely synthesized proteins	biological_process	7.93	3.59E-04	8.26E-03	1.00E+00	28
GO:0033866	nucleoside bisphosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	7.93	3.59E-04	8.26E-03	1.00E+00	28
GO:0034030	ribonucleoside bisphosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	7.93	3.59E-04	8.26E-03	1.00E+00	28
GO:0034033	purine nucleoside bisphosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	7.93	3.59E-04	8.26E-03	1.00E+00	28
GO:0022411	cellular component disassembly	biological_process	7.93	3.61E-04	8.29E-03	8.58E-01	183

GO:1903844	regulation of cellular response to transforming growth factor beta stimulus	biological_process	7.92	3.65E-04	8.38E-03	8.96E-01	96
GO:0016684	oxidoreductase activity, acting on peroxide as acceptor	molecular_function	7.91	3.67E-04	8.38E-03	9.73E-01	37
GO:0000993	RNA polymerase II complex binding	molecular_function	7.91	3.67E-04	8.38E-03	9.73E-01	37
GO:0005048	signal sequence binding	molecular_function	7.91	3.67E-04	8.38E-03	9.73E-01	37
GO:0031304	intrinsic component of mitochondrial inner membrane regulation of transcription elongation from RNA polymerase II	cellular_component	7.91	3.67E-04	8.38E-03	9.73E-01	37
GO:0034243	promoter	biological_process	7.91	3.67E-04	8.38E-03	9.73E-01	37
GO:0015036	disulfide oxidoreductase activity	molecular_function	7.91	3.67E-04	8.38E-03	9.73E-01	37
GO:0031060	regulation of histone methylation	biological_process	7.90	3.71E-04	8.46E-03	9.10E-01	78
GO:0046902	regulation of mitochondrial membrane permeability	biological_process	7.89	3.73E-04	8.48E-03	9.42E-01	52
GO:0030173	integral component of Golgi membrane	cellular_component	7.89	3.73E-04	8.48E-03	9.42E-01	52
GO:0006606	protein import into nucleus	biological_process	7.89	3.74E-04	8.49E-03	9.00E-01	90
GO:0040017	positive regulation of locomotion	biological_process	7.89	3.75E-04	8.50E-03	8.13E-01	557
GO:0016829	lyase activity	molecular_function	7.88	3.80E-04	8.59E-03	8.62E-01	167
GO:0050792	regulation of viral process	biological_process	7.88	3.80E-04	8.59E-03	8.62E-01	167
GO:0015629	actin cytoskeleton	cellular_component	7.87	3.83E-04	8.66E-03	8.54E-01	198
GO:0065008	regulation of biological quality	biological_process	7.83	3.98E-04	8.99E-03	7.77E-01	3003
GO:0019395	fatty acid oxidation	biological_process	7.81	4.06E-04	9.17E-03	9.23E-01	65
GO:0016773	phosphotransferase activity, alcohol group as acceptor	molecular_function	7.77	4.23E-04	9.54E-03	8.08E-01	647
GO:0031401	positive regulation of protein modification process	biological_process	7.76	4.25E-04	9.58E-03	7.96E-01	1054
GO:0016605	PML body	cellular_component	7.74	4.36E-04	9.81E-03	9.15E-01	71
GO:0009792	embryo development ending in birth or egg hatching	biological_process	7.71	4.47E-04	1.00E-02	8.34E-01	301
GO:1902600	proton transmembrane transport	biological_process	7.71	4.48E-04	1.00E-02	9.31E-01	58
GO:0009199	ribonucleoside triphosphate metabolic process	biological_process	7.71	4.48E-04	1.00E-02	9.31E-01	58
GO:0016575	histone deacetylation	biological_process	7.71	4.50E-04	1.01E-02	9.55E-01	44
GO:0010827	regulation of glucose transmembrane transport	biological_process	7.70	4.51E-04	1.01E-02	9.09E-01	77
GO:0051235	maintenance of location	biological_process	7.66	4.69E-04	1.05E-02	8.65E-01	155
GO:1901998	toxin transport	biological_process	7.65	4.76E-04	1.06E-02	9.72E-01	36
GO:0051898	negative regulation of protein kinase B signaling	biological_process	7.65	4.76E-04	1.06E-02	9.72E-01	36
GO:0031305	integral component of mitochondrial inner membrane	cellular_component	7.65	4.76E-04	1.06E-02	9.72E-01	36
GO:0060964	regulation of gene silencing by miRNA	biological_process	7.65	4.76E-04	1.06E-02	9.72E-01	36
GO:0070129	regulation of mitochondrial translation	biological_process	7.65	4.77E-04	1.06E-02	1.00E+00	27
GO:1902235	regulation of endoplasmic reticulum stress-induced intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	7.65	4.77E-04	1.06E-02	1.00E+00	27
GO:0001825	blastocyst formation	biological_process	7.65	4.77E-04	1.06E-02	1.00E+00	27
GO:0030515	snoRNA binding	molecular_function	7.65	4.77E-04	1.06E-02	1.00E+00	27
GO:2000147	positive regulation of cell motility	biological_process	7.64	4.81E-04	1.06E-02	8.14E-01	531
GO:0030030	cell projection organization	biological_process	7.62	4.90E-04	1.08E-02	8.03E-01	785
GO:0006513	protein monoubiquitination	biological_process	7.60	5.01E-04	1.11E-02	9.22E-01	64
GO:0009144	purine nucleoside triphosphate metabolic process	biological_process	7.60	5.01E-04	1.11E-02	9.22E-01	64
GO:0051495	positive regulation of cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	7.59	5.03E-04	1.11E-02	8.51E-01	201

GO:0071363	cellular response to growth factor stimulus	biological_process	7.59	5.08E-04	1.12E-02	8.50E-01	206
GO:0043009	chordate embryonic development	biological_process	7.57	5.15E-04	1.13E-02	8.34E-01	290
GO:0051087	chaperone binding	molecular_function	7.56	5.22E-04	1.15E-02	8.94E-01	94
GO:2000045	regulation of G1/S transition of mitotic cell cycle	biological_process	7.55	5.24E-04	1.15E-02	8.83E-01	111
GO:0000784	nuclear chromosome, telomeric region	N/A	7.54	5.33E-04	1.17E-02	9.14E-01	70
GO:0005802	trans-Golgi network	cellular_component	7.52	5.43E-04	1.19E-02	8.56E-01	180
GO:0016651	oxidoreductase activity, acting on NAD(P)H	molecular_function	7.51	5.48E-04	1.20E-02	9.08E-01	76
GO:1902554	serine/threonine protein kinase complex	cellular_component	7.51	5.48E-04	1.20E-02	9.08E-01	76
GO:0005788	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	cellular_component	7.49	5.57E-04	1.21E-02	9.30E-01	57
GO:0010494	cytoplasmic stress granule	cellular_component	7.49	5.57E-04	1.21E-02	9.30E-01	57
GO:0019903	protein phosphatase binding	molecular_function	7.48	5.62E-04	1.23E-02	8.62E-01	159
GO:0030139	endocytic vesicle	cellular_component	7.46	5.77E-04	1.26E-02	8.67E-01	143
GO:0016627	oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors	molecular_function	7.44	5.88E-04	1.28E-02	9.40E-01	50
GO:0016796	exonuclease activity, active with either ribo- or deoxyribonucleic acids and producing 5'-phosphomonoesters	molecular_function	7.44	5.88E-04	1.28E-02	9.40E-01	50
GO:0043967	histone H4 acetylation	biological_process	7.44	5.88E-04	1.28E-02	9.40E-01	50
GO:0061077	chaperone-mediated protein folding	biological_process	7.44	5.88E-04	1.28E-02	9.40E-01	50
GO:2001236	regulation of extrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	7.41	6.03E-04	1.31E-02	8.65E-01	148
GO:0030135	coated vesicle	cellular_component	7.41	6.04E-04	1.31E-02	8.71E-01	132
GO:0043331	response to dsRNA	biological_process	7.39	6.15E-04	1.33E-02	9.71E-01	35
GO:0000726	non-recombinational repair	biological_process	7.39	6.15E-04	1.33E-02	9.71E-01	35
GO:0032205	negative regulation of telomere maintenance	biological_process	7.39	6.15E-04	1.33E-02	9.71E-01	35
GO:0032451	demethylase activity	molecular_function	7.39	6.15E-04	1.33E-02	9.71E-01	35
GO:0032543	mitochondrial translation	biological_process	7.39	6.15E-04	1.33E-02	9.71E-01	35
GO:0090559	regulation of membrane permeability	biological_process	7.39	6.16E-04	1.33E-02	9.21E-01	63
GO:0031058	positive regulation of histone modification	biological_process	7.38	6.23E-04	1.34E-02	8.92E-01	93
GO:0042273	ribosomal large subunit biogenesis	biological_process	7.36	6.33E-04	1.35E-02	1.00E+00	26
GO:0044257	cellular protein catabolic process	N/A	7.36	6.33E-04	1.35E-02	1.00E+00	26
GO:0071007	U2-type catalytic step 2 spliceosome	cellular_component	7.36	6.33E-04	1.35E-02	1.00E+00	26
GO:0000154	rRNA modification	biological_process	7.36	6.33E-04	1.35E-02	1.00E+00	26
GO:0006891	intra-Golgi vesicle-mediated transport	biological_process	7.36	6.33E-04	1.35E-02	1.00E+00	26
GO:0035198	miRNA binding	molecular_function	7.36	6.33E-04	1.35E-02	1.00E+00	26
GO:0006469	negative regulation of protein kinase activity	biological_process	7.36	6.39E-04	1.36E-02	8.52E-01	189
GO:0032271	regulation of protein polymerization	biological_process	7.33	6.58E-04	1.40E-02	8.46E-01	214
GO:0072593	reactive oxygen species metabolic process	biological_process	7.32	6.62E-04	1.41E-02	9.01E-01	81
GO:0001047	core promoter binding	N/A	7.28	6.91E-04	1.47E-02	9.29E-01	56
GO:0051287	NAD binding	molecular_function	7.28	6.91E-04	1.47E-02	9.29E-01	56
GO:0030512	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway	biological_process	7.28	6.91E-04	1.47E-02	9.29E-01	56
GO:0097193	intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	7.27	6.97E-04	1.48E-02	8.64E-01	147
GO:0045598	regulation of fat cell differentiation	biological_process	7.26	7.04E-04	1.49E-02	8.70E-01	131
GO:0031589	cell-substrate adhesion	biological_process	7.26	7.04E-04	1.49E-02	8.70E-01	131
GO:0018024	histone-lysine N-methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	7.23	7.27E-04	1.54E-02	9.52E-01	42
GO:1901264	carbohydrate derivative transport	biological_process	7.23	7.27E-04	1.54E-02	9.52E-01	42

GO:0031201	SNARE complex	cellular_component	7.23	7.27E-04	1.54E-02	9.52E-01	42
GO:0060249	anatomical structure homeostasis	biological_process	7.21	7.38E-04	1.55E-02	8.42E-01	228
GO:0072665	protein localization to vacuole	biological_process	7.21	7.38E-04	1.55E-02	9.39E-01	49
GO:0010332	response to gamma radiation	biological_process	7.21	7.38E-04	1.55E-02	9.39E-01	49
GO:2001243	negative regulation of intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	7.20	7.43E-04	1.56E-02	8.91E-01	92
GO:0034614	cellular response to reactive oxygen species	biological_process	7.20	7.43E-04	1.56E-02	8.91E-01	92
GO:0043413	macromolecule glycosylation	biological_process	7.20	7.45E-04	1.56E-02	8.60E-01	157
GO:0006486	protein glycosylation	biological_process	7.20	7.45E-04	1.56E-02	8.60E-01	157
GO:0050793	regulation of developmental process	biological_process	7.18	7.58E-04	1.59E-02	7.80E-01	2311
GO:0030705	cytoskeleton-dependent intracellular transport	biological_process	7.18	7.65E-04	1.60E-02	8.58E-01	162
GO:0044242	cellular lipid catabolic process	biological_process	7.16	7.75E-04	1.62E-02	8.65E-01	141
GO:0001568	blood vessel development	biological_process	7.16	7.75E-04	1.62E-02	8.65E-01	141
GO:0031098	stress-activated protein kinase signaling cascade	biological_process	7.16	7.75E-04	1.62E-02	8.95E-01	86
GO:0070085	glycosylation	biological_process	7.15	7.83E-04	1.63E-02	8.56E-01	167
GO:0005758	mitochondrial intermembrane space	cellular_component	7.14	7.94E-04	1.65E-02	9.12E-01	68
GO:0016655	oxidoreductase activity, acting on NAD(P)H, quinone or similar compound as acceptor	molecular_function	7.14	7.96E-04	1.65E-02	9.71E-01	34
GO:2000785	regulation of autophagosome assembly	biological_process	7.14	7.96E-04	1.65E-02	9.71E-01	34
GO:0031970	organelle envelope lumen	cellular_component	7.13	7.97E-04	1.65E-02	9.00E-01	80
GO:0033865	nucleoside bisphosphate metabolic process	biological_process	7.13	7.97E-04	1.65E-02	9.00E-01	80
GO:0033875	ribonucleoside bisphosphate metabolic process	biological_process	7.13	7.97E-04	1.65E-02	9.00E-01	80
GO:0034032	purine nucleoside bisphosphate metabolic process	biological_process	7.13	7.97E-04	1.65E-02	9.00E-01	80
GO:1902905	positive regulation of supramolecular fiber organization	biological_process	7.12	8.10E-04	1.68E-02	8.53E-01	177
GO:0001012	RNA polymerase II regulatory region DNA binding	N/A	7.11	8.13E-04	1.68E-02	8.05E-01	652
GO:0070201	regulation of establishment of protein localization	biological_process	7.11	8.17E-04	1.69E-02	8.04E-01	679
GO:1903900	regulation of viral life cycle	biological_process	7.11	8.19E-04	1.69E-02	8.69E-01	130
GO:0008610	lipid biosynthetic process	biological_process	7.10	8.21E-04	1.69E-02	8.23E-01	362
GO:0070461	SAGA-type complex	cellular_component	7.08	8.41E-04	1.72E-02	1.00E+00	25
GO:0046966	thyroid hormone receptor binding	molecular_function	7.08	8.41E-04	1.72E-02	1.00E+00	25
GO:0050136	NADH dehydrogenase (quinone) activity	molecular_function	7.08	8.41E-04	1.72E-02	1.00E+00	25
GO:0000462	maturation of SSU-rRNA from tricistronic rRNA transcript (SSU-rRNA, 5.8S rRNA, LSU-rRNA)	biological_process	7.08	8.41E-04	1.72E-02	1.00E+00	25
GO:0001671	ATPase activator activity	molecular_function	7.08	8.41E-04	1.72E-02	1.00E+00	25
GO:0005689	U12-type spliceosomal complex	cellular_component	7.08	8.41E-04	1.72E-02	1.00E+00	25
GO:0008137	NADH dehydrogenase (ubiquinone) activity	molecular_function	7.08	8.41E-04	1.72E-02	1.00E+00	25
GO:0034661	ncRNA catabolic process	biological_process	7.08	8.41E-04	1.72E-02	1.00E+00	25
GO:0090140	regulation of mitochondrial fission	biological_process	7.08	8.41E-04	1.72E-02	1.00E+00	25
GO:0007265	Ras protein signal transduction	biological_process	7.08	8.42E-04	1.72E-02	8.45E-01	207
GO:0016278	lysine N-methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	7.06	8.56E-04	1.74E-02	9.27E-01	55
GO:0016279	protein-lysine N-methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	7.06	8.56E-04	1.74E-02	9.27E-01	55
GO:0019838	growth factor binding	molecular_function	7.06	8.59E-04	1.75E-02	8.67E-01	135
GO:0040008	regulation of growth	biological_process	7.05	8.65E-04	1.76E-02	8.07E-01	615
GO:2000059	negative regulation of ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process	biological_process	6.99	9.24E-04	1.88E-02	9.38E-01	48

GO:0000781	chromosome, telomeric region	cellular_component	6.99	9.25E-04	1.88E-02	8.82E-01	102
GO:0055037	recycling endosome	cellular_component	6.99	9.25E-04	1.88E-02	8.82E-01	102
GO:2000378	negative regulation of reactive oxygen species metabolic process	biological_process	6.98	9.30E-04	1.88E-02	9.18E-01	61
GO:0048646	anatomical structure formation involved in morphogenesis	biological_process	6.97	9.44E-04	1.91E-02	8.04E-01	668
GO:0016571	histone methylation	biological_process	6.95	9.59E-04	1.94E-02	8.99E-01	79
GO:0000723	telomere maintenance	biological_process	6.93	9.74E-04	1.96E-02	9.04E-01	73
GO:0032200	telomere organization	biological_process	6.93	9.74E-04	1.96E-02	9.04E-01	73
GO:0032507	maintenance of protein location in cell	biological_process	6.93	9.74E-04	1.96E-02	9.04E-01	73
GO:0120035	regulation of plasma membrane bounded cell projection organization	biological_process	6.93	9.78E-04	1.97E-02	8.03E-01	690
GO:0060090	molecular adaptor activity	molecular_function	6.89	1.02E-03	2.05E-02	8.38E-01	240
GO:0001103	RNA polymerase II repressing transcription factor binding	N/A	6.88	1.03E-03	2.06E-02	9.70E-01	33
GO:1905898	positive regulation of response to endoplasmic reticulum stress	biological_process	6.88	1.03E-03	2.06E-02	9.70E-01	33
GO:0004601	peroxidase activity	molecular_function	6.88	1.03E-03	2.06E-02	9.70E-01	33
GO:0006303	double-strand break repair via nonhomologous end joining	biological_process	6.88	1.03E-03	2.06E-02	9.70E-01	33
GO:0009205	purine ribonucleoside triphosphate metabolic process	biological_process	6.85	1.06E-03	2.12E-02	9.26E-01	54
GO:0043903	regulation of symbiosis, encompassing mutualism through parasitism	biological_process	6.85	1.06E-03	2.13E-02	8.50E-01	180
GO:0000287	magnesium ion binding	molecular_function	6.84	1.07E-03	2.14E-02	8.49E-01	185
GO:0006470	protein dephosphorylation	biological_process	6.81	1.10E-03	2.20E-02	8.59E-01	149
GO:0016180	snRNA processing	biological_process	6.80	1.12E-03	2.22E-02	1.00E+00	24
GO:0071782	endoplasmic reticulum tubular network	cellular_component	6.80	1.12E-03	2.22E-02	1.00E+00	24
GO:0097346	INO80-type complex	cellular_component	6.80	1.12E-03	2.22E-02	1.00E+00	24
GO:0005158	insulin receptor binding	molecular_function	6.80	1.12E-03	2.22E-02	1.00E+00	24
GO:0030687	preribosome, large subunit precursor	cellular_component	6.80	1.12E-03	2.22E-02	1.00E+00	24
GO:0006984	ER-nucleus signaling pathway	biological_process	6.80	1.12E-03	2.22E-02	1.00E+00	24
GO:1903312	negative regulation of mRNA metabolic process	biological_process	6.77	1.15E-03	2.28E-02	8.97E-01	78
GO:0009266	response to temperature stimulus	biological_process	6.77	1.15E-03	2.28E-02	8.65E-01	133
GO:0019213	deacetylase activity	molecular_function	6.75	1.17E-03	2.31E-02	9.50E-01	40
GO:1900087	positive regulation of G1/S transition of mitotic cell cycle	biological_process	6.75	1.17E-03	2.31E-02	9.50E-01	40
GO:0051539	4 iron, 4 sulfur cluster binding	molecular_function	6.75	1.17E-03	2.31E-02	9.50E-01	40
GO:0010883	regulation of lipid storage	biological_process	6.75	1.17E-03	2.31E-02	9.50E-01	40
GO:1903670	regulation of sprouting angiogenesis	biological_process	6.75	1.18E-03	2.32E-02	9.09E-01	66
GO:0006906	vesicle fusion	biological_process	6.75	1.18E-03	2.32E-02	9.09E-01	66
GO:0072331	signal transduction by p53 class mediator	biological_process	6.75	1.18E-03	2.32E-02	9.03E-01	72
GO:0030031	cell projection assembly	biological_process	6.74	1.19E-03	2.34E-02	8.29E-01	287
GO:0043547	positive regulation of GTPase activity	biological_process	6.71	1.21E-03	2.38E-02	8.43E-01	204
GO:0030427	site of polarized growth	cellular_component	6.71	1.21E-03	2.38E-02	8.48E-01	184
GO:0051272	positive regulation of cellular component movement	biological_process	6.71	1.22E-03	2.39E-02	8.08E-01	547

GO:0006631	fatty acid metabolic process	biological_process	6.68	1.26E-03	2.47E-02	8.35E-01	243
GO:0120031	plasma membrane bounded cell projection assembly	biological_process	6.67	1.26E-03	2.47E-02	8.31E-01	272
GO:0034097	response to cytokine	biological_process	6.65	1.29E-03	2.53E-02	8.09E-01	528
GO:0005789	endoplasmic reticulum membrane	cellular_component	6.65	1.30E-03	2.53E-02	8.26E-01	310
GO:1901799	negative regulation of proteasomal protein catabolic process	biological_process	6.64	1.31E-03	2.56E-02	9.25E-01	53
GO:0051117	ATPase binding	molecular_function	6.63	1.32E-03	2.58E-02	8.92E-01	83
GO:0016469	proton-transporting two-sector ATPase complex	cellular_component	6.62	1.33E-03	2.58E-02	9.69E-01	32
GO:0045070	positive regulation of viral genome replication	biological_process	6.62	1.33E-03	2.58E-02	9.69E-01	32
GO:0090316	positive regulation of intracellular protein transport	biological_process	6.62	1.33E-03	2.59E-02	8.64E-01	132
GO:0043244	regulation of protein-containing complex disassembly	biological_process	6.61	1.35E-03	2.62E-02	8.71E-01	116
GO:1905475	regulation of protein localization to membrane	biological_process	6.60	1.36E-03	2.65E-02	8.50E-01	173
GO:0070507	regulation of microtubule cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	6.59	1.38E-03	2.67E-02	8.45E-01	193
GO:0046332	SMAD binding	molecular_function	6.58	1.38E-03	2.68E-02	8.96E-01	77
GO:0033613	activating transcription factor binding	N/A	6.58	1.38E-03	2.68E-02	8.96E-01	77
GO:0046324	regulation of glucose import	biological_process	6.57	1.40E-03	2.70E-02	9.15E-01	59
GO:0140034	methylation-dependent protein binding	molecular_function	6.57	1.40E-03	2.70E-02	9.15E-01	59
GO:0035064	methyated histone binding	molecular_function	6.57	1.40E-03	2.70E-02	9.15E-01	59
GO:0010564	regulation of cell cycle process	biological_process	6.56	1.41E-03	2.72E-02	8.08E-01	536
GO:0006637	acyl-CoA metabolic process	biological_process	6.55	1.43E-03	2.75E-02	9.08E-01	65
GO:0035383	thioester metabolic process	biological_process	6.55	1.43E-03	2.75E-02	9.08E-01	65
GO:0016706	2-oxoglutarate-dependent dioxygenase activity	molecular_function	6.54	1.44E-03	2.77E-02	9.35E-01	46
GO:0045333	cellular respiration	biological_process	6.54	1.44E-03	2.77E-02	9.35E-01	46
GO:0006289	nucleotide-excision repair	biological_process	6.54	1.44E-03	2.77E-02	9.35E-01	46
GO:0000977	RNA polymerase II regulatory region sequence-specific DNA binding	molecular_function	6.53	1.45E-03	2.79E-02	8.03E-01	644
GO:0071108	protein K48-linked deubiquitination	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	1.00E+00	23
GO:0098927	vesicle-mediated transport between endosomal compartments	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	1.00E+00	23
GO:0000407	phagophore assembly site	cellular_component	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	1.00E+00	23
GO:0000469	cleavage involved in rRNA processing	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	1.00E+00	23
GO:0031954	positive regulation of protein autophosphorylation	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	1.00E+00	23
GO:0008535	respiratory chain complex IV assembly	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	1.00E+00	23
GO:0060148	positive regulation of posttranscriptional gene silencing	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	1.00E+00	23
GO:0048008	platelet-derived growth factor receptor signaling pathway	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	9.49E-01	39
GO:0050873	brown fat cell differentiation	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	9.49E-01	39
GO:0002181	cytoplasmic translation	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	9.49E-01	39
GO:0060147	regulation of posttranscriptional gene silencing	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	9.49E-01	39
GO:0010762	regulation of fibroblast migration	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	9.49E-01	39
GO:0060966	regulation of gene silencing by RNA	biological_process	6.51	1.48E-03	2.81E-02	9.49E-01	39
GO:0000792	heterochromatin	cellular_component	6.51	1.49E-03	2.81E-02	8.86E-01	88
GO:0009791	post-embryonic development	biological_process	6.51	1.49E-03	2.81E-02	8.86E-01	88

GO:0006260	DNA replication	biological_process	6.48	1.54E-03	2.91E-02	8.63E-01	131
GO:0004674	protein serine/threonine kinase activity	molecular_function	6.46	1.56E-03	2.96E-02	8.15E-01	411
GO:0032879	regulation of localization	biological_process	6.46	1.57E-03	2.97E-02	7.77E-01	2429
GO:0035258	steroid hormone receptor binding	N/A	6.45	1.58E-03	2.98E-02	8.90E-01	82
GO:0051640	organelle localization	biological_process	6.45	1.59E-03	2.99E-02	8.17E-01	383
GO:0031113	regulation of microtubule polymerization	biological_process	6.43	1.62E-03	3.05E-02	9.23E-01	52
GO:0048583	regulation of response to stimulus	biological_process	6.42	1.62E-03	3.06E-02	7.73E-01	3256
GO:0010595	positive regulation of endothelial cell migration	biological_process	6.41	1.64E-03	3.08E-02	8.82E-01	93
GO:0031344	regulation of cell projection organization	biological_process	6.41	1.64E-03	3.08E-02	8.00E-01	696
GO:0010212	response to ionizing radiation	biological_process	6.41	1.65E-03	3.10E-02	8.67E-01	120
GO:0046578	regulation of Ras protein signal transduction	biological_process	6.40	1.67E-03	3.12E-02	8.37E-01	221
GO:0051301	cell division	biological_process	6.40	1.67E-03	3.13E-02	8.15E-01	401
	negative regulation of cellular response to transforming growth factor beta stimulus	biological_process	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.14E-01	58
GO:1903845	factor beta stimulus	biological_process	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.14E-01	58
GO:0004722	protein serine/threonine phosphatase activity	molecular_function	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.14E-01	58
GO:0006446	regulation of translational initiation	biological_process	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.14E-01	58
GO:1902117	positive regulation of organelle assembly	biological_process	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.00E-01	70
GO:0042974	retinoic acid receptor binding	molecular_function	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.68E-01	31
GO:0050686	negative regulation of mRNA processing	biological_process	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.68E-01	31
GO:0006505	GPI anchor metabolic process	biological_process	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.68E-01	31
GO:0006998	nuclear envelope organization	biological_process	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.68E-01	31
GO:0009225	nucleotide-sugar metabolic process	biological_process	6.37	1.71E-03	3.18E-02	9.68E-01	31
GO:0045171	intercellular bridge	cellular_component	6.36	1.73E-03	3.22E-02	9.06E-01	64
GO:0016054	organic acid catabolic process	biological_process	6.34	1.76E-03	3.27E-02	8.48E-01	171
GO:0046395	carboxylic acid catabolic process	biological_process	6.34	1.76E-03	3.27E-02	8.48E-01	171
GO:0001046	core promoter sequence-specific DNA binding	molecular_function	6.32	1.80E-03	3.34E-02	9.33E-01	45
GO:0017069	snRNA binding	molecular_function	6.28	1.88E-03	3.47E-02	9.47E-01	38
GO:0046854	phosphatidylinositol phosphorylation	biological_process	6.28	1.88E-03	3.47E-02	9.47E-01	38
GO:1903313	positive regulation of mRNA metabolic process	biological_process	6.28	1.88E-03	3.47E-02	8.89E-01	81
	modification of morphology or physiology of other organism	biological_process	6.28	1.88E-03	3.47E-02	8.89E-01	81
GO:0051817	involved in symbiotic interaction	biological_process	6.28	1.88E-03	3.47E-02	8.89E-01	81
GO:0010970	transport along microtubule	biological_process	6.26	1.91E-03	3.52E-02	8.55E-01	145
GO:0045022	early endosome to late endosome transport	biological_process	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
	positive regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase I	biological_process	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
GO:0045943	positive regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase I	biological_process	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
GO:2000637	positive regulation of gene silencing by miRNA	biological_process	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
GO:0000178	exosome (RNase complex)	cellular_component	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
GO:1905354	exoribonuclease complex	cellular_component	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
GO:0031365	N-terminal protein amino acid modification	biological_process	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
GO:0035327	transcriptionally active chromatin	N/A	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
GO:0035561	regulation of chromatin binding	biological_process	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
	RNA phosphodiester bond hydrolysis, endonucleolytic	biological_process	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
GO:0090502	RNA phosphodiester bond hydrolysis, endonucleolytic	biological_process	6.23	1.97E-03	3.60E-02	1.00E+00	22
GO:0006661	phosphatidylinositol biosynthetic process	biological_process	6.22	1.99E-03	3.65E-02	9.22E-01	51
GO:0007569	cell aging	biological_process	6.17	2.08E-03	3.81E-02	9.12E-01	57
GO:0001558	regulation of cell growth	biological_process	6.15	2.14E-03	3.90E-02	8.16E-01	375

GO:0016242	negative regulation of macroautophagy	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:0043330	response to exogenous dsRNA	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:0072599	establishment of protein localization to endoplasmic reticulum	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:1902186	regulation of viral release from host cell	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:0000387	spliceosomal snRNP assembly	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:0002262	myeloid cell homeostasis	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:0006414	translational elongation	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:0006506	GPI anchor biosynthetic process	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:0060260	regulation of transcription initiation from RNA polymerase II promoter	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:0010939	regulation of necrotic cell death	biological_process	6.12	2.21E-03	3.99E-02	9.67E-01	30
GO:0090199	regulation of release of cytochrome c from mitochondria	biological_process	6.10	2.24E-03	4.06E-02	9.32E-01	44
GO:0006302	double-strand break repair	biological_process	6.10	2.25E-03	4.07E-02	8.49E-01	159
GO:0046474	glycerophospholipid biosynthetic process	biological_process	6.09	2.28E-03	4.11E-02	8.79E-01	91
GO:0007049	cell cycle	biological_process	6.08	2.28E-03	4.11E-02	7.99E-01	700
GO:0043531	ADP binding	molecular_function	6.04	2.37E-03	4.24E-02	9.46E-01	37
GO:0018208	peptidyl-proline modification	biological_process	6.04	2.37E-03	4.24E-02	9.46E-01	37
GO:0071326	cellular response to monosaccharide stimulus	biological_process	6.04	2.37E-03	4.24E-02	9.46E-01	37
GO:0005778	peroxisomal membrane	cellular_component	6.04	2.37E-03	4.24E-02	9.46E-01	37
GO:0031463	Cul3-RING ubiquitin ligase complex	cellular_component	6.04	2.37E-03	4.24E-02	9.46E-01	37
GO:0031903	microbody membrane	cellular_component	6.04	2.37E-03	4.24E-02	9.46E-01	37
GO:0010613	positive regulation of cardiac muscle hypertrophy	biological_process	6.04	2.37E-03	4.24E-02	9.46E-01	37
GO:0014742	positive regulation of muscle hypertrophy	biological_process	6.04	2.37E-03	4.24E-02	9.46E-01	37
GO:0007015	actin filament organization	biological_process	6.04	2.37E-03	4.24E-02	8.36E-01	213
GO:0036064	ciliary basal body	cellular_component	6.03	2.42E-03	4.32E-02	8.57E-01	133
GO:0044262	cellular carbohydrate metabolic process	biological_process	6.01	2.46E-03	4.40E-02	8.55E-01	138
GO:0071407	cellular response to organic cyclic compound hydrolase activity, acting on carbon-nitrogen (but not peptide)	biological_process	6.00	2.47E-03	4.41E-02	8.28E-01	256
GO:0016811	bonds, in linear amides	molecular_function	6.00	2.47E-03	4.41E-02	8.97E-01	68
GO:0045739	positive regulation of DNA repair	biological_process	6.00	2.47E-03	4.41E-02	8.97E-01	68
GO:0031252	cell leading edge	cellular_component	6.00	2.47E-03	4.41E-02	8.97E-01	68
GO:0048365	Rac GTPase binding	N/A	5.98	2.54E-03	4.51E-02	9.03E-01	62
GO:0150116	regulation of cell-substrate junction organization	biological_process	5.98	2.54E-03	4.51E-02	9.03E-01	62
GO:0030865	cortical cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	5.97	2.54E-03	4.52E-02	9.11E-01	56
GO:0030426	growth cone	cellular_component	5.97	2.55E-03	4.53E-02	8.43E-01	178
GO:0000987	cis-regulatory region sequence-specific DNA binding K63-linked polyubiquitin modification-dependent protein	molecular_function	5.96	2.57E-03	4.56E-02	8.06E-01	510
GO:0070530	binding	molecular_function	5.95	2.61E-03	4.60E-02	1.00E+00	21
GO:0098780	response to mitochondrial depolarisation	biological_process	5.95	2.61E-03	4.60E-02	1.00E+00	21
GO:0051220	cytoplasmic sequestering of protein	biological_process	5.95	2.61E-03	4.60E-02	1.00E+00	21
GO:0006119	oxidative phosphorylation	biological_process	5.95	2.61E-03	4.60E-02	1.00E+00	21
GO:0006403	RNA localization	biological_process	5.95	2.61E-03	4.60E-02	1.00E+00	21
GO:0032527	protein exit from endoplasmic reticulum	biological_process	5.95	2.61E-03	4.60E-02	1.00E+00	21
GO:0035145	exon-exon junction complex	cellular_component	5.95	2.61E-03	4.60E-02	1.00E+00	21

GO:0062098	regulation of programmed necrotic cell death	biological_process	5.95	2.61E-03	4.60E-02	1.00E+00	21
GO:0010035	response to inorganic substance	biological_process	5.93	2.67E-03	4.69E-02	8.18E-01	340
GO:0042641	actomyosin	cellular_component	5.92	2.68E-03	4.71E-02	8.78E-01	90
GO:0043086	negative regulation of catalytic activity	biological_process	5.92	2.69E-03	4.73E-02	8.04E-01	550
GO:1902806	regulation of cell cycle G1/S phase transition	biological_process	5.91	2.71E-03	4.77E-02	8.58E-01	127
GO:0045017	glycerolipid biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.90	2.74E-03	4.81E-02	8.68E-01	106
GO:1903421	regulation of synaptic vesicle recycling	biological_process	5.86	2.84E-03	4.96E-02	9.66E-01	29
GO:0006482	protein demethylation	biological_process	5.86	2.84E-03	4.96E-02	9.66E-01	29
GO:0006754	ATP biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.86	2.84E-03	4.96E-02	9.66E-01	29
GO:0008214	protein dealkylation	biological_process	5.86	2.84E-03	4.96E-02	9.66E-01	29
GO:0010390	histone monoubiquitination	biological_process	5.86	2.84E-03	4.96E-02	9.66E-01	29
GO:0035967	cellular response to topologically incorrect protein	biological_process	5.86	2.84E-03	4.96E-02	9.66E-01	29
GO:0045786	negative regulation of cell cycle	biological_process	5.85	2.87E-03	5.00E-02	8.15E-01	367
GO:0031346	positive regulation of cell projection organization	biological_process	5.84	2.91E-03	5.07E-02	8.10E-01	422
GO:0001726	ruffle	cellular_component	5.84	2.91E-03	5.07E-02	8.81E-01	84
GO:0016592	mediator complex	cellular_component	5.81	2.99E-03	5.19E-02	9.44E-01	36
GO:0071331	cellular response to hexose stimulus	biological_process	5.81	2.99E-03	5.19E-02	9.44E-01	36
GO:0031369	translation initiation factor binding	molecular_function	5.81	2.99E-03	5.19E-02	9.44E-01	36
GO:0006261	DNA-dependent DNA replication	biological_process	5.81	2.99E-03	5.19E-02	9.44E-01	36
GO:0006458	'de novo' protein folding	biological_process	5.81	2.99E-03	5.19E-02	9.44E-01	36
GO:0032781	positive regulation of ATPase activity	biological_process	5.81	2.99E-03	5.19E-02	9.44E-01	36
GO:0031047	gene silencing by RNA	biological_process	5.80	3.02E-03	5.22E-02	9.18E-01	49
GO:0006893	Golgi to plasma membrane transport	biological_process	5.80	3.02E-03	5.22E-02	9.18E-01	49
GO:0046822	regulation of nucleocytoplasmic transport	biological_process	5.79	3.05E-03	5.27E-02	8.60E-01	121
GO:0006520	cellular amino acid metabolic process	biological_process	5.79	3.06E-03	5.28E-02	8.36E-01	201
GO:0045814	negative regulation of gene expression, epigenetic	biological_process	5.79	3.07E-03	5.29E-02	9.02E-01	61
GO:1904356	regulation of telomere maintenance via telomere lengthening	biological_process	5.79	3.07E-03	5.29E-02	9.02E-01	61
GO:0032387	negative regulation of intracellular transport	biological_process	5.79	3.07E-03	5.29E-02	9.02E-01	61
GO:0014070	response to organic cyclic compound	biological_process	5.78	3.08E-03	5.30E-02	8.09E-01	435
GO:0097549	chromatin organization involved in negative regulation of transcription	biological_process	5.78	3.09E-03	5.33E-02	9.09E-01	55
GO:1905952	regulation of lipid localization	biological_process	5.77	3.12E-03	5.36E-02	8.57E-01	126
GO:1902936	phosphatidylinositol bisphosphate binding	molecular_function	5.76	3.15E-03	5.40E-02	8.76E-01	89
GO:0051651	maintenance of location in cell	biological_process	5.76	3.15E-03	5.40E-02	8.76E-01	89
GO:0080134	regulation of response to stress	biological_process	5.75	3.17E-03	5.44E-02	7.86E-01	1219
GO:2000377	regulation of reactive oxygen species metabolic process	biological_process	5.75	3.18E-03	5.45E-02	8.39E-01	186
GO:0035326	cis-regulatory region binding	N/A	5.74	3.22E-03	5.51E-02	8.04E-01	516
GO:0071478	cellular response to radiation	biological_process	5.74	3.22E-03	5.51E-02	8.53E-01	136
GO:0014069	postsynaptic density	cellular_component	5.72	3.28E-03	5.61E-02	8.21E-01	291
GO:0098589	membrane region	N/A	5.72	3.29E-03	5.62E-02	8.17E-01	333
GO:0004519	endonuclease activity	molecular_function	5.71	3.31E-03	5.65E-02	8.64E-01	110
GO:0007568	aging	biological_process	5.71	3.31E-03	5.65E-02	8.64E-01	110
GO:1901657	glycosyl compound metabolic process	biological_process	5.70	3.35E-03	5.71E-02	8.72E-01	94
GO:0018022	peptidyl-lysine methylation	biological_process	5.69	3.36E-03	5.71E-02	8.89E-01	72

GO:0001889	liver development	biological_process	5.69	3.36E-03	5.71E-02	8.89E-01	72
GO:0006664	glycolipid metabolic process	biological_process	5.69	3.36E-03	5.71E-02	8.89E-01	72
GO:0007266	Rho protein signal transduction	biological_process	5.69	3.36E-03	5.71E-02	8.89E-01	72
GO:0009314	response to radiation	biological_process	5.69	3.37E-03	5.73E-02	8.16E-01	342
GO:2000278	regulation of DNA biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.68	3.42E-03	5.79E-02	8.61E-01	115
GO:0016042	lipid catabolic process	biological_process	5.68	3.42E-03	5.79E-02	8.35E-01	200
GO:0015985	energy coupled proton transport, down electrochemical gradient	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0015986	ATP synthesis coupled proton transport	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0016226	iron-sulfur cluster assembly	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0017049	GTP-Rho binding	N/A	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:2000209	regulation of anoikis	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0001091	RNA polymerase II general transcription initiation factor binding	molecular_function	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0051291	protein heterooligomerization	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0030662	coated vesicle membrane	cellular_component	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0031065	positive regulation of histone deacetylation	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0031163	metallo-sulfur cluster assembly	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0006383	transcription by RNA polymerase III	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0032365	intracellular lipid transport	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0032806	carboxy-terminal domain protein kinase complex	cellular_component	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0033617	mitochondrial respiratory chain complex IV assembly	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	1.00E+00	20
GO:0070534	protein K63-linked ubiquitination	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	9.29E-01	42
GO:0070849	response to epidermal growth factor	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	9.29E-01	42
GO:0055038	recycling endosome membrane	cellular_component	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	9.29E-01	42
GO:0009201	ribonucleoside triphosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	9.29E-01	42
GO:0090317	negative regulation of intracellular protein transport	biological_process	5.66	3.47E-03	5.79E-02	9.29E-01	42
GO:0097190	apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	5.65	3.52E-03	5.88E-02	8.27E-01	243
GO:0034401	chromatin organization involved in regulation of transcription	biological_process	5.64	3.56E-03	5.93E-02	8.94E-01	66
GO:0070536	protein K63-linked deubiquitination	biological_process	5.61	3.66E-03	6.06E-02	9.64E-01	28
GO:1902555	endoribonuclease complex	cellular_component	5.61	3.66E-03	6.06E-02	9.64E-01	28
GO:1903649	regulation of cytoplasmic transport	biological_process	5.61	3.66E-03	6.06E-02	9.64E-01	28
GO:0006354	DNA-templated transcription, elongation	biological_process	5.61	3.66E-03	6.06E-02	9.64E-01	28
GO:0032509	endosome transport via multivesicular body sorting pathway	biological_process	5.61	3.66E-03	6.06E-02	9.64E-01	28
GO:0033119	negative regulation of RNA splicing	biological_process	5.61	3.66E-03	6.06E-02	9.64E-01	28
GO:0034260	negative regulation of GTPase activity	biological_process	5.61	3.66E-03	6.06E-02	9.64E-01	28
GO:0032956	regulation of actin cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	5.60	3.68E-03	6.10E-02	8.15E-01	341
GO:1903076	regulation of protein localization to plasma membrane	biological_process	5.60	3.69E-03	6.11E-02	8.65E-01	104
GO:0045595	regulation of cell differentiation	biological_process	5.60	3.70E-03	6.12E-02	7.81E-01	1619
GO:0099513	polymeric cytoskeletal fiber	cellular_component	5.59	3.73E-03	6.16E-02	8.04E-01	514
GO:0043536	positive regulation of blood vessel endothelial cell migration	biological_process	5.58	3.76E-03	6.20E-02	9.07E-01	54

GO:0042149	cellular response to glucose starvation	biological_process	5.58	3.77E-03	6.20E-02	9.43E-01	35
GO:0051084	'de novo' posttranslational protein folding	biological_process	5.58	3.77E-03	6.20E-02	9.43E-01	35
GO:0007044	cell-substrate junction assembly	biological_process	5.58	3.77E-03	6.20E-02	9.43E-01	35
GO:0032506	cytokinetic process	biological_process	5.58	3.77E-03	6.20E-02	9.43E-01	35
GO:0032786	positive regulation of DNA-templated transcription, elongation	biological_process	5.58	3.77E-03	6.20E-02	9.43E-01	35
GO:0060840	artery development	biological_process	5.58	3.77E-03	6.20E-02	9.43E-01	35
GO:0150115	cell-substrate junction organization	biological_process	5.58	3.77E-03	6.20E-02	9.43E-01	35
GO:0098857	membrane microdomain	cellular_component	5.56	3.84E-03	6.30E-02	8.17E-01	322
GO:0099572	postsynaptic specialization	cellular_component	5.56	3.85E-03	6.31E-02	8.20E-01	294
GO:0060998	regulation of dendritic spine development	biological_process	5.54	3.92E-03	6.42E-02	8.71E-01	93
GO:0007623	circadian rhythm	biological_process	5.54	3.94E-03	6.45E-02	8.60E-01	114
GO:0009749	response to glucose	biological_process	5.52	4.00E-03	6.55E-02	8.87E-01	71
GO:0061024	membrane organization	biological_process	5.52	4.01E-03	6.55E-02	8.03E-01	513
GO:0006282	regulation of DNA repair	biological_process	5.51	4.03E-03	6.59E-02	8.57E-01	119
GO:0046677	response to antibiotic	biological_process	5.50	4.10E-03	6.70E-02	8.39E-01	174
GO:0045121	membrane raft	cellular_component	5.47	4.19E-03	6.84E-02	8.16E-01	321
GO:0001667	ameboidal-type cell migration	biological_process	5.46	4.24E-03	6.90E-02	8.47E-01	144
GO:1900006	positive regulation of dendrite development	biological_process	5.45	4.28E-03	6.97E-02	8.64E-01	103
GO:0048856	anatomical structure development	biological_process	5.45	4.29E-03	6.99E-02	7.73E-01	2747
GO:0030866	cortical actin cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	5.45	4.31E-03	7.00E-02	9.27E-01	41
GO:0043502	regulation of muscle adaptation	biological_process	5.44	4.32E-03	7.02E-02	8.74E-01	87
GO:0046165	alcohol biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.44	4.32E-03	7.02E-02	8.74E-01	87
GO:0005884	actin filament	cellular_component	5.44	4.32E-03	7.02E-02	8.74E-01	87
GO:0034644	cellular response to UV	biological_process	5.43	4.40E-03	7.14E-02	8.82E-01	76
GO:0043542	endothelial cell migration	biological_process	5.41	4.45E-03	7.20E-02	8.98E-01	59
GO:0051893	regulation of focal adhesion assembly	biological_process	5.41	4.45E-03	7.20E-02	8.98E-01	59
GO:0005080	protein kinase C binding	molecular_function	5.41	4.45E-03	7.20E-02	8.98E-01	59
GO:0090109	regulation of cell-substrate junction assembly	biological_process	5.41	4.45E-03	7.20E-02	8.98E-01	59
GO:0000978	RNA polymerase II cis-regulatory region sequence-specific DNA binding	molecular_function	5.41	4.47E-03	7.22E-02	8.04E-01	489
GO:0009725	response to hormone	biological_process	5.40	4.51E-03	7.28E-02	8.11E-01	380
GO:0046834	lipid phosphorylation	biological_process	5.39	4.54E-03	7.31E-02	9.15E-01	47
GO:0061014	positive regulation of mRNA catabolic process	biological_process	5.39	4.54E-03	7.31E-02	9.15E-01	47
GO:0090311	regulation of protein deacetylation	biological_process	5.39	4.54E-03	7.31E-02	9.15E-01	47
GO:0030832	regulation of actin filament length	biological_process	5.39	4.55E-03	7.31E-02	8.37E-01	178
GO:0006342	chromatin silencing	N/A	5.39	4.57E-03	7.31E-02	9.06E-01	53
GO:0008023	transcription elongation factor complex	cellular_component	5.39	4.57E-03	7.31E-02	9.06E-01	53
GO:0035306	positive regulation of dephosphorylation	biological_process	5.39	4.57E-03	7.31E-02	9.06E-01	53
GO:0042975	peroxisome proliferator activated receptor binding	molecular_function	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0070300	phosphatidic acid binding	molecular_function	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0070971	endoplasmic reticulum exit site	cellular_component	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:1900101	regulation of endoplasmic reticulum unfolded protein response	biological_process	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:2000641	regulation of early endosome to late endosome transport	biological_process	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19

GO:0000460	maturation of 5.8S rRNA	biological_process	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:1903798	regulation of production of miRNAs involved in gene silencing by miRNA	biological_process	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0140223	general transcription initiation factor activity	molecular_function	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0031082	BLOC complex	cellular_component	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0006353	DNA-templated transcription, termination	biological_process	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0006783	heme biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0010485	H4 histone acetyltransferase activity	molecular_function	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0035329	hippo signaling	biological_process	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0061912	selective autophagy	biological_process	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0038084	vascular endothelial growth factor signaling pathway	biological_process	5.38	4.61E-03	7.31E-02	1.00E+00	19
GO:0051223	regulation of protein transport	biological_process	5.37	4.67E-03	7.40E-02	7.97E-01	649
GO:0016891	endoribonuclease activity, producing 5'-phosphomonoesters	molecular_function	5.36	4.70E-03	7.40E-02	9.63E-01	27
GO:0018126	protein hydroxylation	biological_process	5.36	4.70E-03	7.40E-02	9.63E-01	27
GO:0001223	transcription coactivator binding	molecular_function	5.36	4.70E-03	7.40E-02	9.63E-01	27
GO:0031063	regulation of histone deacetylation	biological_process	5.36	4.70E-03	7.40E-02	9.63E-01	27
GO:0031440	regulation of mRNA 3'-end processing	biological_process	5.36	4.70E-03	7.40E-02	9.63E-01	27
GO:0032469	endoplasmic reticulum calcium ion homeostasis	biological_process	5.36	4.70E-03	7.40E-02	9.63E-01	27
GO:0008156	negative regulation of DNA replication	biological_process	5.36	4.70E-03	7.40E-02	9.63E-01	27
GO:0034394	protein localization to cell surface	biological_process	5.36	4.70E-03	7.40E-02	9.63E-01	27
GO:0090312	positive regulation of protein deacetylation	biological_process	5.36	4.70E-03	7.40E-02	9.63E-01	27
GO:0016504	peptidase activator activity	molecular_function	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	9.41E-01	34
GO:0042162	telomeric DNA binding	molecular_function	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	9.41E-01	34
GO:0071333	cellular response to glucose stimulus	biological_process	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	9.41E-01	34
GO:0097718	disordered domain specific binding	molecular_function	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	9.41E-01	34
GO:0051019	mitogen-activated protein kinase binding	molecular_function	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	9.41E-01	34
GO:0000979	RNA polymerase II core promoter sequence-specific DNA binding	molecular_function	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	9.41E-01	34
GO:0032435	negative regulation of proteasomal ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process	biological_process	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	9.41E-01	34
GO:0009409	response to cold	biological_process	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	9.41E-01	34
GO:0003730	mRNA 3'-UTR binding	molecular_function	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	8.77E-01	81
GO:0004553	hydrolase activity, hydrolyzing O-glycosyl compounds	molecular_function	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	8.86E-01	70
GO:0010507	negative regulation of autophagy	biological_process	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	8.86E-01	70
GO:0009755	hormone-mediated signaling pathway	biological_process	5.35	4.75E-03	7.43E-02	8.86E-01	70
GO:0001101	response to acid chemical	biological_process	5.35	4.76E-03	7.44E-02	8.28E-01	221
GO:0023014	signal transduction by protein phosphorylation	N/A	5.34	4.80E-03	7.49E-02	8.48E-01	138
GO:0010975	regulation of neuron projection development	biological_process	5.31	4.92E-03	7.67E-02	8.01E-01	537
GO:1901215	negative regulation of neuron death	biological_process	5.30	4.99E-03	7.77E-02	8.29E-01	211
GO:0031023	microtubule organizing center organization	biological_process	5.28	5.08E-03	7.91E-02	8.91E-01	64
GO:0032502	developmental process	biological_process	5.28	5.09E-03	7.92E-02	7.69E-01	3995
GO:0008064	regulation of actin polymerization or depolymerization	biological_process	5.28	5.10E-03	7.93E-02	8.36E-01	177
GO:0097435	supramolecular fiber organization	biological_process	5.27	5.12E-03	7.96E-02	8.09E-01	383

GO:0034284	response to monosaccharide	biological_process	5.26	5.20E-03	8.06E-02	8.80E-01	75
GO:2000142	regulation of DNA-templated transcription, initiation	biological_process	5.23	5.33E-03	8.26E-02	9.25E-01	40
GO:0030119	AP-type membrane coat adaptor complex	cellular_component	5.23	5.33E-03	8.26E-02	9.25E-01	40
GO:0009145	purine nucleoside triphosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.23	5.33E-03	8.26E-02	9.25E-01	40
GO:0045931	positive regulation of mitotic cell cycle	biological_process	5.23	5.35E-03	8.28E-02	8.41E-01	157
GO:0005546	phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate binding	molecular_function	5.23	5.36E-03	8.28E-02	8.97E-01	58
GO:0071229	cellular response to acid chemical	biological_process	5.22	5.40E-03	8.34E-02	8.42E-01	152
GO:0010634	positive regulation of epithelial cell migration	biological_process	5.21	5.45E-03	8.42E-02	8.47E-01	137
GO:0004860	protein kinase inhibitor activity	molecular_function	5.20	5.53E-03	8.53E-02	9.04E-01	52
GO:0009142	nucleoside triphosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.20	5.53E-03	8.53E-02	9.04E-01	52
GO:0051879	Hsp90 protein binding	molecular_function	5.19	5.56E-03	8.55E-02	9.13E-01	46
GO:0005844	polysome	cellular_component	5.19	5.56E-03	8.55E-02	9.13E-01	46
GO:0120163	negative regulation of cold-induced thermogenesis	biological_process	5.19	5.56E-03	8.55E-02	9.13E-01	46
GO:2001021	negative regulation of response to DNA damage stimulus	biological_process	5.18	5.64E-03	8.67E-02	8.84E-01	69
GO:0045860	positive regulation of protein kinase activity	biological_process	5.14	5.84E-03	8.98E-02	8.08E-01	395
GO:0032231	regulation of actin filament bundle assembly	biological_process	5.14	5.87E-03	9.01E-02	8.58E-01	106
GO:0042542	response to hydrogen peroxide	biological_process	5.13	5.91E-03	9.07E-02	8.71E-01	85
GO:1903427	negative regulation of reactive oxygen species biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.12	5.97E-03	9.10E-02	9.39E-01	33
GO:0001885	endothelial cell development	biological_process	5.12	5.97E-03	9.10E-02	9.39E-01	33
GO:0030134	COPII-coated ER to Golgi transport vesicle	cellular_component	5.12	5.97E-03	9.10E-02	9.39E-01	33
GO:0006623	protein targeting to vacuole	biological_process	5.12	5.97E-03	9.10E-02	9.39E-01	33
GO:0032355	response to estradiol	biological_process	5.12	5.97E-03	9.10E-02	9.39E-01	33
GO:0032728	positive regulation of interferon-beta production	biological_process	5.12	5.97E-03	9.10E-02	9.39E-01	33
GO:0009060	aerobic respiration	biological_process	5.12	5.97E-03	9.10E-02	9.39E-01	33
GO:0036002	pre-mRNA binding	molecular_function	5.12	5.97E-03	9.10E-02	9.39E-01	33
GO:0032273	positive regulation of protein polymerization	biological_process	5.12	5.99E-03	9.10E-02	8.56E-01	111
GO:0016577	histone demethylation	biological_process	5.11	6.03E-03	9.10E-02	9.62E-01	26
GO:0042168	heme metabolic process	biological_process	5.11	6.03E-03	9.10E-02	9.62E-01	26
GO:0070076	histone lysine demethylation	biological_process	5.11	6.03E-03	9.10E-02	9.62E-01	26
GO:0045047	protein targeting to ER	biological_process	5.11	6.03E-03	9.10E-02	9.62E-01	26
GO:0070979	protein K11-linked ubiquitination	biological_process	5.11	6.03E-03	9.10E-02	9.62E-01	26
GO:0032452	histone demethylase activity	molecular_function	5.11	6.03E-03	9.10E-02	9.62E-01	26
GO:0035904	aorta development	biological_process	5.11	6.03E-03	9.10E-02	9.62E-01	26
GO:0016251	RNA polymerase II general transcription initiation factor activity	molecular_function	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0016514	SWI/SNF complex	cellular_component	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0042274	ribosomal small subunit biogenesis	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0016780	phosphotransferase activity, for other substituted phosphate groups	molecular_function	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0042982	amyloid precursor protein metabolic process	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0070131	positive regulation of mitochondrial translation	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0045324	late endosome to vacuole transport	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0045722	positive regulation of gluconeogenesis	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18

GO:0071616	acyl-CoA biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0097602	cullin family protein binding	molecular_function	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
	negative regulation of endoplasmic reticulum stress-induced						
GO:1902236	intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0050435	amyloid-beta metabolic process	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:1903599	positive regulation of autophagy of mitochondrion	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:1904262	negative regulation of TORC1 signaling	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0140102	catalytic activity, acting on a rRNA	molecular_function	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0031167	rRNA methylation	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0005666	RNA polymerase III complex	cellular_component	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0005686	U2 snRNP	cellular_component	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0005740	mitochondrial envelope	cellular_component	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0032239	regulation of nucleobase-containing compound transport	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0006743	ubiquinone metabolic process	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0008139	nuclear localization sequence binding	molecular_function	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0008649	rRNA methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0034472	snRNA 3'-end processing	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0060544	regulation of necroptotic process	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0035384	thioester biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.10	6.11E-03	9.10E-02	1.00E+00	18
GO:0019003	GDP binding	molecular_function	5.10	6.12E-03	9.10E-02	8.78E-01	74
GO:0010631	epithelial cell migration	biological_process	5.10	6.12E-03	9.10E-02	8.78E-01	74
GO:0009746	response to hexose	biological_process	5.10	6.12E-03	9.10E-02	8.78E-01	74
GO:0017124	SH3 domain binding	molecular_function	5.09	6.14E-03	9.11E-02	8.51E-01	121
GO:0032886	regulation of microtubule-based process	biological_process	5.07	6.31E-03	9.36E-02	8.25E-01	223
GO:2001238	positive regulation of extrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway	biological_process	5.05	6.43E-03	9.53E-02	8.95E-01	57
GO:0008286	insulin receptor signaling pathway	biological_process	5.05	6.43E-03	9.53E-02	8.95E-01	57
GO:0071453	cellular response to oxygen levels	biological_process	5.03	6.54E-03	9.69E-02	8.73E-01	79
GO:0016879	ligase activity, forming carbon-nitrogen bonds	molecular_function	5.02	6.60E-03	9.73E-02	9.23E-01	39
GO:0071364	cellular response to epidermal growth factor stimulus	biological_process	5.02	6.60E-03	9.73E-02	9.23E-01	39
GO:0072666	establishment of protein localization to vacuole	biological_process	5.02	6.60E-03	9.73E-02	9.23E-01	39
GO:0031985	Golgi cisterna	cellular_component	5.02	6.60E-03	9.73E-02	9.23E-01	39
GO:0009206	purine ribonucleoside triphosphate biosynthetic process	biological_process	5.02	6.60E-03	9.73E-02	9.23E-01	39
GO:0035307	positive regulation of protein dephosphorylation	biological_process	5.02	6.60E-03	9.73E-02	9.23E-01	39
GO:0002039	p53 binding	molecular_function	5.01	6.68E-03	9.84E-02	8.82E-01	68
GO:0005543	phospholipid binding	molecular_function	5.01	6.68E-03	9.84E-02	8.09E-01	366
GO:0032481	positive regulation of type I interferon production	biological_process	5.01	6.70E-03	9.85E-02	9.02E-01	51
GO:0010656	negative regulation of muscle cell apoptotic process	biological_process	5.01	6.70E-03	9.85E-02	9.02E-01	51
GO:0070988	demethylation	biological_process	4.99	6.79E-03	9.95E-02	9.11E-01	45
GO:0071322	cellular response to carbohydrate stimulus	biological_process	4.99	6.79E-03	9.95E-02	9.11E-01	45
GO:0051402	neuron apoptotic process	biological_process	4.99	6.79E-03	9.95E-02	9.11E-01	45
GO:0030331	estrogen receptor binding	molecular_function	4.99	6.79E-03	9.95E-02	9.11E-01	45
GO:1900180	regulation of protein localization to nucleus	biological_process	4.96	7.02E-03	1.03E-01	8.48E-01	125

GO:0030496	midbody	cellular_component	4.96	7.03E-03	1.03E-01	8.46E-01	130
GO:0032535	regulation of cellular component size	biological_process	4.94	7.12E-03	1.04E-01	8.18E-01	264
GO:0051347	positive regulation of transferase activity	biological_process	4.94	7.12E-03	1.04E-01	7.99E-01	536
GO:0010720	positive regulation of cell development	biological_process	4.94	7.17E-03	1.05E-01	7.97E-01	567
GO:0040013	negative regulation of locomotion	biological_process	4.94	7.17E-03	1.05E-01	8.14E-01	301
GO:1901888	regulation of cell junction assembly	biological_process	4.94	7.19E-03	1.05E-01	8.65E-01	89
GO:1903509	liposaccharide metabolic process	biological_process	4.93	7.21E-03	1.05E-01	8.77E-01	73
GO:0022625	cytosolic large ribosomal subunit	cellular_component	4.93	7.21E-03	1.05E-01	8.87E-01	62
GO:0060999	positive regulation of dendritic spine development	biological_process	4.93	7.21E-03	1.05E-01	8.87E-01	62
GO:2000144	positive regulation of DNA-templated transcription, initiation	biological_process	4.89	7.49E-03	1.09E-01	9.38E-01	32
GO:0046320	regulation of fatty acid oxidation	biological_process	4.89	7.49E-03	1.09E-01	9.38E-01	32
GO:0071985	multivesicular body sorting pathway	biological_process	4.89	7.49E-03	1.09E-01	9.38E-01	32
GO:0051059	NF-kappaB binding	molecular_function	4.89	7.49E-03	1.09E-01	9.38E-01	32
GO:0031112	positive regulation of microtubule polymerization or depolymerization	biological_process	4.89	7.49E-03	1.09E-01	9.38E-01	32
GO:0006900	vesicle budding from membrane	biological_process	4.89	7.49E-03	1.09E-01	9.38E-01	32
GO:0007507	heart development	biological_process	4.89	7.49E-03	1.09E-01	8.23E-01	226
GO:0003700	DNA-binding transcription factor activity	molecular_function	4.89	7.53E-03	1.09E-01	7.90E-01	786
GO:0000149	SNARE binding	molecular_function	4.88	7.62E-03	1.10E-01	8.59E-01	99
GO:0004721	phosphoprotein phosphatase activity	molecular_function	4.88	7.63E-03	1.10E-01	8.38E-01	154
GO:0019217	regulation of fatty acid metabolic process	biological_process	4.87	7.66E-03	1.11E-01	8.72E-01	78
GO:0042770	signal transduction in response to DNA damage	biological_process	4.87	7.70E-03	1.11E-01	8.93E-01	56
GO:0070997	neuron death	biological_process	4.87	7.70E-03	1.11E-01	8.93E-01	56
GO:0042026	protein refolding	biological_process	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:0016866	intramolecular transferase activity	molecular_function	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:0000030	mannosyltransferase activity	molecular_function	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:1903671	negative regulation of sprouting angiogenesis	biological_process	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:1904357	negative regulation of telomere maintenance via telomere lengthening	biological_process	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:0030660	Golgi-associated vesicle membrane	cellular_component	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:0032373	positive regulation of sterol transport	biological_process	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:0032376	positive regulation of cholesterol transport	biological_process	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:0007031	peroxisome organization	biological_process	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:0032878	regulation of establishment or maintenance of cell polarity	biological_process	4.86	7.73E-03	1.11E-01	9.60E-01	25
GO:0030100	regulation of endocytosis	biological_process	4.86	7.74E-03	1.11E-01	8.27E-01	202
GO:2001022	positive regulation of response to DNA damage stimulus	biological_process	4.86	7.76E-03	1.11E-01	8.56E-01	104
GO:0030097	hemopoiesis	biological_process	4.86	7.76E-03	1.11E-01	8.56E-01	104
GO:0090087	regulation of peptide transport	biological_process	4.86	7.78E-03	1.11E-01	7.93E-01	676
GO:0043433	negative regulation of DNA-binding transcription factor activity	biological_process	4.85	7.81E-03	1.12E-01	8.40E-01	144
GO:0043618	regulation of transcription from RNA polymerase II promoter in response to stress	biological_process	4.82	8.09E-03	1.14E-01	9.00E-01	50
GO:0045599	negative regulation of fat cell differentiation	biological_process	4.82	8.09E-03	1.14E-01	9.00E-01	50

GO:0031648	protein destabilization	biological_process	4.82	8.09E-03	1.14E-01	9.00E-01	50
GO:0032206	positive regulation of telomere maintenance	biological_process	4.82	8.09E-03	1.14E-01	9.00E-01	50
GO:0043574	peroxisomal transport	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0045259	proton-transporting ATP synthase complex	cellular_component	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0070822	Sin3-type complex	cellular_component	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0071359	cellular response to dsRNA	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:2000001	regulation of DNA damage checkpoint	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:1900363	regulation of mRNA polyadenylation	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0022624	proteasome accessory complex	cellular_component	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:1901524	regulation of mitophagy	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0000028	ribosomal small subunit assembly	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0000380	alternative mRNA splicing, via spliceosome	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0001522	pseudouridine synthesis	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0051895	negative regulation of focal adhesion assembly	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0002098	tRNA wobble uridine modification	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0004602	glutathione peroxidase activity	molecular_function	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0030150	protein import into mitochondrial matrix	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0031231	intrinsic component of peroxisomal membrane	cellular_component	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0005753	mitochondrial proton-transporting ATP synthase complex	cellular_component	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0006448	regulation of translational elongation	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0034389	lipid droplet organization	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0150118	negative regulation of cell-substrate junction organization	biological_process	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0015035	protein disulfide oxidoreductase activity	molecular_function	4.81	8.12E-03	1.14E-01	1.00E+00	17
GO:0004712	protein serine/threonine/tyrosine kinase activity	molecular_function	4.81	8.14E-03	1.14E-01	9.21E-01	38
GO:2000725	regulation of cardiac muscle cell differentiation	biological_process	4.79	8.28E-03	1.16E-01	9.09E-01	44
GO:0007029	endoplasmic reticulum organization	biological_process	4.79	8.28E-03	1.16E-01	9.09E-01	44
GO:0120162	positive regulation of cold-induced thermogenesis	biological_process	4.79	8.34E-03	1.17E-01	8.64E-01	88
GO:0034404	nucleobase-containing small molecule biosynthetic process	biological_process	4.77	8.47E-03	1.19E-01	8.75E-01	72
GO:0060284	regulation of cell development	biological_process	4.75	8.69E-03	1.22E-01	7.86E-01	931
GO:0104004	cellular response to environmental stimulus	biological_process	4.74	8.74E-03	1.22E-01	8.23E-01	215
GO:0071214	cellular response to abiotic stimulus	biological_process	4.74	8.74E-03	1.22E-01	8.23E-01	215
GO:0055076	transition metal ion homeostasis	biological_process	4.74	8.77E-03	1.22E-01	8.57E-01	98
GO:0019209	kinase activator activity	molecular_function	4.72	8.95E-03	1.25E-01	8.70E-01	77
GO:0062012	regulation of small molecule metabolic process	biological_process	4.72	8.95E-03	1.25E-01	8.12E-01	303
GO:0043620	regulation of DNA-templated transcription in response to stress	biological_process	4.69	9.22E-03	1.28E-01	8.91E-01	55
GO:0001678	cellular glucose homeostasis	biological_process	4.69	9.22E-03	1.28E-01	8.91E-01	55
GO:1901214	regulation of neuron death	biological_process	4.68	9.28E-03	1.29E-01	8.09E-01	330
GO:0070373	negative regulation of ERK1 and ERK2 cascade	biological_process	4.68	9.32E-03	1.30E-01	8.79E-01	66
GO:0000077	DNA damage checkpoint	biological_process	4.68	9.32E-03	1.30E-01	8.79E-01	66
GO:0042592	homeostatic process	biological_process	4.67	9.37E-03	1.30E-01	7.81E-01	1239
GO:0043537	negative regulation of blood vessel endothelial cell migration	biological_process	4.67	9.38E-03	1.30E-01	9.35E-01	31

GO:1900181	negative regulation of protein localization to nucleus	biological_process	4.67	9.38E-03	1.30E-01	9.35E-01	31
GO:0080008	Cul4-RING E3 ubiquitin ligase complex	cellular_component	4.67	9.38E-03	1.30E-01	9.35E-01	31
GO:0030330	DNA damage response, signal transduction by p53 class mediator	biological_process	4.67	9.38E-03	1.30E-01	9.35E-01	31
GO:0009161	ribonucleoside monophosphate metabolic process	biological_process	4.67	9.38E-03	1.30E-01	9.35E-01	31
GO:0044042	glucan metabolic process	biological_process	4.63	9.75E-03	1.35E-01	8.98E-01	49
GO:0072332	intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway by p53 class mediator	biological_process	4.63	9.75E-03	1.35E-01	8.98E-01	49
GO:0006073	cellular glucan metabolic process	biological_process	4.63	9.75E-03	1.35E-01	8.98E-01	49
GO:0005977	glycogen metabolic process	biological_process	4.63	9.75E-03	1.35E-01	8.98E-01	49
GO:0034446	substrate adhesion-dependent cell spreading	biological_process	4.63	9.75E-03	1.35E-01	8.98E-01	49
GO:0061951	establishment of protein localization to plasma membrane	biological_process	4.63	9.75E-03	1.35E-01	8.98E-01	49
GO:0035303	regulation of dephosphorylation	biological_process	4.63	9.75E-03	1.35E-01	8.37E-01	147
GO:0050772	positive regulation of axonogenesis	biological_process	4.62	9.89E-03	1.35E-01	8.59E-01	92
GO:0051492	regulation of stress fiber assembly	biological_process	4.62	9.89E-03	1.35E-01	8.59E-01	92
GO:0010660	regulation of muscle cell apoptotic process	biological_process	4.62	9.89E-03	1.35E-01	8.59E-01	92
GO:0016556	mRNA modification	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0044003	modification by symbiont of host morphology or physiology	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0070584	mitochondrion morphogenesis	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0097352	autophagosome maturation	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0048010	vascular endothelial growth factor receptor signaling pathway	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:1902414	protein localization to cell junction	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0050687	negative regulation of defense response to virus	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0031529	ruffle organization	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0033522	histone H2A ubiquitination	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0060261	positive regulation of transcription initiation from RNA polymerase II promoter	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0090181	regulation of cholesterol metabolic process	biological_process	4.62	9.90E-03	1.35E-01	9.58E-01	24
GO:0000422	autophagy of mitochondrion	biological_process	4.60	1.00E-02	1.37E-01	9.19E-01	37
GO:0055026	negative regulation of cardiac muscle tissue development	biological_process	4.60	1.00E-02	1.37E-01	9.19E-01	37
GO:0005547	phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate binding	molecular_function	4.60	1.00E-02	1.37E-01	9.19E-01	37
GO:0061726	mitochondrion disassembly	biological_process	4.60	1.00E-02	1.37E-01	9.19E-01	37
GO:0090049	regulation of cell migration involved in sprouting angiogenesis	biological_process	4.60	1.00E-02	1.37E-01	9.19E-01	37
GO:1902041	regulation of extrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway via death domain receptors	biological_process	4.60	1.01E-02	1.37E-01	9.07E-01	43
GO:1903293	phosphatase complex	cellular_component	4.60	1.01E-02	1.37E-01	9.07E-01	43
GO:0031902	late endosome membrane	cellular_component	4.60	1.01E-02	1.37E-01	9.07E-01	43
GO:0008287	protein serine/threonine phosphatase complex	cellular_component	4.60	1.01E-02	1.37E-01	9.07E-01	43
GO:0010828	positive regulation of glucose transmembrane transport	biological_process	4.60	1.01E-02	1.37E-01	9.07E-01	43
GO:0016835	carbon-oxygen lyase activity	molecular_function	4.59	1.02E-02	1.38E-01	8.83E-01	60

GO:1903008	organelle disassembly	biological_process	4.59	1.02E-02	1.38E-01	8.83E-01	60
GO:0000381	regulation of alternative mRNA splicing, via spliceosome	biological_process	4.59	1.02E-02	1.38E-01	8.83E-01	60
GO:0031122	cytoplasmic microtubule organization	biological_process	4.59	1.02E-02	1.38E-01	8.83E-01	60
GO:0034968	histone lysine methylation	biological_process	4.59	1.02E-02	1.38E-01	8.83E-01	60
GO:0015078	proton transmembrane transporter activity	molecular_function	4.59	1.02E-02	1.38E-01	8.53E-01	102
GO:0051604	protein maturation	biological_process	4.58	1.03E-02	1.39E-01	8.27E-01	185
GO:0012505	endomembrane system	cellular_component	4.58	1.03E-02	1.39E-01	8.44E-01	122
GO:0043122	regulation of I-kappaB kinase/NF-kappaB signaling	biological_process	4.57	1.04E-02	1.40E-01	8.32E-01	161
GO:0050769	positive regulation of neurogenesis	biological_process	4.55	1.05E-02	1.42E-01	7.98E-01	499
GO:0033500	carbohydrate homeostasis	biological_process	4.55	1.06E-02	1.42E-01	8.33E-01	156
GO:0016075	rRNA catabolic process	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0016854	racemase and epimerase activity	molecular_function	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0043149	stress fiber assembly	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0070932	histone H3 deacetylation	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:1900037	regulation of cellular response to hypoxia	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0046831	regulation of RNA export from nucleus	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0046933	proton-transporting ATP synthase activity, rotational mechanism	molecular_function	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:1901663	quinone biosynthetic process	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0098974	postsynaptic actin cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0099188	postsynaptic cytoskeleton organization	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:1903358	regulation of Golgi organization	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:1903513	endoplasmic reticulum to cytosol transport	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0001056	RNA polymerase III activity	molecular_function	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0030014	CCR4-NOT complex	cellular_component	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0030038	contractile actin filament bundle assembly	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0030970	retrograde protein transport, ER to cytosol	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0005662	DNA replication factor A complex	cellular_component	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0005779	integral component of peroxisomal membrane	cellular_component	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0005852	eukaryotic translation initiation factor 3 complex	cellular_component	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0006089	lactate metabolic process	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0006744	ubiquinone biosynthetic process	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0006896	Golgi to vacuole transport	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0032986	protein-DNA complex disassembly	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0034399	nuclear periphery	cellular_component	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0034979	NAD-dependent protein deacetylase activity	molecular_function	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0010888	negative regulation of lipid storage	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0035459	vesicle cargo loading	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:1990868	response to chemokine	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:1990869	cellular response to chemokine	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0090069	regulation of ribosome biogenesis	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0090151	establishment of protein localization to mitochondrial membrane	biological_process	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	1.00E+00	16
GO:0030674	protein binding, bridging	molecular_function	4.53	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	8.25E-01	194
GO:0097517	contractile actin filament bundle	cellular_component	4.52	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	8.64E-01	81

GO:0001725	stress fiber	cellular_component	4.52	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	8.64E-01	81
GO:0032479	regulation of type I interferon production	biological_process	4.52	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	8.64E-01	81
GO:0090630	activation of GTPase activity	biological_process	4.52	1.08E-02	1.43E-01	8.64E-01	81
GO:0043462	regulation of ATPase activity	biological_process	4.51	1.10E-02	1.45E-01	8.89E-01	54
GO:0061001	regulation of dendritic spine morphogenesis	biological_process	4.51	1.10E-02	1.45E-01	8.89E-01	54
GO:0005798	Golgi-associated vesicle	cellular_component	4.50	1.12E-02	1.47E-01	8.60E-01	86
GO:0034330	cell junction organization	biological_process	4.48	1.13E-02	1.49E-01	8.30E-01	165
GO:0006066	alcohol metabolic process	biological_process	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	8.17E-01	240
GO:0045177	apical part of cell	cellular_component	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	8.51E-01	101
GO:0072659	protein localization to plasma membrane	biological_process	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	8.27E-01	179
GO:0048511	rhythmic process	biological_process	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	8.21E-01	212
GO:0043631	RNA polyadenylation	biological_process	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	9.33E-01	30
GO:0071889	14-3-3 protein binding	molecular_function	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	9.33E-01	30
GO:0051085	chaperone cofactor-dependent protein refolding	biological_process	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	9.33E-01	30
GO:0007097	nuclear migration	biological_process	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	9.33E-01	30
GO:0009262	deoxyribonucleotide metabolic process	biological_process	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	9.33E-01	30
GO:1903533	regulation of protein targeting	biological_process	4.45	1.17E-02	1.53E-01	8.96E-01	48
GO:0042593	glucose homeostasis	biological_process	4.44	1.18E-02	1.54E-01	8.32E-01	155
GO:0048732	gland development	biological_process	4.43	1.19E-02	1.56E-01	8.24E-01	193
GO:0032970	regulation of actin filament-based process	biological_process	4.43	1.20E-02	1.56E-01	8.03E-01	381
GO:0006090	pyruvate metabolic process	biological_process	4.42	1.21E-02	1.57E-01	8.81E-01	59
GO:0016052	carbohydrate catabolic process	biological_process	4.41	1.22E-02	1.58E-01	8.67E-01	75
GO:0046825	regulation of protein export from nucleus	biological_process	4.40	1.22E-02	1.59E-01	9.05E-01	42
GO:0000152	nuclear ubiquitin ligase complex	cellular_component	4.40	1.22E-02	1.59E-01	9.05E-01	42
GO:0010976	positive regulation of neuron projection development	biological_process	4.40	1.23E-02	1.60E-01	8.07E-01	331
GO:0045601	regulation of endothelial cell differentiation	biological_process	4.39	1.23E-02	1.60E-01	9.17E-01	36
GO:0098531	ligand-activated transcription factor activity	molecular_function	4.39	1.23E-02	1.60E-01	9.17E-01	36
GO:0043230	extracellular organelle	cellular_component	4.38	1.26E-02	1.63E-01	8.63E-01	80
GO:0045292	mRNA cis splicing, via spliceosome	biological_process	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:0045648	positive regulation of erythrocyte differentiation	biological_process	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:2000765	regulation of cytoplasmic translation	biological_process	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:0046931	pore complex assembly	biological_process	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:0048025	negative regulation of mRNA splicing, via spliceosome	biological_process	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:0051457	maintenance of protein location in nucleus	biological_process	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:0051537	2 iron, 2 sulfur cluster binding	molecular_function	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:0051787	misfolded protein binding	molecular_function	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:0032968	positive regulation of transcription elongation from RNA polymerase II promoter	biological_process	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:0009299	mRNA transcription	biological_process	4.37	1.27E-02	1.63E-01	9.57E-01	23
GO:0006575	cellular modified amino acid metabolic process	biological_process	4.37	1.27E-02	1.64E-01	8.37E-01	135
GO:0051702	interaction with symbiont	biological_process	4.35	1.29E-02	1.66E-01	8.75E-01	64
GO:0071156	regulation of cell cycle arrest	N/A	4.33	1.31E-02	1.68E-01	8.87E-01	53
GO:2000134	negative regulation of G1/S transition of mitotic cell cycle	biological_process	4.33	1.31E-02	1.68E-01	8.87E-01	53

GO:0032648	regulation of interferon-beta production	biological_process	4.33	1.31E-02	1.68E-01	8.87E-01	53
GO:0009185	ribonucleoside diphosphate metabolic process	biological_process	4.33	1.31E-02	1.68E-01	8.87E-01	53
GO:0009247	glycolipid biosynthetic process	biological_process	4.33	1.31E-02	1.68E-01	8.87E-01	53
GO:0061515	myeloid cell development	biological_process	4.33	1.31E-02	1.68E-01	8.87E-01	53
GO:0045765	regulation of angiogenesis	biological_process	4.33	1.32E-02	1.70E-01	8.11E-01	280
GO:0045807	positive regulation of endocytosis	biological_process	4.32	1.33E-02	1.70E-01	8.43E-01	115
GO:2000146	negative regulation of cell motility	biological_process	4.32	1.33E-02	1.71E-01	8.13E-01	257
GO:0048145	regulation of fibroblast proliferation	biological_process	4.32	1.33E-02	1.71E-01	8.50E-01	100
GO:0046434	organophosphate catabolic process	biological_process	4.32	1.34E-02	1.71E-01	8.48E-01	105
GO:0004672	protein kinase activity	molecular_function	4.27	1.39E-02	1.78E-01	7.93E-01	552
GO:0016776	phosphotransferase activity, phosphate group as acceptor	molecular_function	4.26	1.41E-02	1.79E-01	8.94E-01	47
GO:0097581	lamellipodium organization	biological_process	4.26	1.41E-02	1.79E-01	8.94E-01	47
GO:1905515	non-motile cilium assembly	biological_process	4.26	1.41E-02	1.79E-01	8.94E-01	47
GO:0006487	protein N-linked glycosylation	biological_process	4.26	1.41E-02	1.79E-01	8.94E-01	47
GO:0045666	positive regulation of neuron differentiation	biological_process	4.25	1.42E-02	1.79E-01	8.00E-01	401
GO:0000904	cell morphogenesis involved in differentiation	biological_process	4.25	1.42E-02	1.79E-01	8.36E-01	134
GO:0016765	transferase activity, transferring alkyl or aryl (other than methyl) groups	molecular_function	4.25	1.42E-02	1.79E-01	8.79E-01	58
GO:0015919	peroxisomal membrane transport	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0042255	ribosome assembly	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0017136	NAD-dependent histone deacetylase activity	molecular_function	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0044068	modulation by symbiont of host cellular process	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0043981	histone H4-K5 acetylation	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0043982	histone H4-K8 acetylation	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0044827	modulation by host of viral genome replication	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0071004	U2-type prespliceosome	cellular_component	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0070897	transcription preinitiation complex assembly	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0071010	prespliceosome	cellular_component	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0071392	cellular response to estradiol stimulus	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0046755	viral budding	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:2000811	negative regulation of anoikis	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:2001034	positive regulation of double-strand break repair via nonhomologous end joining	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0072662	protein localization to peroxisome	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0072663	establishment of protein localization to peroxisome	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0048038	quinone binding	molecular_function	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:1902188	positive regulation of viral release from host cell	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0051290	protein heterotetramerization	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:1904263	positive regulation of TORC1 signaling	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:1904814	regulation of protein localization to chromosome, telomeric region	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0080009	mRNA methylation	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0140053	mitochondrial gene expression	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0005671	Ada2/Gcn5/Ada3 transcription activator complex	cellular_component	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0005682	U5 snRNP	cellular_component	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15

GO:0005797	Golgi medial cisterna	cellular_component	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0006474	N-terminal protein amino acid acetylation	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0006625	protein targeting to peroxisome	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0033202	DNA helicase complex	cellular_component	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0008432	JUN kinase binding	molecular_function	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0034236	protein kinase A catalytic subunit binding	molecular_function	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0035102	PRC1 complex	cellular_component	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0035196	production of miRNAs involved in gene silencing by miRNA	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0062099	negative regulation of programmed necrotic cell death	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0090141	positive regulation of mitochondrial fission	biological_process	4.25	1.43E-02	1.79E-01	1.00E+00	15
GO:0045597	positive regulation of cell differentiation	biological_process	4.23	1.45E-02	1.81E-01	7.83E-01	955
GO:0051093	negative regulation of developmental process	biological_process	4.23	1.45E-02	1.81E-01	7.84E-01	899
GO:0000027	ribosomal large subunit assembly	biological_process	4.22	1.46E-02	1.82E-01	9.31E-01	29
GO:0050681	androgen receptor binding	molecular_function	4.22	1.46E-02	1.82E-01	9.31E-01	29
GO:0051205	protein insertion into membrane	biological_process	4.22	1.46E-02	1.82E-01	9.31E-01	29
GO:1904292	regulation of ERAD pathway	biological_process	4.22	1.46E-02	1.82E-01	9.31E-01	29
GO:1905476	negative regulation of protein localization to membrane	biological_process	4.22	1.46E-02	1.82E-01	9.31E-01	29
GO:0031116	positive regulation of microtubule polymerization	biological_process	4.22	1.46E-02	1.82E-01	9.31E-01	29
GO:0006099	tricarboxylic acid cycle	biological_process	4.22	1.46E-02	1.82E-01	9.31E-01	29
GO:0006739	NADP metabolic process	biological_process	4.22	1.46E-02	1.82E-01	9.31E-01	29
GO:0090568	nuclear transcriptional repressor complex	N/A	4.22	1.46E-02	1.82E-01	9.31E-01	29
GO:2000008	regulation of protein localization to cell surface	biological_process	4.21	1.48E-02	1.84E-01	9.02E-01	41
GO:0010824	regulation of centrosome duplication	biological_process	4.21	1.48E-02	1.84E-01	9.02E-01	41
GO:0045069	regulation of viral genome replication	biological_process	4.21	1.48E-02	1.84E-01	8.57E-01	84
GO:0031110	regulation of microtubule polymerization or depolymerization	biological_process	4.21	1.48E-02	1.84E-01	8.57E-01	84
GO:0098727	maintenance of cell number	biological_process	4.21	1.49E-02	1.84E-01	8.40E-01	119
GO:1902904	negative regulation of supramolecular fiber organization	biological_process	4.20	1.50E-02	1.86E-01	8.31E-01	148
GO:0008092	cytoskeletal protein binding	molecular_function	4.19	1.51E-02	1.86E-01	7.84E-01	881
GO:0008289	lipid binding	molecular_function	4.19	1.51E-02	1.86E-01	7.91E-01	612
GO:0030307	positive regulation of cell growth	biological_process	4.19	1.51E-02	1.86E-01	8.26E-01	167
GO:0072523	purine-containing compound catabolic process	biological_process	4.19	1.52E-02	1.86E-01	9.14E-01	35
GO:0004879	nuclear receptor activity	molecular_function	4.19	1.52E-02	1.86E-01	9.14E-01	35
GO:0031124	mRNA 3'-end processing	biological_process	4.19	1.52E-02	1.86E-01	9.14E-01	35
GO:0061980	regulatory RNA binding	molecular_function	4.19	1.52E-02	1.86E-01	9.14E-01	35
GO:0071897	DNA biosynthetic process	biological_process	4.19	1.52E-02	1.86E-01	8.73E-01	63
GO:0010633	negative regulation of epithelial cell migration	biological_process	4.19	1.52E-02	1.86E-01	8.73E-01	63
GO:0016798	hydrolase activity, acting on glycosyl bonds	molecular_function	4.19	1.52E-02	1.86E-01	8.51E-01	94
GO:0019751	polyol metabolic process	biological_process	4.19	1.52E-02	1.87E-01	8.48E-01	99
GO:0030336	negative regulation of cell migration	biological_process	4.16	1.55E-02	1.91E-01	8.13E-01	246
GO:0051100	negative regulation of binding	biological_process	4.16	1.55E-02	1.91E-01	8.27E-01	162
GO:0032210	regulation of telomere maintenance via telomerase	biological_process	4.16	1.56E-02	1.91E-01	8.85E-01	52

GO:0045664	regulation of neuron differentiation	biological_process	4.15	1.57E-02	1.93E-01	7.89E-01	668
GO:0005089	Rho guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity	N/A	4.14	1.59E-02	1.94E-01	8.68E-01	68
GO:0007163	establishment or maintenance of cell polarity	biological_process	4.14	1.59E-02	1.95E-01	8.28E-01	157
GO:0019320	hexose catabolic process	biological_process	4.13	1.62E-02	1.97E-01	9.55E-01	22
GO:0097502	mannosylation	biological_process	4.13	1.62E-02	1.97E-01	9.55E-01	22
GO:1903077	negative regulation of protein localization to plasma membrane	biological_process	4.13	1.62E-02	1.97E-01	9.55E-01	22
GO:0005849	mRNA cleavage factor complex	cellular_component	4.13	1.62E-02	1.97E-01	9.55E-01	22
GO:0010499	proteasomal ubiquitin-independent protein catabolic process	biological_process	4.13	1.62E-02	1.97E-01	9.55E-01	22
GO:0035162	embryonic hemopoiesis	biological_process	4.13	1.62E-02	1.97E-01	9.55E-01	22
GO:1904375	regulation of protein localization to cell periphery	biological_process	4.12	1.62E-02	1.98E-01	8.36E-01	128
GO:0022406	membrane docking	biological_process	4.11	1.64E-02	2.00E-01	8.63E-01	73
GO:0046916	cellular transition metal ion homeostasis	biological_process	4.11	1.64E-02	2.00E-01	8.63E-01	73
GO:1901983	regulation of protein acetylation	biological_process	4.11	1.64E-02	2.00E-01	8.63E-01	73
GO:0098657	import into cell	biological_process	4.10	1.66E-02	2.02E-01	8.01E-01	372
GO:0048513	animal organ development	biological_process	4.10	1.66E-02	2.02E-01	7.81E-01	1072
GO:0003924	GTPase activity	molecular_function	4.09	1.68E-02	2.04E-01	8.10E-01	268
GO:0019210	kinase inhibitor activity	molecular_function	4.09	1.68E-02	2.04E-01	8.77E-01	57
GO:1902807	negative regulation of cell cycle G1/S phase transition	biological_process	4.09	1.68E-02	2.04E-01	8.77E-01	57
GO:0030145	manganese ion binding	molecular_function	4.09	1.68E-02	2.04E-01	8.77E-01	57
GO:0042625	ATPase-coupled ion transmembrane transporter activity	molecular_function	4.08	1.69E-02	2.04E-01	8.91E-01	46
GO:0010596	negative regulation of endothelial cell migration	biological_process	4.08	1.69E-02	2.04E-01	8.91E-01	46
GO:0090342	regulation of cell aging	biological_process	4.08	1.69E-02	2.04E-01	8.91E-01	46
GO:0050767	regulation of neurogenesis	biological_process	4.08	1.69E-02	2.04E-01	7.85E-01	814
GO:0042692	muscle cell differentiation	biological_process	4.06	1.73E-02	2.09E-01	8.45E-01	103
GO:0032984	protein-containing complex disassembly	biological_process	4.06	1.73E-02	2.09E-01	8.47E-01	98
GO:0042623	ATPase activity, coupled	N/A	4.05	1.74E-02	2.10E-01	8.10E-01	263
GO:0071900	regulation of protein serine/threonine kinase activity	biological_process	4.05	1.75E-02	2.11E-01	7.99E-01	398
GO:0044309	neuron spine	cellular_component	4.03	1.77E-02	2.14E-01	8.27E-01	156
GO:0019005	SCF ubiquitin ligase complex	cellular_component	4.03	1.78E-02	2.14E-01	8.71E-01	62
GO:0016020	membrane	cellular_component	4.03	1.79E-02	2.15E-01	7.63E-01	6211
GO:0033013	tetrapyrrole metabolic process	biological_process	4.02	1.80E-02	2.16E-01	9.00E-01	40
GO:0060828	regulation of canonical Wnt signaling pathway	biological_process	4.01	1.81E-02	2.18E-01	8.16E-01	212
GO:1903047	mitotic cell cycle process	biological_process	4.01	1.82E-02	2.18E-01	7.97E-01	433
GO:0016417	S-acyltransferase activity	molecular_function	4.00	1.82E-02	2.19E-01	9.29E-01	28
GO:0043015	gamma-tubulin binding	molecular_function	4.00	1.82E-02	2.19E-01	9.29E-01	28
GO:0071480	cellular response to gamma radiation	biological_process	4.00	1.82E-02	2.19E-01	9.29E-01	28
GO:1902653	secondary alcohol biosynthetic process	biological_process	4.00	1.82E-02	2.19E-01	9.29E-01	28
GO:0006378	mRNA polyadenylation	biological_process	4.00	1.82E-02	2.19E-01	9.29E-01	28
GO:0061003	positive regulation of dendritic spine morphogenesis	biological_process	4.00	1.82E-02	2.19E-01	9.29E-01	28
GO:0061462	protein localization to lysosome	biological_process	4.00	1.82E-02	2.19E-01	9.29E-01	28
GO:0048592	eye morphogenesis	biological_process	3.99	1.85E-02	2.21E-01	8.82E-01	51

GO:0033135	regulation of peptidyl-serine phosphorylation	biological_process	3.99	1.86E-02	2.21E-01	8.36E-01	122
GO:2000781	positive regulation of double-strand break repair	biological_process	3.99	1.86E-02	2.21E-01	9.12E-01	34
GO:0006778	porphyrin-containing compound metabolic process	biological_process	3.99	1.86E-02	2.21E-01	9.12E-01	34
GO:0008180	COP9 signalosome	cellular_component	3.99	1.86E-02	2.21E-01	9.12E-01	34
GO:0015030	Cajal body	cellular_component	3.99	1.86E-02	2.21E-01	9.12E-01	34
GO:0048568	embryonic organ development	biological_process	3.98	1.86E-02	2.21E-01	8.29E-01	146
GO:0015936	coenzyme A metabolic process	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0016441	posttranscriptional gene silencing	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0016442	RISC complex	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0042407	cristae formation	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0016881	acid-amino acid ligase activity	molecular_function	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0042776	mitochondrial ATP synthesis coupled proton transport	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0042800	histone methyltransferase activity (H3-K4 specific)	molecular_function	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0043024	ribosomal small subunit binding	molecular_function	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0043248	proteasome assembly	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0043555	regulation of translation in response to stress	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0045647	negative regulation of erythrocyte differentiation	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0071426	ribonucleoprotein complex export from nucleus	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0071428	rRNA-containing ribonucleoprotein complex export from nucleus	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:2000232	regulation of rRNA processing	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:1901836	regulation of transcription of nucleolar large rRNA by RNA polymerase I	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0098799	outer mitochondrial membrane protein complex	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0098847	sequence-specific single stranded DNA binding	molecular_function	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0000054	ribosomal subunit export from nucleus	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0000176	nuclear exosome (RNase complex)	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0000291	nuclear-transcribed mRNA catabolic process, exonucleolytic	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0000963	mitochondrial RNA processing	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0000974	Prp19 complex	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0051131	chaperone-mediated protein complex assembly	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0051645	Golgi localization	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:1904923	regulation of autophagy of mitochondrion in response to mitochondrial depolarization	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0002161	aminoacyl-tRNA editing activity	molecular_function	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0030127	COPII vesicle coat	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0030479	actin cortical patch	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0005161	platelet-derived growth factor receptor binding	molecular_function	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0031011	Ino80 complex	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0031083	BLOC-1 complex	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0031332	RNAi effector complex	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0006103	2-oxoglutarate metabolic process	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0006337	nucleosome disassembly	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0031937	positive regulation of chromatin silencing	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14

GO:0006862	nucleotide transport	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0006999	nuclear pore organization	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0033276	transcription factor TFTC complex	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0033750	ribosome localization	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0009226	nucleotide-sugar biosynthetic process	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0060211	regulation of nuclear-transcribed mRNA poly(A) tail shortening	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0060546	negative regulation of necroptotic process	biological_process	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0061645	endocytic patch	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:1990404	protein ADP-ribosylase activity	molecular_function	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0038201	TOR complex	cellular_component	3.96	1.90E-02	2.21E-01	1.00E+00	14
GO:0010675	regulation of cellular carbohydrate metabolic process	biological_process	3.96	1.91E-02	2.22E-01	8.30E-01	141
GO:0030833	regulation of actin filament polymerization	biological_process	3.96	1.91E-02	2.22E-01	8.25E-01	160
GO:0006468	protein phosphorylation	biological_process	3.95	1.92E-02	2.23E-01	7.88E-01	660
GO:0046982	protein heterodimerization activity	molecular_function	3.94	1.94E-02	2.25E-01	8.10E-01	248
GO:0110020	regulation of actomyosin structure organization	biological_process	3.93	1.96E-02	2.27E-01	8.43E-01	102
GO:0006275	regulation of DNA replication	biological_process	3.93	1.96E-02	2.27E-01	8.43E-01	102
GO:0035304	regulation of protein dephosphorylation	biological_process	3.93	1.96E-02	2.28E-01	8.54E-01	82
GO:0009743	response to carbohydrate	biological_process	3.93	1.97E-02	2.29E-01	8.51E-01	87
GO:0015399	primary active transmembrane transporter activity	molecular_function	3.92	1.98E-02	2.29E-01	8.48E-01	92
GO:0046605	regulation of centrosome cycle	biological_process	3.92	1.98E-02	2.29E-01	8.75E-01	56
GO:0001085	RNA polymerase II transcription factor binding	N/A	3.92	1.98E-02	2.29E-01	8.75E-01	56
GO:0006112	energy reserve metabolic process	biological_process	3.92	1.98E-02	2.29E-01	8.75E-01	56
GO:0016860	intramolecular oxidoreductase activity	molecular_function	3.90	2.02E-02	2.33E-01	8.89E-01	45
GO:0071560	cellular response to transforming growth factor beta stimulus	biological_process	3.90	2.02E-02	2.33E-01	8.89E-01	45
GO:1902893	regulation of pri-miRNA transcription by RNA polymerase II	biological_process	3.90	2.02E-02	2.33E-01	8.89E-01	45
GO:0003707	steroid hormone receptor activity	molecular_function	3.90	2.02E-02	2.33E-01	8.89E-01	45
GO:0009166	nucleotide catabolic process	biological_process	3.90	2.02E-02	2.33E-01	8.89E-01	45
GO:0015630	microtubule cytoskeleton	cellular_component	3.90	2.02E-02	2.33E-01	8.27E-01	150
GO:0016578	histone deubiquitination	biological_process	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0017025	TBP-class protein binding	molecular_function	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0043153	entrainment of circadian clock by photoperiod	biological_process	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:1900242	regulation of synaptic vesicle endocytosis	biological_process	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0046965	retinoid X receptor binding	molecular_function	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:1902410	mitotic cytokinetic process	biological_process	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0000313	organellar ribosome	cellular_component	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0000413	protein peptidyl-prolyl isomerization	biological_process	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0050750	low-density lipoprotein particle receptor binding	molecular_function	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0002097	tRNA wobble base modification	biological_process	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0030371	translation repressor activity	molecular_function	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0030904	retromer complex	cellular_component	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0005761	mitochondrial ribosome	cellular_component	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21

GO:0031306	intrinsic component of mitochondrial outer membrane	cellular_component	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0008171	O-methyltransferase activity	molecular_function	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0034593	phosphatidylinositol bisphosphate phosphatase activity	molecular_function	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0034620	cellular response to unfolded protein	biological_process	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0009648	photoperiodism	biological_process	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0035268	protein mannosylation	biological_process	3.88	2.06E-02	2.35E-01	9.52E-01	21
GO:0071479	cellular response to ionizing radiation	biological_process	3.87	2.08E-02	2.37E-01	8.69E-01	61
GO:0051058	negative regulation of small GTPase mediated signal transduction	biological_process	3.87	2.08E-02	2.37E-01	8.69E-01	61
GO:0036294	cellular response to decreased oxygen levels	biological_process	3.84	2.15E-02	2.45E-01	8.64E-01	66
GO:0010906	regulation of glucose metabolic process	biological_process	3.84	2.16E-02	2.46E-01	8.38E-01	111
GO:0016893	endonuclease activity, active with either ribo- or deoxyribonucleic acids and producing 5'-phosphomonoesters	molecular_function	3.83	2.17E-02	2.46E-01	8.97E-01	39
GO:0043044	ATP-dependent chromatin remodeling	N/A	3.83	2.17E-02	2.46E-01	8.97E-01	39
GO:2000279	negative regulation of DNA biosynthetic process	biological_process	3.83	2.17E-02	2.46E-01	8.97E-01	39
GO:1901505	carbohydrate derivative transmembrane transporter activity	molecular_function	3.83	2.17E-02	2.46E-01	8.97E-01	39
GO:0031057	negative regulation of histone modification	biological_process	3.83	2.17E-02	2.46E-01	8.97E-01	39
GO:0007098	centrosome cycle	biological_process	3.83	2.17E-02	2.46E-01	8.97E-01	39
GO:0005874	microtubule	cellular_component	3.83	2.18E-02	2.47E-01	7.98E-01	377
GO:1902808	positive regulation of cell cycle G1/S phase transition	biological_process	3.82	2.19E-02	2.49E-01	8.80E-01	50
GO:0006111	regulation of gluconeogenesis	biological_process	3.82	2.19E-02	2.49E-01	8.80E-01	50
GO:0032465	regulation of cytokinesis	biological_process	3.82	2.20E-02	2.49E-01	8.59E-01	71
GO:0022402	cell cycle process	biological_process	3.82	2.20E-02	2.49E-01	7.86E-01	718
GO:0120032	regulation of plasma membrane bounded cell projection assembly	biological_process	3.82	2.20E-02	2.49E-01	8.21E-01	168

Genes in list	Genes not in list	Genes in list, not in set	Genes not in list, not in set	Gene set	Description
8163	1432	3665	2437	GO:0043229	intracellular organelle
8275	1499	3553	2370	GO:0043226	organelle
7193	1135	4635	2734	GO:0043231	intracellular membrane-bounded organelle
7578	1275	4250	2594	GO:0043227	membrane-bounded organelle
4872	718	6956	3151	GO:0044237	cellular metabolic process
5368	867	6460	3002	GO:0008152	metabolic process
4970	823	6858	3046	GO:0071704	organic substance metabolic process
4696	758	7132	3111	GO:0044238	primary metabolic process
4394	694	7434	3175	GO:0005634	nucleus
4348	687	7480	3182	GO:0006807	nitrogen compound metabolic process
3876	584	7952	3285	GO:0043170	macromolecule metabolic process
10556	2888	1272	981	GO:0110165	cellular anatomical entity
2300	250	9528	3619	GO:0034641	cellular nitrogen compound metabolic process
3072	430	8756	3439	GO:0044260	cellular macromolecule metabolic process
8432	2083	3396	1786	GO:0009987	cellular process
2261	270	9567	3599	GO:0005654	nucleoplasm
1499	118	10329	3751	GO:0005739	mitochondrion
3927	689	7901	3180	GO:0032991	protein-containing complex
1840	189	9988	3680	GO:0006139	nucleobase-containing compound metabolic process
1931	212	9897	3657	GO:0046483	heterocycle metabolic process
4832	959	6996	2910	GO:0005737	cytoplasm
8409	2133	3419	1736	GO:0005488	binding
1087	61	10741	3808	GO:0016070	RNA metabolic process
3686	648	8142	3221	GO:1901363	heterocyclic compound binding
1960	229	9868	3640	GO:0006725	cellular aromatic compound metabolic process
2535	360	9293	3509	GO:0005829	cytosol
3732	665	8096	3204	GO:0097159	organic cyclic compound binding
1511	138	10317	3731	GO:0090304	nucleic acid metabolic process
4071	776	7757	3093	GO:0003824	catalytic activity
2076	269	9752	3600	GO:1901360	organic cyclic compound metabolic process
2337	339	9491	3530	GO:0003676	nucleic acid binding
2071	282	9757	3587	GO:0044267	cellular protein metabolic process
3136	560	8692	3309	GO:1901564	organonitrogen compound metabolic process
1169	102	10659	3767	GO:1902494	catalytic complex
943	64	10885	3805	GO:0003723	RNA binding
2536	421	9292	3448	GO:0019538	protein metabolic process
679	29	11149	3840	GO:0006396	RNA processing
4120	857	7708	3012	GO:0019222	regulation of metabolic process
3858	796	7970	3073	GO:0031323	regulation of cellular metabolic process
1906	284	9922	3585	GO:0043412	macromolecule modification
3702	762	8126	3107	GO:0080090	regulation of primary metabolic process
3596	739	8232	3130	GO:0051171	regulation of nitrogen compound metabolic process

3767	788	8061	3081 GO:0060255	regulation of macromolecule metabolic process
991	95	10837	3774 GO:0046907	intracellular transport
2379	415	9449	3454 GO:0043228	non-membrane-bounded organelle
2360	412	9468	3457 GO:0043232	intracellular non-membrane-bounded organelle
631	34	11197	3835 GO:1990904	ribonucleoprotein complex
1868	294	9960	3575 GO:0019899	enzyme binding
1529	218	10299	3651 GO:0009058	biosynthetic process
916	88	10912	3781 GO:0044271	cellular nitrogen compound biosynthetic process
2678	507	9150	3362 GO:0010468	regulation of gene expression
1760	275	10068	3594 GO:0006464	cellular protein modification process
1760	275	10068	3594 GO:0036211	protein modification process
1393	193	10435	3676 GO:0044249	cellular biosynthetic process
1465	211	10363	3658 GO:1901576	organic substance biosynthetic process
1095	130	10733	3739 GO:0044248	cellular catabolic process
666	48	11162	3821 GO:1990234	transferase complex
586	36	11242	3833 GO:0044265	cellular macromolecule catabolic process
1253	167	10575	3702 GO:0009056	catabolic process
2566	493	9262	3376 GO:0009889	regulation of biosynthetic process
2419	454	9409	3415 GO:0010556	regulation of macromolecule biosynthetic process
1370	195	10458	3674 GO:0031090	organelle membrane regulation of cellular macromolecule biosynthetic process
2355	439	9473	3430 GO:2000112	process
1506	227	10322	3642 GO:0051641	cellular localization
672	52	11156	3817 GO:0009057	macromolecule catabolic process
2514	484	9314	3385 GO:0031326	regulation of cellular biosynthetic process
3432	742	8396	3127 GO:0071840	cellular component organization or biogenesis regulation of nucleobase-containing compound
2391	457	9437	3412 GO:0019219	metabolic process
470	23	11358	3846 GO:0016071	mRNA metabolic process
325	5	11503	3864 GO:0034470	ncRNA processing
1014	125	10814	3744 GO:0015833	peptide transport
797	81	11031	3788 GO:0009059	macromolecule biosynthetic process
997	122	10831	3747 GO:0015031	protein transport
382	12	11446	3857 GO:0034660	ncRNA metabolic process
632	51	11196	3818 GO:0005730	nucleolus
1030	130	10798	3739 GO:0042886	amide transport
6022	1546	5806	2323 GO:0005515	protein binding
1064	138	10764	3731 GO:1901575	organic substance catabolic process
1059	137	10769	3732 GO:0045184	establishment of protein localization
1481	236	10347	3633 GO:0033036	macromolecule localization
2200	419	9628	3450 GO:0051252	regulation of RNA metabolic process
1218	175	10610	3694 GO:0071705	nitrogen compound transport
3351	742	8477	3127 GO:0016043	cellular component organization
3841	885	7987	2984 GO:0043167	ion binding
1731	302	10097	3567 GO:0016740	transferase activity
1462	236	10366	3633 GO:0008104	protein localization

716	73	11112	3796 GO:0034645	cellular macromolecule biosynthetic process
1132	163	10696	3706 GO:0033554	cellular response to stress
718	77	11110	3792 GO:0009894	regulation of catabolic process
1971	378	9857	3491 GO:0009892	negative regulation of metabolic process
500	38	11328	3831 GO:0031966	mitochondrial membrane
2516	527	9312	3342 GO:0009893	positive regulation of metabolic process
266	5	11562	3864 GO:0006412	translation
308	10	11520	3859 GO:0140098	catalytic activity, acting on RNA
1998	390	9830	3479 GO:2001141	regulation of RNA biosynthetic process
255	4	11573	3865 GO:0098798	mitochondrial protein complex
1996	390	9832	3479 GO:1903506	regulation of nucleic acid-templated transcription
389	22	11439	3847 GO:0019866	organelle inner membrane
1988	390	9840	3479 GO:0006355	regulation of transcription, DNA-templated
1764	332	10064	3537 GO:0031324	negative regulation of cellular metabolic process
363	19	11465	3850 GO:0005743	mitochondrial inner membrane
595	60	11233	3809 GO:0016604	nuclear body
600	61	11228	3808 GO:0031329	regulation of cellular catabolic process
372	21	11456	3848 GO:0006518	peptide metabolic process
467	37	11361	3832 GO:0051603	proteolysis involved in cellular protein catabolic process
2310	484	9518	3385 GO:0031325	positive regulation of cellular metabolic process
1376	239	10452	3630 GO:0071702	organic substance transport
1774	341	10054	3528 GO:0010605	negative regulation of macromolecule metabolic process
1635	305	10193	3564 GO:0006996	organelle organization
1623	302	10205	3567 GO:0051172	negative regulation of nitrogen compound metabolic process
2298	484	9530	3385 GO:0010604	positive regulation of macromolecule metabolic process
355	20	11473	3849 GO:0006397	mRNA processing
276	9	11552	3860 GO:0043043	peptide biosynthetic process
500	45	11328	3824 GO:0070647	protein modification by small protein conjugation or removal
421	31	11407	3838 GO:0043632	modification-dependent macromolecule catabolic process
606	66	11222	3803 GO:0006886	intracellular protein transport
1967	398	9861	3471 GO:0051716	cellular response to stimulus
412	31	11416	3838 GO:0019941	modification-dependent protein catabolic process
2177	459	9651	3410 GO:0051173	positive regulation of nitrogen compound metabolic process
528	53	11300	3816 GO:0043603	cellular amide metabolic process
346	21	11482	3848 GO:0043604	amide biosynthetic process
592	66	11236	3803 GO:0018130	heterocycle biosynthetic process
6204	1687	5624	2182 GO:0050794	regulation of cellular process
401	31	11427	3838 GO:0006511	ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process
798	112	11030	3757 GO:0016192	vesicle-mediated transport

453	41	11375	3828 GO:0051020	GTPase binding
1944	402	9884	3467 GO:0051246	regulation of protein metabolic process
540	58	11288	3811 GO:0034654	nucleobase-containing compound biosynthetic process
1557	300	10271	3569 GO:1901265	nucleoside phosphate binding
1557	300	10271	3569 GO:0000166	nucleotide binding
1435	272	10393	3597 GO:0003677	DNA binding
194	3	11634	3866 GO:0016072	rRNA metabolic process
3206	768	8622	3101 GO:0048523	negative regulation of cellular process
3533	866	8295	3003 GO:0048519	negative regulation of biological process
1805	374	10023	3495 GO:0032268	regulation of cellular protein metabolic process
360	28	11468	3841 GO:0010608	posttranscriptional regulation of gene expression
187	3	11641	3866 GO:0006364	rRNA processing
279	15	11549	3854 GO:0008380	RNA splicing
220	7	11608	3862 GO:0048193	Golgi vesicle transport
1388	265	10440	3604 GO:0006357	regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II
1106	194	10722	3675 GO:0009890	negative regulation of biosynthetic process
586	74	11242	3795 GO:0019438	aromatic compound biosynthetic process
1897	404	9931	3465 GO:0051128	regulation of cellular component organization
395	36	11433	3833 GO:0003712	transcription coregulator activity
1561	314	10267	3555 GO:0140096	catalytic activity, acting on a protein
1038	180	10790	3689 GO:0010558	negative regulation of macromolecule biosynthetic process
985	167	10843	3702 GO:0005794	Golgi apparatus
1073	190	10755	3679 GO:0031327	negative regulation of cellular biosynthetic process
1196	221	10632	3648 GO:0010629	negative regulation of gene expression
183	4	11645	3865 GO:0005681	spliceosomal complex
1292	247	10536	3622 GO:0045935	positive regulation of nucleobase-containing compound metabolic process
2429	560	9399	3309 GO:0046872	metal ion binding
161	2	11667	3867 GO:0006399	tRNA metabolic process
1011	177	10817	3692 GO:2000113	negative regulation of cellular macromolecule biosynthetic process
136	0	11692	3869 GO:0044085	cellular component biogenesis
368	34	11460	3835 GO:0031267	small GTPase binding
1151	214	10677	3655 GO:0005783	endoplasmic reticulum
3613	913	8215	2956 GO:0048522	positive regulation of cellular process
1011	179	10817	3690 GO:0033043	regulation of organelle organization
1032	185	10796	3684 GO:0044281	small molecule metabolic process
1767	379	10061	3490 GO:0036094	small molecule binding
651	94	11177	3775 GO:1901362	organic cyclic compound biosynthetic process
266	17	11562	3852 GO:0031625	ubiquitin protein ligase binding
1416	285	10412	3584 GO:0022607	cellular component assembly
399	41	11429	3828 GO:0032446	protein modification by small protein conjugation
571	77	11257	3792 GO:0008134	transcription factor binding
1400	282	10428	3587 GO:0010628	positive regulation of gene expression

2470	580	9358	3289 GO:0043169	cation binding
282	21	11546	3848 GO:0016607	nuclear speck
332	30	11496	3839 GO:0034248	regulation of cellular amide metabolic process
2724	658	9104	3211 GO:0051179	localization
1680	361	10148	3508 GO:0016787	hydrolase activity
637	94	11191	3775 GO:1901566	organonitrogen compound biosynthetic process
1312	262	10516	3607 GO:0035639	purine ribonucleoside triphosphate binding
124	0	11704	3869 GO:0022613	ribonucleoprotein complex biogenesis
1368	277	10460	3592 GO:0017076	purine nucleotide binding
773	126	11055	3743 GO:0070727	cellular macromolecule localization
352	34	11476	3835 GO:0017016	Ras GTPase binding
291	23	11537	3846 GO:0006417	regulation of translation
1368	278	10460	3591 GO:0032553	ribonucleotide binding
646	97	11182	3772 GO:0005768	endosome
565	79	11263	3790 GO:0055114	oxidation-reduction process
1161	225	10667	3644 GO:0051254	positive regulation of RNA metabolic process
331	31	11497	3838 GO:0030163	protein catabolic process
765	126	11063	3743 GO:0034613	cellular protein localization
132	1	11696	3868 GO:0006401	RNA catabolic process
1086	206	10742	3663 GO:0044877	protein-containing complex binding
372	39	11456	3830 GO:0009896	positive regulation of catabolic process
1356	277	10472	3592 GO:0032555	purine ribonucleotide binding
361	37	11467	3832 GO:0016567	protein ubiquitination
1010	187	10818	3682 GO:0045934	negative regulation of nucleobase-containing compound metabolic process
1291	260	10537	3609 GO:0010557	positive regulation of macromolecule biosynthetic process
6876	1970	4952	1899 GO:0065007	biological regulation
6543	1860	5285	2009 GO:0050789	regulation of biological process
278	22	11550	3847 GO:0044389	ubiquitin-like protein ligase binding
247	17	11581	3852 GO:0031647	regulation of protein stability
4013	1055	7815	2814 GO:0048518	positive regulation of biological process
470	61	11358	3808 GO:0033365	protein localization to organelle
294	26	11534	3843 GO:0032774	RNA biosynthetic process
1377	287	10451	3582 GO:0009891	positive regulation of biosynthetic process
184	8	11644	3861 GO:0005840	ribosome
315	30	11513	3839 GO:0031331	positive regulation of cellular catabolic process
1948	446	9880	3423 GO:0043168	anion binding
264	21	11564	3848 GO:0043233	organelle lumen
264	21	11564	3848 GO:0070013	intracellular organelle lumen
264	21	11564	3848 GO:0031974	membrane-enclosed lumen
930	171	10898	3698 GO:0051253	negative regulation of RNA metabolic process
1350	281	10478	3588 GO:0031328	positive regulation of cellular biosynthetic process
560	82	11268	3787 GO:0006974	cellular response to DNA damage stimulus
378	43	11450	3826 GO:0008047	enzyme activator activity
284	25	11544	3844 GO:0016569	covalent chromatin modification

187	9	11641	3860 GO:0044391	ribosomal subunit
775	134	11053	3735 GO:0051248	negative regulation of protein metabolic process
148	4	11680	3865 GO:0000375	RNA splicing, via transesterification reactions
139	3	11689	3866 GO:0043021	ribonucleoprotein complex binding
264	22	11564	3847 GO:0010498	proteasomal protein catabolic process
				RNA splicing, via transesterification reactions with bulged
147	4	11681	3865 GO:0000377	adenosine as nucleophile
147	4	11681	3865 GO:0000398	mRNA splicing, via spliceosome
202	12	11626	3857 GO:0034655	nucleobase-containing compound catabolic process
1237	255	10591	3614 GO:0006793	phosphorus metabolic process
1085	215	10743	3654 GO:1902680	positive regulation of RNA biosynthetic process
277	25	11551	3844 GO:0016570	histone modification
				positive regulation of nucleic acid-templated
1084	215	10744	3654 GO:1903508	transcription
1081	215	10747	3654 GO:0045893	positive regulation of transcription, DNA-templated
1219	252	10609	3617 GO:0006796	phosphate-containing compound metabolic process
464	64	11364	3805 GO:1903827	regulation of cellular protein localization
				proteasome-mediated ubiquitin-dependent protein
246	20	11582	3849 GO:0043161	catabolic process
113	1	11715	3868 GO:0140101	catalytic activity, acting on a tRNA
500	73	11328	3796 GO:0006325	chromatin organization
332	37	11496	3832 GO:0042176	regulation of protein catabolic process
2231	539	9597	3330 GO:0006810	transport
1115	227	10713	3642 GO:0030554	adenyl nucleotide binding
212	15	11616	3854 GO:0018205	peptidyl-lysine modification
98	0	11730	3869 GO:0042254	ribosome biogenesis
723	127	11105	3742 GO:0032269	negative regulation of cellular protein metabolic process
109	1	11719	3868 GO:0006402	mRNA catabolic process
221	17	11607	3852 GO:1903362	regulation of cellular protein catabolic process
243	21	11585	3848 GO:0072594	establishment of protein localization to organelle
751	135	11077	3734 GO:0006508	proteolysis
461	66	11367	3803 GO:0003682	chromatin binding
177	10	11651	3859 GO:0016197	endosomal transport
860	163	10968	3706 GO:0043933	protein-containing complex subunit organization
852	161	10976	3708 GO:1902679	negative regulation of RNA biosynthetic process
				negative regulation of nucleic acid-templated
852	161	10976	3708 GO:1903507	transcription
125	3	11703	3866 GO:0009451	RNA modification
1104	227	10724	3642 GO:0032559	adenyl ribonucleotide binding
507	77	11321	3792 GO:1901565	organonitrogen compound catabolic process
1062	216	10766	3653 GO:0005524	ATP binding
549	87	11279	3782 GO:0019637	organophosphate metabolic process
484	72	11344	3797 GO:0010638	positive regulation of organelle organization
161	8	11667	3861 GO:0015931	nucleobase-containing compound transport
154	7	11674	3862 GO:0022618	ribonucleoprotein complex assembly

848	161	10980	3708 GO:0045892	negative regulation of transcription, DNA-templated
955	189	10873	3680 GO:0140110	transcription regulator activity
1548	350	10280	3519 GO:0097367	carbohydrate derivative binding
160	8	11668	3861 GO:0071826	ribonucleoprotein complex subunit organization
2324	573	9504	3296 GO:0051234	establishment of localization
122	3	11706	3866 GO:0098800	inner mitochondrial membrane protein complex
112	2	11716	3867 GO:0008033	tRNA processing
151	7	11677	3862 GO:0003735	structural constituent of ribosome
337	41	11491	3828 GO:0019787	ubiquitin-like protein transferase activity
534	85	11294	3784 GO:1901698	response to nitrogen compound
694	124	11134	3745 GO:0030234	enzyme regulator activity
157	8	11671	3861 GO:0050821	protein stabilization
321	38	11507	3831 GO:0004842	ubiquitin-protein transferase activity
510	80	11318	3789 GO:0034622	cellular protein-containing complex assembly
249	24	11579	3845 GO:0000151	ubiquitin ligase complex
254	25	11574	3844 GO:0007005	mitochondrion organization
259	26	11569	3843 GO:0060589	nucleoside-triphosphatase regulator activity
221	19	11607	3850 GO:0003713	transcription coactivator activity
307	36	11521	3833 GO:0140297	DNA-binding transcription factor binding
108	2	11720	3867 GO:0007033	vacuole organization
87	0	11741	3869 GO:0000956	nuclear-transcribed mRNA catabolic process
256	26	11572	3843 GO:0006979	response to oxidative stress
537	88	11291	3781 GO:0016788	hydrolase activity, acting on ester bonds
97	1	11731	3868 GO:0006888	endoplasmic reticulum to Golgi vesicle-mediated transport
648	116	11180	3753 GO:0060341	regulation of cellular localization
1199	261	10629	3608 GO:0051247	positive regulation of protein metabolic process
104	2	11724	3867 GO:0016241	regulation of macroautophagy
135	6	11693	3863 GO:0051236	establishment of RNA localization
135	6	11693	3863 GO:0008757	S-adenosylmethionine-dependent methyltransferase activity
1202	263	10626	3606 GO:0097708	intracellular vesicle
133	6	11695	3863 GO:0050657	nucleic acid transport
133	6	11695	3863 GO:0050658	RNA transport
1199	263	10629	3606 GO:0031410	cytoplasmic vesicle
497	81	11331	3788 GO:0098805	whole membrane
751	144	11077	3725 GO:0065003	protein-containing complex assembly
1190	261	10638	3608 GO:0008144	drug binding
176	13	11652	3856 GO:0008168	methyltransferase activity
635	115	11193	3754 GO:0000122	negative regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II
368	52	11460	3817 GO:0000785	chromatin
224	22	11604	3847 GO:0003729	mRNA binding
79	0	11749	3869 GO:0033108	mitochondrial respiratory chain complex assembly
1275	286	10553	3583 GO:0031982	vesicle
239	25	11589	3844 GO:0006351	transcription, DNA-templated

				regulation of proteolysis involved in cellular protein
191	16	11637	3853 GO:1903050	catabolic process
222	22	11606	3847 GO:0010506	regulation of autophagy
184	15	11644	3854 GO:0016741	transferase activity, transferring one-carbon groups
231	24	11597	3845 GO:0032259	methylation
509	86	11319	3783 GO:1901135	carbohydrate derivative metabolic process
1112	243	10716	3626 GO:0032270	positive regulation of cellular protein metabolic process
120	5	11708	3864 GO:0005759	mitochondrial matrix
492	82	11336	3787 GO:0010243	response to organonitrogen compound
1435	333	10393	3536 GO:0042802	identical protein binding
454	73	11374	3796 GO:0031400	negative regulation of protein modification process
76	0	11752	3869 GO:0030684	preribosome
				transferase complex, transferring phosphorus-containing
176	14	11652	3855 GO:0061695	groups
170	13	11658	3856 GO:0042393	histone binding
548	96	11280	3773 GO:0080135	regulation of cellular response to stress
229	24	11599	3845 GO:0046700	heterocycle catabolic process
259	30	11569	3839 GO:0031301	integral component of organelle membrane
239	26	11589	3843 GO:0097659	nucleic acid-templated transcription
501	85	11327	3784 GO:0006259	DNA metabolic process
118	5	11710	3864 GO:0007034	vacuolar transport
395	60	11433	3809 GO:0005622	intracellular
566	101	11262	3768 GO:0008219	cell death
305	40	11523	3829 GO:1901699	cellular response to nitrogen compound
85	1	11743	3868 GO:0005684	U2-type spliceosomal complex
536	94	11292	3775 GO:0012501	programmed cell death
640	120	11188	3749 GO:0098588	bounding membrane of organelle
1212	273	10616	3596 GO:0010941	regulation of cell death
167	13	11661	3856 GO:0061136	regulation of proteasomal protein catabolic process
371	55	11457	3814 GO:0005773	vacuole
362	53	11466	3816 GO:0006281	DNA repair
161	12	11667	3857 GO:0000209	protein polyubiquitination
225	24	11603	3845 GO:0044270	cellular nitrogen compound catabolic process
142	9	11686	3860 GO:0043543	protein acylation
148	10	11680	3859 GO:0044403	symbiotic process
115	5	11713	3864 GO:0045182	translation regulator activity
1106	245	10722	3624 GO:0005856	cytoskeleton
233	26	11595	3843 GO:0019439	aromatic compound catabolic process
646	123	11182	3746 GO:0019900	kinase binding
114	5	11714	3864 GO:0010508	positive regulation of autophagy
186	17	11642	3852 GO:0043414	macromolecule methylation
71	0	11757	3869 GO:0019843	rRNA binding
1279	294	10549	3575 GO:0031399	regulation of protein modification process
934	199	10894	3670 GO:0051130	positive regulation of cellular component organization

285	37	11543	3832 GO:0031300	intrinsic component of organelle membrane
106	4	11722	3865 GO:0016032	viral process
211	22	11617	3847 GO:0006091	generation of precursor metabolites and energy
168	14	11660	3855 GO:0044798	nuclear transcription factor complex
841	175	10987	3694 GO:0045944	positive regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II
105	4	11723	3865 GO:0070646	protein modification by small protein removal
1667	406	10161	3463 GO:0042221	response to chemical
144	10	11684	3859 GO:0006605	protein targeting
757	153	11071	3716 GO:0051726	regulation of cell cycle
1152	260	10676	3609 GO:0070887	cellular response to chemical stimulus
89	2	11739	3867 GO:1902493	acetyltransferase complex
89	2	11739	3867 GO:0031248	protein acetyltransferase complex
505	89	11323	3780 GO:0006915	apoptotic process
739	149	11089	3720 GO:0044087	regulation of cellular component biogenesis
208	22	11620	3847 GO:1903311	regulation of mRNA metabolic process
579	108	11249	3761 GO:0019901	protein kinase binding
559	103	11269	3766 GO:0018193	peptidyl-amino acid modification
176	16	11652	3853 GO:0006914	autophagy
176	16	11652	3853 GO:0035770	ribonucleoprotein granule
176	16	11652	3853 GO:0061919	process utilizing autophagic mechanism
237	28	11591	3841 GO:0061629	RNA polymerase II-specific DNA-binding transcription factor binding
109	5	11719	3864 GO:0032868	response to insulin
109	5	11719	3864 GO:0034708	methyltransferase complex
278	37	11550	3832 GO:0051186	cofactor metabolic process
128	8	11700	3861 GO:0140030	modification-dependent protein binding
711	143	11117	3726 GO:0016772	transferase activity, transferring phosphorus-containing groups
295	41	11533	3828 GO:0090407	organophosphate biosynthetic process
335	50	11493	3819 GO:2001233	regulation of apoptotic signaling pathway
308	44	11520	3825 GO:0033044	regulation of chromosome organization
85	2	11743	3867 GO:1905368	peptidase complex
1360	322	10468	3547 GO:0010033	response to organic substance
139	10	11689	3859 GO:2000058	regulation of ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process
76	1	11752	3868 GO:0015935	small ribosomal subunit
604	116	11224	3753 GO:0019904	protein domain specific binding
120	7	11708	3862 GO:0016482	cytosolic transport
177	17	11651	3852 GO:0005085	guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity
92	3	11736	3866 GO:0018394	peptidyl-lysine acetylation
92	3	11736	3866 GO:0019783	ubiquitin-like protein-specific protease activity
92	3	11736	3866 GO:0006475	internal protein amino acid acetylation
1100	250	10728	3619 GO:0043067	regulation of programmed cell death
143	11	11685	3858 GO:0017137	Rab GTPase binding
64	0	11764	3869 GO:0070469	respirasome

175	17	11653	3852 GO:0034976	response to endoplasmic reticulum stress regulation of proteasomal ubiquitin-dependent protein
118	7	11710	3862 GO:0032434	catabolic process
220	26	11608	3843 GO:0030695	GTPase regulator activity
205	23	11623	3846 GO:0005096	GTPase activator activity
200	22	11628	3847 GO:0035091	phosphatidylinositol binding
63	0	11765	3869 GO:0001510	RNA methylation
90	3	11738	3866 GO:0090079	translation regulator activity, nucleic acid binding
158	14	11670	3855 GO:0043209	myelin sheath
97	4	11731	3865 GO:0051028	mRNA transport regulation of protein modification by small protein
204	23	11624	3846 GO:1903320	conjugation or removal
89	3	11739	3866 GO:0018393	internal peptidyl-lysine acetylation
188	20	11640	3849 GO:0016050	vesicle organization
936	207	10892	3662 GO:0071310	cellular response to organic substance
109	6	11719	3863 GO:0006473	protein acetylation
330	51	11498	3818 GO:0055086	nucleobase-containing small molecule metabolic process
61	0	11767	3869 GO:0043022	ribosome binding
764	161	11064	3708 GO:0040012	regulation of locomotion
127	9	11701	3860 GO:0010821	regulation of mitochondrion organization
71	1	11757	3868 GO:0006400	tRNA modification
108	6	11720	3863 GO:0019318	hexose metabolic process
421	73	11407	3796 GO:0005813	centrosome
138	11	11690	3858 GO:1901653	cellular response to peptide
165	16	11663	3853 GO:2001252	positive regulation of chromosome organization
165	16	11663	3853 GO:0036464	cytoplasmic ribonucleoprotein granule
101	5	11727	3864 GO:1990204	oxidoreductase complex
79	2	11749	3867 GO:0000123	histone acetyltransferase complex
170	17	11658	3852 GO:0051169	nuclear transport
170	17	11658	3852 GO:0006913	nucleocytoplasmic transport
366	60	11462	3809 GO:0048037	cofactor binding
60	0	11768	3869 GO:0008173	RNA methyltransferase activity
131	10	11697	3859 GO:0034250	positive regulation of cellular amide metabolic process
519	98	11309	3771 GO:0016491	oxidoreductase activity
352	57	11476	3812 GO:0043254	regulation of protein-containing complex assembly
251	34	11577	3835 GO:1901137	carbohydrate derivative biosynthetic process
78	2	11750	3867 GO:0071013	catalytic step 2 spliceosome
78	2	11750	3867 GO:0008080	N-acetyltransferase activity
189	21	11639	3848 GO:0045732	positive regulation of protein catabolic process
203	24	11625	3845 GO:0006790	sulfur compound metabolic process
1070	247	10758	3622 GO:0044093	positive regulation of molecular function
85	3	11743	3866 GO:0016573	histone acetylation
1744	441	10084	3428 GO:0065009	regulation of molecular function
272	39	11556	3830 GO:0071417	cellular response to organonitrogen compound

1848	472	9980	3397 GO:0006950	response to stress
207	25	11621	3844 GO:0061659	ubiquitin-like protein ligase activity
249	34	11579	3835 GO:0009895	negative regulation of catabolic process
216	27	11612	3842 GO:0019693	ribose phosphate metabolic process
68	1	11760	3868 GO:0034212	peptide N-acetyltransferase activity
111	7	11717	3862 GO:0006839	mitochondrial transport
98	5	11730	3864 GO:0071375	cellular response to peptide hormone stimulus
1296	312	10532	3557 GO:0050790	regulation of catalytic activity
134	11	11694	3858 GO:0042594	response to starvation
76	2	11752	3867 GO:0098803	respiratory chain complex
76	2	11752	3867 GO:0032869	cellular response to insulin stimulus
128	10	11700	3859 GO:0006457	protein folding
1076	250	10752	3619 GO:0042981	regulation of apoptotic process
283	42	11545	3827 GO:0032386	regulation of intracellular transport
322	51	11506	3818 GO:0000323	lytic vacuole
322	51	11506	3818 GO:0005764	lysosome
116	8	11712	3861 GO:0015934	large ribosomal subunit
83	3	11745	3866 GO:0101005	ubiquitinyl hydrolase activity
83	3	11745	3866 GO:0007041	lysosomal transport
90	4	11738	3865 GO:0016579	protein deubiquitination
109	7	11719	3862 GO:0045727	positive regulation of translation
199	24	11629	3845 GO:0061630	ubiquitin protein ligase activity
194	23	11634	3846 GO:0008022	protein C-terminus binding
143	13	11685	3856 GO:0030027	lamellipodium
557	110	11271	3759 GO:0043436	oxoacid metabolic process
82	3	11746	3866 GO:0036459	thiol-dependent ubiquitinyl hydrolase activity
74	2	11754	3867 GO:1905897	regulation of response to endoplasmic reticulum stress
74	2	11754	3867 GO:0008135	translation factor activity, RNA binding
125	10	11703	3859 GO:1903364	positive regulation of cellular protein catabolic process
136	12	11692	3857 GO:0090575	RNA polymerase II transcription factor complex
192	23	11636	3846 GO:0005769	early endosome
113	8	11715	3861 GO:0005777	peroxisome
130	11	11698	3858 GO:0035257	nuclear hormone receptor binding
94	5	11734	3864 GO:0090305	nucleic acid phosphodiester bond hydrolysis
124	10	11704	3859 GO:0016874	ligase activity
64	1	11764	3868 GO:0016239	positive regulation of macroautophagy
54	0	11774	3869 GO:0006352	DNA-templated transcription, initiation
106	7	11722	3862 GO:1903828	negative regulation of cellular protein localization
204	26	11624	3843 GO:0031330	negative regulation of cellular catabolic process
227	31	11601	3838 GO:0050662	coenzyme binding
531	105	11297	3764 GO:0019752	carboxylic acid metabolic process
405	73	11423	3796 GO:0022604	regulation of cell morphogenesis
139	13	11689	3856 GO:0005770	late endosome

565	114	11263	3755 GO:0051129	negative regulation of cellular component organization
530	105	11298	3764 GO:1901701	cellular response to oxygen-containing compound
487	94	11341	3775 GO:0005815	microtubule organizing center
122	10	11706	3859 GO:0017038	protein import
279	43	11549	3826 GO:0006753	nucleoside phosphate metabolic process
300	48	11528	3821 GO:1902903	regulation of supramolecular fiber organization
1914	499	9914	3370 GO:0009966	regulation of signal transduction
567	115	11261	3754 GO:0006082	organic acid metabolic process
127	11	11701	3858 GO:0006366	transcription by RNA polymerase II
713	154	11115	3715 GO:2000145	regulation of cell motility
211	28	11617	3841 GO:0006163	purine nucleotide metabolic process
132	12	11696	3857 GO:0008234	cysteine-type peptidase activity
158	17	11670	3852 GO:0004518	nuclease activity
52	0	11776	3869 GO:0006413	translational initiation
206	27	11622	3842 GO:0009259	ribonucleotide metabolic process
685	147	11143	3722 GO:0030334	regulation of cell migration
787	175	11041	3694 GO:0032880	regulation of protein localization
61	1	11767	3868 GO:0099023	vesicle tethering complex
61	1	11767	3868 GO:1905037	autophagosome organization
69	2	11759	3867 GO:0120114	Sm-like protein family complex
284	45	11544	3824 GO:0005667	transcription factor complex
96	6	11732	3863 GO:0016407	acetyltransferase activity
102	7	11726	3862 GO:0007030	Golgi organization
671	144	11157	3725 GO:0046983	protein dimerization activity
611	128	11217	3741 GO:0016817	hydrolase activity, acting on acid anhydrides
				hydrolase activity, acting on acid anhydrides, in
611	128	11217	3741 GO:0016818	phosphorus-containing anhydrides
481	94	11347	3775 GO:0030162	regulation of proteolysis
175	21	11653	3848 GO:1902275	regulation of chromatin organization
60	1	11768	3868 GO:0000049	tRNA binding
60	1	11768	3868 GO:1905369	endopeptidase complex
60	1	11768	3868 GO:0061733	peptide-lysine-N-acetyltransferase activity
809	182	11019	3687 GO:0043085	positive regulation of catalytic activity
89	5	11739	3864 GO:0032006	regulation of TOR signaling
107	8	11721	3861 GO:0046390	ribose phosphate biosynthetic process
484	95	11344	3774 GO:0048471	perinuclear region of cytoplasm
50	0	11778	3869 GO:0071011	precatalytic spliceosome
401	74	11427	3795 GO:1902532	negative regulation of intracellular signal transduction
609	128	11219	3741 GO:0016462	pyrophosphatase activity
118	10	11710	3859 GO:0042579	microbody
174	21	11654	3848 GO:0031396	regulation of protein ubiquitination
88	5	11740	3864 GO:0007006	mitochondrial membrane organization
59	1	11769	3868 GO:0000315	organellar large ribosomal subunit
59	1	11769	3868 GO:0000502	proteasome complex

59	1	11769	3868 GO:0030532	small nuclear ribonucleoprotein complex
59	1	11769	3868 GO:0005762	mitochondrial large ribosomal subunit
246	37	11582	3832 GO:1901361	organic cyclic compound catabolic process
187	24	11641	3845 GO:0033157	regulation of intracellular protein transport
49	0	11779	3869 GO:0045271	respiratory chain complex I
49	0	11779	3869 GO:0030964	NADH dehydrogenase complex
49	0	11779	3869 GO:0005747	mitochondrial respiratory chain complex I
163	19	11665	3850 GO:0051099	positive regulation of binding
74	3	11754	3866 GO:0004843	thiol-dependent ubiquitin-specific protease activity
557	115	11271	3754 GO:0044255	cellular lipid metabolic process
271	43	11557	3826 GO:0009117	nucleotide metabolic process
753	168	11075	3701 GO:0043565	sequence-specific DNA binding
87	5	11741	3864 GO:0032182	ubiquitin-like protein binding
58	1	11770	3868 GO:0004402	histone acetyltransferase activity
137	14	11691	3855 GO:0051188	cofactor biosynthetic process
1132	275	10696	3594 GO:1902531	regulation of intracellular signal transduction
142	15	11686	3854 GO:0017048	Rho GTPase binding
393	73	11435	3796 GO:0005198	structural molecule activity
126	12	11702	3857 GO:0005774	vacuolar membrane
115	10	11713	3859 GO:0009267	cellular response to starvation
65	2	11763	3867 GO:0006405	RNA export from nucleus
72	3	11756	3866 GO:0004527	exonuclease activity
484	97	11344	3772 GO:0042803	protein homodimerization activity
47	0	11781	3869 GO:0071005	U2-type precatalytic spliceosome
155	18	11673	3851 GO:0003714	transcription corepressor activity
641	139	11187	3730 GO:0001067	regulatory region nucleic acid binding
228	34	11600	3835 GO:0031667	response to nutrient levels
56	1	11772	3868 GO:0000045	autophagosome assembly
56	1	11772	3868 GO:0001098	basal transcription machinery binding
56	1	11772	3868 GO:0001099	basal RNA polymerase II transcription machinery binding
478	96	11350	3773 GO:0008270	zinc ion binding
71	3	11757	3866 GO:0003727	single-stranded RNA binding
196	27	11632	3842 GO:0009150	purine ribonucleotide metabolic process
84	5	11744	3864 GO:0035097	histone methyltransferase complex
635	138	11193	3731 GO:0046914	transition metal ion binding
46	0	11782	3869 GO:0032981	mitochondrial respiratory chain complex I assembly
46	0	11782	3869 GO:0010257	NADH dehydrogenase complex assembly
303	52	11525	3817 GO:0005975	carbohydrate metabolic process
163	20	11665	3849 GO:0006732	coenzyme metabolic process
697	155	11131	3714 GO:0006629	lipid metabolic process
128	13	11700	3856 GO:0034504	protein localization to nucleus
101	8	11727	3861 GO:0030176	integral component of endoplasmic reticulum membrane
101	8	11727	3861 GO:0009260	ribonucleotide biosynthetic process
418	81	11410	3788 GO:0045936	negative regulation of phosphate metabolic process

418	81	11410	3788 GO:0010563	negative regulation of phosphorus metabolic process
637	139	11191	3730 GO:0044212	transcription regulatory region DNA binding
83	5	11745	3864 GO:0051082	unfolded protein binding
251	40	11577	3829 GO:1903829	positive regulation of cellular protein localization
966	231	10862	3638 GO:0035556	intracellular signal transduction
45	0	11783	3869 GO:1990928	response to amino acid starvation
142	16	11686	3853 GO:0051427	hormone receptor binding
137	15	11691	3854 GO:0005925	focal adhesion
76	4	11752	3865 GO:0008276	protein methyltransferase activity
62	2	11766	3867 GO:0009055	electron transfer activity
233	36	11595	3833 GO:0072521	purine-containing compound metabolic process
54	1	11774	3868 GO:0097525	spliceosomal snRNP complex
121	12	11707	3857 GO:0050684	regulation of mRNA processing
105	9	11723	3860 GO:0072522	purine-containing compound biosynthetic process
215	32	11613	3837 GO:1901652	response to peptide
179	24	11649	3845 GO:0016747	transferase activity, transferring acyl groups other than amino-acyl groups
126	13	11702	3856 GO:0031072	heat shock protein binding
131	14	11697	3855 GO:0016853	isomerase activity
136	15	11692	3854 GO:0090150	establishment of protein localization to membrane
735	167	11093	3702 GO:0060548	negative regulation of cell death
110	10	11718	3859 GO:0042177	negative regulation of protein catabolic process
44	0	11784	3869 GO:0000428	DNA-directed RNA polymerase complex
192	27	11636	3842 GO:0031965	nuclear membrane
355	66	11473	3803 GO:0042326	negative regulation of phosphorylation
68	3	11760	3866 GO:0022900	electron transport chain
140	16	11688	3853 GO:0034599	cellular response to oxidative stress
125	13	11703	3856 GO:0034249	negative regulation of cellular amide metabolic process
417	82	11411	3787 GO:0007346	regulation of mitotic cell cycle
159	20	11669	3849 GO:0031967	organelle envelope
159	20	11669	3849 GO:0031975	envelope
109	10	11719	3859 GO:0045444	fat cell differentiation
109	10	11719	3859 GO:0046488	phosphatidylinositol metabolic process
285	49	11543	3820 GO:0032549	ribonucleoside binding
74	4	11754	3865 GO:0042147	retrograde transport, endosome to Golgi
217	33	11611	3836 GO:0031984	organelle subcompartment
760	175	11068	3694 GO:0051270	regulation of cellular component movement
139	16	11689	3853 GO:0031056	regulation of histone modification
234	37	11594	3832 GO:0007264	small GTPase mediated signal transduction
43	0	11785	3869 GO:0043038	amino acid activation
43	0	11785	3869 GO:0055029	nuclear DNA-directed RNA polymerase complex
124	13	11704	3856 GO:0005996	monosaccharide metabolic process
80	5	11748	3864 GO:0032436	positive regulation of proteasomal ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process

80	5	11748	3864 GO:0008170	N-methyltransferase activity
129	14	11699	3855 GO:0004386	helicase activity
86	6	11742	3863 GO:0004540	ribonuclease activity
238	38	11590	3831 GO:0006897	endocytosis
67	3	11761	3866 GO:0000118	histone deacetylase complex
67	3	11761	3866 GO:0031123	RNA 3'-end processing
434	87	11394	3782 GO:0071495	cellular response to endogenous stimulus
229	36	11599	3833 GO:0000790	nuclear chromatin
				positive regulation of proteasomal protein catabolic process
97	8	11731	3861 GO:1901800	process
320	58	11508	3811 GO:0001933	negative regulation of protein phosphorylation
320	58	11508	3811 GO:0030029	actin filament-based process
291	51	11537	3818 GO:0001882	nucleoside binding
266	45	11562	3824 GO:0045862	positive regulation of proteolysis
245	40	11583	3829 GO:0009991	response to extracellular stimulus
59	2	11769	3867 GO:0070585	protein localization to mitochondrion
107	10	11721	3859 GO:0047485	protein N-terminus binding
				positive regulation of proteolysis involved in cellular protein catabolic process
107	10	11721	3859 GO:1903052	protein catabolic process
42	0	11786	3869 GO:0043039	tRNA aminoacylation
42	0	11786	3869 GO:0005801	cis-Golgi network
282	49	11546	3820 GO:0032550	purine ribonucleoside binding
206	31	11622	3838 GO:0051348	negative regulation of transferase activity
				oxidoreductase activity, acting on a sulfur group of donors
51	1	11777	3868 GO:0016667	donors
393	77	11435	3792 GO:0051345	positive regulation of hydrolase activity
90	7	11738	3862 GO:0051168	nuclear export
858	204	10970	3665 GO:0009968	negative regulation of signal transduction
165	22	11663	3847 GO:0043434	response to peptide hormone
72	4	11756	3865 GO:0036503	ERAD pathway
72	4	11756	3865 GO:1990542	mitochondrial transmembrane transport
146	18	11682	3851 GO:0030055	cell-substrate junction
78	5	11750	3864 GO:0072329	monocarboxylic acid catabolic process
78	5	11750	3864 GO:0048524	positive regulation of viral process
78	5	11750	3864 GO:0006006	glucose metabolic process
78	5	11750	3864 GO:0006892	post-Golgi vesicle-mediated transport
160	21	11668	3848 GO:0019207	kinase regulator activity
309	56	11519	3813 GO:0051098	regulation of binding
111	11	11717	3858 GO:0017148	negative regulation of translation
111	11	11717	3858 GO:0001650	fibrillar center
276	48	11552	3821 GO:0005525	GTP binding
116	12	11712	3857 GO:0043484	regulation of RNA splicing
284	50	11544	3819 GO:0001883	purine nucleoside binding
41	0	11787	3869 GO:0034198	cellular response to amino acid starvation
652	147	11176	3722 GO:0003690	double-stranded DNA binding

				positive regulation of ubiquitin-dependent protein
89	7	11739	3862 GO:2000060	catabolic process
100	9	11728	3860 GO:0006164	purine nucleotide biosynthetic process
71	4	11757	3865 GO:0006997	nucleus organization
271	47	11557	3822 GO:0042578	phosphoric ester hydrolase activity
154	20	11674	3849 GO:0010008	endosome membrane
130	15	11698	3854 GO:0010594	regulation of endothelial cell migration
64	3	11764	3866 GO:0022904	respiratory electron transport chain
64	3	11764	3866 GO:0000932	P-body
64	3	11764	3866 GO:0090734	site of DNA damage
158	21	11670	3848 GO:0070482	response to oxygen levels
99	9	11729	3860 GO:0016458	gene silencing
40	0	11788	3869 GO:0016875	ligase activity, forming carbon-oxygen bonds
40	0	11788	3869 GO:0004812	aminoacyl-tRNA ligase activity
				retrograde vesicle-mediated transport, Golgi to
40	0	11788	3869 GO:0006890	endoplasmic reticulum
539	117	11289	3752 GO:0010942	positive regulation of cell death
49	1	11779	3868 GO:0031593	polyubiquitin modification-dependent protein binding
49	1	11779	3868 GO:0010823	negative regulation of mitochondrion organization
70	4	11758	3865 GO:0030522	intracellular receptor signaling pathway
63	3	11765	3866 GO:0030433	ubiquitin-dependent ERAD pathway
138	17	11690	3852 GO:0031461	cullin-RING ubiquitin ligase complex
56	2	11772	3867 GO:0070063	RNA polymerase binding
56	2	11772	3867 GO:0098732	macromolecule deacylation
56	2	11772	3867 GO:0035601	protein deacylation
56	2	11772	3867 GO:0090501	RNA phosphodiester bond hydrolysis
625	141	11203	3728 GO:0009628	response to abiotic stimulus
496	106	11332	3763 GO:0043068	positive regulation of programmed cell death
128	15	11700	3854 GO:1901981	phosphatidylinositol phosphate binding
81	6	11747	3863 GO:0043535	regulation of blood vessel endothelial cell migration
2161	594	9667	3275 GO:0023051	regulation of signaling
39	0	11789	3869 GO:0030490	maturation of SSU-rRNA
39	0	11789	3869 GO:0006418	tRNA aminoacylation for protein translation
39	0	11789	3869 GO:0060590	ATPase regulator activity
92	8	11736	3861 GO:0009152	purine ribonucleotide biosynthetic process
165	23	11663	3846 GO:0062197	cellular response to chemical stress
777	184	11051	3685 GO:1901700	response to oxygen-containing compound
561	124	11267	3745 GO:0017111	nucleoside-triphosphatase activity
221	36	11607	3833 GO:0046486	glycerolipid metabolic process
579	129	11249	3740 GO:0009719	response to endogenous stimulus
55	2	11773	3867 GO:0072655	establishment of protein localization to mitochondrion
55	2	11773	3867 GO:1903902	positive regulation of viral life cycle
55	2	11773	3867 GO:0005776	autophagosome

55	2	11773	3867 GO:0005793	endoplasmic reticulum-Golgi intermediate compartment
107	11	11721	3858 GO:0016779	nucleotidyltransferase activity
589	132	11239	3737 GO:1990837	sequence-specific double-stranded DNA binding
290	53	11538	3816 GO:0030036	actin cytoskeleton organization
68	4	11760	3865 GO:0043130	ubiquitin binding
241	41	11587	3828 GO:0043087	regulation of GTPase activity
136	17	11692	3852 GO:0009165	nucleotide biosynthetic process
650	149	11178	3720 GO:0051338	regulation of transferase activity
47	1	11781	3868 GO:0071806	protein transmembrane transport
207	33	11621	3836 GO:0044419	interspecies interaction between organisms
2149	592	9679	3277 GO:0010646	regulation of cell communication
96	9	11732	3860 GO:0003697	single-stranded DNA binding
38	0	11790	3869 GO:0000959	mitochondrial RNA metabolic process
1183	302	10645	3567 GO:0051174	regulation of phosphorus metabolic process
492	106	11336	3763 GO:0043065	positive regulation of apoptotic process
				intrinsic component of endoplasmic reticulum
				membrane
106	11	11722	3858 GO:0031227	membrane
1182	302	10646	3567 GO:0019220	regulation of phosphate metabolic process
79	6	11749	3863 GO:0048284	organelle fusion
90	8	11738	3861 GO:0016410	N-acyltransferase activity
73	5	11755	3864 GO:0006497	protein lipidation
73	5	11755	3864 GO:0035966	response to topologically incorrect protein
144	19	11684	3850 GO:0031669	cellular response to nutrient levels
184	28	11644	3841 GO:2001234	negative regulation of apoptotic signaling pathway
46	1	11782	3868 GO:0003743	translation initiation factor activity
46	1	11782	3868 GO:0030880	RNA polymerase complex
46	1	11782	3868 GO:0065002	intracellular protein transmembrane transport
105	11	11723	3858 GO:0006479	protein methylation
105	11	11723	3858 GO:0008213	protein alkylation
110	12	11718	3857 GO:0005088	Ras guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity
37	0	11791	3869 GO:0003899	DNA-directed 5'-3' RNA polymerase activity
60	3	11768	3866 GO:0032922	circadian regulation of gene expression
143	19	11685	3850 GO:0030258	lipid modification
761	182	11067	3687 GO:0098796	membrane protein complex
690	162	11138	3707 GO:0016310	phosphorylation
216	36	11612	3833 GO:0001525	angiogenesis
142	19	11686	3850 GO:0001666	response to hypoxia
				positive regulation of protein-containing complex
182	28	11646	3841 GO:0031334	assembly
45	1	11783	3868 GO:0042645	mitochondrial nucleoid
45	1	11783	3868 GO:0007032	endosome organization
45	1	11783	3868 GO:0009295	nucleoid
77	6	11751	3863 GO:1904949	ATPase complex
59	3	11769	3866 GO:0016209	antioxidant activity
59	3	11769	3866 GO:0030117	membrane coat

173	26	11655	3843 GO:0006650	glycerophospholipid metabolic process
203	33	11625	3836 GO:0016791	phosphatase activity
36	0	11792	3869 GO:0032040	small-subunit processome
146	20	11682	3849 GO:0036293	response to decreased oxygen levels
71	5	11757	3864 GO:0017053	transcriptional repressor complex
434	92	11394	3777 GO:0051493	regulation of cytoskeleton organization
98	10	11730	3859 GO:1905269	positive regulation of chromatin organization
1078	274	10750	3595 GO:0042325	regulation of phosphorylation
194	31	11634	3838 GO:0098791	Golgi subcompartment
181	28	11647	3841 GO:0010632	regulation of epithelial cell migration
926	230	10902	3639 GO:0010648	negative regulation of cell communication
44	1	11784	3868 GO:0016236	macroautophagy
44	1	11784	3868 GO:0022627	cytosolic small ribosomal subunit
44	1	11784	3868 GO:0008333	endosome to lysosome transport
58	3	11770	3866 GO:0051536	iron-sulfur cluster binding
58	3	11770	3866 GO:0051540	metal cluster binding
58	3	11770	3866 GO:0030374	nuclear receptor transcription coactivator activity
58	3	11770	3866 GO:0005643	nuclear pore
97	10	11731	3859 GO:0016922	nuclear receptor binding
226	39	11602	3830 GO:0006644	phospholipid metabolic process
70	5	11758	3864 GO:0003725	double-stranded RNA binding
102	11	11726	3858 GO:0061013	regulation of mRNA catabolic process
774	187	11054	3682 GO:0022603	regulation of anatomical structure morphogenesis
64	4	11764	3865 GO:0070491	repressing transcription factor binding
35	0	11793	3869 GO:0017112	Rab guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity
35	0	11793	3869 GO:0000184	nuclear-transcribed mRNA catabolic process, nonsense-mediated decay
35	0	11793	3869 GO:1990391	DNA repair complex
166	25	11662	3844 GO:1902115	regulation of organelle assembly
293	56	11535	3813 GO:0051052	regulation of DNA metabolic process
75	6	11753	3863 GO:0045335	phagocytic vesicle
75	6	11753	3863 GO:1903363	negative regulation of cellular protein catabolic process
75	6	11753	3863 GO:0032204	regulation of telomere maintenance
139	19	11689	3850 GO:1901293	nucleoside phosphate biosynthetic process
928	232	10900	3637 GO:0023057	negative regulation of signaling
43	1	11785	3868 GO:0043966	histone H3 acetylation
43	1	11785	3868 GO:0045646	regulation of erythrocyte differentiation
43	1	11785	3868 GO:0080171	lytic vacuole organization
43	1	11785	3868 GO:0031952	regulation of protein autophosphorylation
43	1	11785	3868 GO:0007040	lysosome organization
69	5	11759	3864 GO:0010822	positive regulation of mitochondrion organization
152	22	11676	3847 GO:2001235	positive regulation of apoptotic signaling pathway
143	20	11685	3849 GO:0005635	nuclear envelope
292	56	11536	3813 GO:0009790	embryo development
323	64	11505	3805 GO:0044283	small molecule biosynthetic process

182	29	11646	3840 GO:2001020	regulation of response to DNA damage stimulus
34	0	11794	3869 GO:1903146	regulation of autophagy of mitochondrion
34	0	11794	3869 GO:0030120	vesicle coat
34	0	11794	3869 GO:0030518	intracellular steroid hormone receptor signaling pathway
186	30	11642	3839 GO:0071496	cellular response to external stimulus
368	76	11460	3793 GO:0070925	organelle assembly
100	11	11728	3858 GO:0042826	histone deacetylase binding
95	10	11733	3859 GO:0045185	maintenance of protein location
95	10	11733	3859 GO:0098852	lytic vacuole membrane
95	10	11733	3859 GO:0005765	lysosomal membrane
287	55	11541	3814 GO:0019001	guanyl nucleotide binding
287	55	11541	3814 GO:0032561	guanyl ribonucleotide binding
56	3	11772	3866 GO:0045454	cell redox homeostasis
155	23	11673	3846 GO:0000139	Golgi membrane
42	1	11786	3868 GO:0032007	negative regulation of TOR signaling
84	8	11744	3861 GO:0009108	coenzyme biosynthetic process
123	16	11705	3853 GO:0008654	phospholipid biosynthetic process
647	153	11181	3716 GO:0043069	negative regulation of programmed cell death
94	10	11734	3859 GO:0048814	regulation of dendrite morphogenesis
682	163	11146	3706 GO:0044092	negative regulation of molecular function
118	15	11710	3854 GO:1903322	protein conjugation or removal
11301	3637	527	232 GO:0003674	molecular_function
33	0	11795	3869 GO:0017004	cytochrome complex assembly
33	0	11795	3869 GO:0006356	regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase I
33	0	11795	3869 GO:0008175	tRNA methyltransferase activity
67	5	11761	3864 GO:0005811	lipid droplet
158	24	11670	3845 GO:0032388	positive regulation of intracellular transport
55	3	11773	3866 GO:0051701	interaction with host
55	3	11773	3866 GO:1990841	promoter-specific chromatin binding
61	4	11767	3865 GO:0098573	intrinsic component of mitochondrial membrane
179	29	11649	3840 GO:0032870	cellular response to hormone stimulus
41	1	11787	3868 GO:0043175	RNA polymerase core enzyme binding
41	1	11787	3868 GO:1902562	H4 histone acetyltransferase complex
41	1	11787	3868 GO:1903573	negative regulation of response to endoplasmic reticulum stress
41	1	11787	3868 GO:0140296	general transcription initiation factor binding
88	9	11740	3860 GO:0032092	positive regulation of protein binding
93	10	11735	3859 GO:0015980	energy derivation by oxidation of organic compounds
93	10	11735	3859 GO:0043487	regulation of RNA stability
1117	290	10711	3579 GO:0048585	negative regulation of response to stimulus
72	6	11756	3863 GO:0070603	SWI/SNF superfamily-type complex
187	31	11641	3838 GO:0043393	regulation of protein binding
48	2	11780	3867 GO:0042054	histone methyltransferase activity

48	2	11780	3867 GO:0032784	regulation of DNA-templated transcription, elongation
48	2	11780	3867 GO:0035861	site of double-strand break
569	132	11259	3737 GO:0016301	kinase activity
170	27	11658	3842 GO:0016311	dephosphorylation transcription regulatory region sequence-specific DNA
554	128	11274	3741 GO:0000976	binding
77	7	11751	3862 GO:0016363	nuclear matrix
178	29	11650	3840 GO:0033673	negative regulation of kinase activity
393	84	11435	3785 GO:0044089	positive regulation of cellular component biogenesis
66	5	11762	3864 GO:0043200	response to amino acid
139	20	11689	3849 GO:0019867	outer membrane
139	20	11689	3849 GO:0031968	organelle outer membrane
32	0	11796	3869 GO:0043628	ncRNA 3'-end processing
32	0	11796	3869 GO:0004532	exoribonuclease activity
32	0	11796	3869 GO:0005669	transcription factor TFIID complex
32	0	11796	3869 GO:0006367	transcription initiation from RNA polymerase II promoter
173	28	11655	3841 GO:0051054	positive regulation of DNA metabolic process
198	34	11630	3835 GO:0016746	transferase activity, transferring acyl groups
40	1	11788	3868 GO:0070972	protein localization to endoplasmic reticulum
40	1	11788	3868 GO:0006406	mRNA export from nucleus
40	1	11788	3868 GO:0061650	ubiquitin-like protein conjugating enzyme activity
465	104	11363	3765 GO:0120036	plasma membrane bounded cell projection organization
47	2	11781	3867 GO:0070936	protein K48-linked ubiquitination
138	20	11690	3849 GO:2001242	regulation of intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway
106	13	11722	3856 GO:0006338	chromatin remodeling
424	93	11404	3776 GO:0030335	positive regulation of cell migration
664	160	11164	3709 GO:0051336	regulation of hydrolase activity
59	4	11769	3865 GO:0044272	sulfur compound biosynthetic process
59	4	11769	3865 GO:0032592	integral component of mitochondrial membrane
159	25	11669	3844 GO:0031668	cellular response to extracellular stimulus
31	0	11797	3869 GO:0016073	snRNA metabolic process exoribonuclease activity, producing 5'-
31	0	11797	3869 GO:0016896	phosphomonoesters
31	0	11797	3869 GO:0097526	spliceosomal tri-snRNP complex
31	0	11797	3869 GO:0030488	tRNA methylation
31	0	11797	3869 GO:0005484	SNAP receptor activity
75	7	11753	3862 GO:0009141	nucleoside triphosphate metabolic process
39	1	11789	3868 GO:0016574	histone ubiquitination
39	1	11789	3868 GO:0044088	regulation of vacuole organization
39	1	11789	3868 GO:0032456	endocytic recycling
46	2	11782	3867 GO:0003724	RNA helicase activity
46	2	11782	3867 GO:0006476	protein deacetylation
46	2	11782	3867 GO:0008408	3'-5' exonuclease activity

175	29	11653	3840 GO:0019902	phosphatase binding
220	40	11608	3829 GO:0110053	regulation of actin filament organization
64	5	11764	3864 GO:1903051	negative regulation of proteolysis involved in cellular protein catabolic process
64	5	11764	3864 GO:0009062	fatty acid catabolic process
64	5	11764	3864 GO:0014743	regulation of muscle hypertrophy
85	9	11743	3860 GO:0017015	regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
85	9	11743	3860 GO:0048024	regulation of mRNA splicing, via spliceosome
85	9	11743	3860 GO:0051170	import into nucleus
191	33	11637	3836 GO:0070848	response to growth factor
118	16	11710	3853 GO:0120161	regulation of cold-induced thermogenesis
58	4	11770	3865 GO:0071230	cellular response to amino acid stimulus
52	3	11776	3866 GO:0030218	erythrocyte differentiation
316	65	11512	3804 GO:0016887	ATPase activity
131	19	11697	3850 GO:0019887	protein kinase regulator activity
30	0	11798	3869 GO:0044743	protein transmembrane import into intracellular organelle
30	0	11798	3869 GO:0046540	U4/U6 x U5 tri-snRNP complex
30	0	11798	3869 GO:0000314	organellar small ribosomal subunit
30	0	11798	3869 GO:0005763	mitochondrial small ribosomal subunit
30	0	11798	3869 GO:0033558	protein deacetylase activity
30	0	11798	3869 GO:0062125	regulation of mitochondrial gene expression
74	7	11754	3862 GO:1903321	negative regulation of protein modification by small protein conjugation or removal
94	11	11734	3858 GO:0046034	ATP metabolic process
254	49	11574	3820 GO:0010769	regulation of cell morphogenesis involved in differentiation
148	23	11680	3846 GO:0010770	positive regulation of cell morphogenesis involved in differentiation
84	9	11744	3860 GO:0043488	regulation of mRNA stability
63	5	11765	3864 GO:0006986	response to unfolded protein
63	5	11765	3864 GO:0010611	regulation of cardiac muscle hypertrophy
45	2	11783	3867 GO:0006635	fatty acid beta-oxidation
117	16	11711	3853 GO:0009411	response to UV
38	1	11790	3868 GO:0043401	steroid hormone mediated signaling pathway
38	1	11790	3868 GO:0072595	maintenance of protein localization in organelle
38	1	11790	3868 GO:0097747	RNA polymerase activity
38	1	11790	3868 GO:0034062	5'-3' RNA polymerase activity
683	167	11145	3702 GO:0099080	supramolecular complex
311	64	11517	3805 GO:0032787	monocarboxylic acid metabolic process
341	72	11487	3797 GO:0071345	cellular response to cytokine stimulus
156	25	11672	3844 GO:0140097	catalytic activity, acting on DNA
57	4	11771	3865 GO:0006612	protein targeting to membrane
51	3	11777	3866 GO:0050775	positive regulation of dendrite morphogenesis
51	3	11777	3866 GO:0004521	endoribonuclease activity

51	3	11777	3866 GO:0031228	intrinsic component of Golgi membrane
121	17	11707	3852 GO:0040029	regulation of gene expression, epigenetic
68	6	11760	3863 GO:0050660	flavin adenine dinucleotide binding
562	133	11266	3736 GO:0043549	regulation of kinase activity
213	39	11615	3830 GO:0051056	regulation of small GTPase mediated signal transduction
306	63	11522	3806 GO:0072657	protein localization to membrane
125	18	11703	3851 GO:0000302	response to reactive oxygen species
83	9	11745	3860 GO:1902911	protein kinase complex
29	0	11799	3869 GO:0044665	MLL1/2 complex
29	0	11799	3869 GO:0071339	MLL1 complex
29	0	11799	3869 GO:0000175	3'-5'-exoribonuclease activity
29	0	11799	3869 GO:0000470	maturation of LSU-rRNA
29	0	11799	3869 GO:0003954	NADH dehydrogenase activity
29	0	11799	3869 GO:0004407	histone deacetylase activity
29	0	11799	3869 GO:0007007	inner mitochondrial membrane organization
44	2	11784	3867 GO:0031519	PcG protein complex
305	63	11523	3806 GO:0010639	negative regulation of organelle organization
97	12	11731	3857 GO:0031398	positive regulation of protein ubiquitination
37	1	11791	3868 GO:1903432	regulation of TORC1 signaling
37	1	11791	3868 GO:0032008	positive regulation of TOR signaling
37	1	11791	3868 GO:0061631	ubiquitin conjugating enzyme activity
133	20	11695	3849 GO:0008360	regulation of cell shape
251	49	11577	3820 GO:0019216	regulation of lipid metabolic process
50	3	11778	3866 GO:0001221	transcription cofactor binding
128	19	11700	3850 GO:0005741	mitochondrial outer membrane
629	153	11199	3716 GO:0007010	cytoskeleton organization
61	5	11767	3864 GO:0034440	lipid oxidation
494	115	11334	3754 GO:0045859	regulation of protein kinase activity
972	253	10856	3616 GO:0001932	regulation of protein phosphorylation
238	46	11590	3823 GO:0001701	in utero embryonic development
149	24	11679	3845 GO:0050773	regulation of dendrite development
628	153	11200	3716 GO:0043066	negative regulation of apoptotic process
91	11	11737	3858 GO:0061025	membrane fusion
214	40	11614	3829 GO:0044282	small molecule catabolic process
66	6	11762	3863 GO:0098876	vesicle-mediated transport to the plasma membrane
66	6	11762	3863 GO:0031397	negative regulation of protein ubiquitination
66	6	11762	3863 GO:0090174	organelle membrane fusion
28	0	11800	3869 GO:0006515	protein quality control for misfolded or incompletely synthesized proteins
28	0	11800	3869 GO:0033866	nucleoside bisphosphate biosynthetic process
28	0	11800	3869 GO:0034030	ribonucleoside bisphosphate biosynthetic process
28	0	11800	3869 GO:0034033	purine nucleoside bisphosphate biosynthetic process
157	26	11671	3843 GO:0022411	cellular component disassembly

86	10	11742	3859 GO:1903844	regulation of cellular response to transforming growth factor beta stimulus
36	1	11792	3868 GO:0016684	oxidoreductase activity, acting on peroxide as acceptor
36	1	11792	3868 GO:0000993	RNA polymerase II complex binding
36	1	11792	3868 GO:0005048	signal sequence binding
36	1	11792	3868 GO:0031304	intrinsic component of mitochondrial inner membrane regulation of transcription elongation from RNA
36	1	11792	3868 GO:0034243	polymerase II promoter
36	1	11792	3868 GO:0015036	disulfide oxidoreductase activity
71	7	11757	3862 GO:0031060	regulation of histone methylation
49	3	11779	3866 GO:0046902	regulation of mitochondrial membrane permeability
49	3	11779	3866 GO:0030173	integral component of Golgi membrane
81	9	11747	3860 GO:0006606	protein import into nucleus
453	104	11375	3765 GO:0040017	positive regulation of locomotion
144	23	11684	3846 GO:0016829	lyase activity
144	23	11684	3846 GO:0050792	regulation of viral process
169	29	11659	3840 GO:0015629	actin cytoskeleton
2334	669	9494	3200 GO:0065008	regulation of biological quality
60	5	11768	3864 GO:0019395	fatty acid oxidation
523	124	11305	3745 GO:0016773	phosphotransferase activity, alcohol group as acceptor
839	215	10989	3654 GO:0031401	positive regulation of protein modification process
65	6	11763	3863 GO:0016605	PML body
251	50	11577	3819 GO:0009792	embryo development ending in birth or egg hatching
54	4	11774	3865 GO:1902600	proton transmembrane transport
54	4	11774	3865 GO:0009199	ribonucleoside triphosphate metabolic process
42	2	11786	3867 GO:0016575	histone deacetylation
70	7	11758	3862 GO:0010827	regulation of glucose transmembrane transport
134	21	11694	3848 GO:0051235	maintenance of location
35	1	11793	3868 GO:1901998	toxin transport
35	1	11793	3868 GO:0051898	negative regulation of protein kinase B signaling
35	1	11793	3868 GO:0031305	integral component of mitochondrial inner membrane
35	1	11793	3868 GO:0060964	regulation of gene silencing by miRNA
27	0	11801	3869 GO:0070129	regulation of mitochondrial translation regulation of endoplasmic reticulum stress-induced
27	0	11801	3869 GO:1902235	intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway
27	0	11801	3869 GO:0001825	blastocyst formation
27	0	11801	3869 GO:0030515	snoRNA binding
432	99	11396	3770 GO:2000147	positive regulation of cell motility
630	155	11198	3714 GO:0030030	cell projection organization
59	5	11769	3864 GO:0006513	protein monoubiquitination
59	5	11769	3864 GO:0009144	purine nucleoside triphosphate metabolic process
171	30	11657	3839 GO:0051495	positive regulation of cytoskeleton organization

175	31	11653	3838 GO:0071363	cellular response to growth factor stimulus
242	48	11586	3821 GO:0043009	chordate embryonic development
84	10	11744	3859 GO:0051087	chaperone binding
98	13	11730	3856 GO:2000045	regulation of G1/S transition of mitotic cell cycle
64	6	11764	3863 GO:0000784	nuclear chromosome, telomeric region
154	26	11674	3843 GO:0005802	trans-Golgi network
69	7	11759	3862 GO:0016651	oxidoreductase activity, acting on NAD(P)H
69	7	11759	3862 GO:1902554	serine/threonine protein kinase complex
53	4	11775	3865 GO:0005788	endoplasmic reticulum lumen
53	4	11775	3865 GO:0010494	cytoplasmic stress granule
137	22	11691	3847 GO:0019903	protein phosphatase binding
124	19	11704	3850 GO:0030139	endocytic vesicle
47	3	11781	3866 GO:0016627	oxidoreductase activity, acting on the CH-CH group of donors
47	3	11781	3866 GO:0016796	exonuclease activity, active with either ribo- or deoxyribonucleic acids and producing 5'-phosphomonoesters
47	3	11781	3866 GO:0043967	histone H4 acetylation
47	3	11781	3866 GO:0061077	chaperone-mediated protein folding
128	20	11700	3849 GO:2001236	regulation of extrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway
115	17	11713	3852 GO:0030135	coated vesicle
34	1	11794	3868 GO:0043331	response to dsRNA
34	1	11794	3868 GO:0000726	non-recombinational repair
34	1	11794	3868 GO:0032205	negative regulation of telomere maintenance
34	1	11794	3868 GO:0032451	demethylase activity
34	1	11794	3868 GO:0032543	mitochondrial translation
58	5	11770	3864 GO:0090559	regulation of membrane permeability
83	10	11745	3859 GO:0031058	positive regulation of histone modification
26	0	11802	3869 GO:0042273	ribosomal large subunit biogenesis
26	0	11802	3869 GO:0044257	cellular protein catabolic process
26	0	11802	3869 GO:0071007	U2-type catalytic step 2 spliceosome
26	0	11802	3869 GO:0000154	rRNA modification
26	0	11802	3869 GO:0006891	intra-Golgi vesicle-mediated transport
26	0	11802	3869 GO:0035198	miRNA binding
161	28	11667	3841 GO:0006469	negative regulation of protein kinase activity
181	33	11647	3836 GO:0032271	regulation of protein polymerization
73	8	11755	3861 GO:0072593	reactive oxygen species metabolic process
52	4	11776	3865 GO:0001047	core promoter binding
52	4	11776	3865 GO:0051287	NAD binding
52	4	11776	3865 GO:0030512	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
127	20	11701	3849 GO:0097193	intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway
114	17	11714	3852 GO:0045598	regulation of fat cell differentiation
114	17	11714	3852 GO:0031589	cell-substrate adhesion
40	2	11788	3867 GO:0018024	histone-lysine N-methyltransferase activity
40	2	11788	3867 GO:1901264	carbohydrate derivative transport

40	2	11788	3867 GO:0031201	SNARE complex
192	36	11636	3833 GO:0060249	anatomical structure homeostasis
46	3	11782	3866 GO:0072665	protein localization to vacuole
46	3	11782	3866 GO:0010332	response to gamma radiation negative regulation of intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway
82	10	11746	3859 GO:2001243	cellular response to reactive oxygen species
82	10	11746	3859 GO:0034614	cellular response to reactive oxygen species
135	22	11693	3847 GO:0043413	macromolecule glycosylation
135	22	11693	3847 GO:0006486	protein glycosylation
1802	509	10026	3360 GO:0050793	regulation of developmental process
139	23	11689	3846 GO:0030705	cytoskeleton-dependent intracellular transport
122	19	11706	3850 GO:0044242	cellular lipid catabolic process
122	19	11706	3850 GO:0001568	blood vessel development
77	9	11751	3860 GO:0031098	stress-activated protein kinase signaling cascade
143	24	11685	3845 GO:0070085	glycosylation
62	6	11766	3863 GO:0005758	mitochondrial intermembrane space oxidoreductase activity, acting on NAD(P)H, quinone or similar compound as acceptor
33	1	11795	3868 GO:0016655	similar compound as acceptor
33	1	11795	3868 GO:2000785	regulation of autophagosome assembly
72	8	11756	3861 GO:0031970	organelle envelope lumen
72	8	11756	3861 GO:0033865	nucleoside bisphosphate metabolic process
72	8	11756	3861 GO:0033875	ribonucleoside bisphosphate metabolic process
72	8	11756	3861 GO:0034032	purine nucleoside bisphosphate metabolic process
151	26	11677	3843 GO:1902905	positive regulation of supramolecular fiber organization
525	127	11303	3742 GO:0001012	RNA polymerase II regulatory region DNA binding
546	133	11282	3736 GO:0070201	regulation of establishment of protein localization
113	17	11715	3852 GO:1903900	regulation of viral life cycle
298	64	11530	3805 GO:0008610	lipid biosynthetic process
25	0	11803	3869 GO:0070461	SAGA-type complex
25	0	11803	3869 GO:0046966	thyroid hormone receptor binding
25	0	11803	3869 GO:0050136	NADH dehydrogenase (quinone) activity maturation of SSU-rRNA from tricistronic rRNA transcript (SSU-rRNA, 5.8S rRNA, LSU-rRNA)
25	0	11803	3869 GO:0000462	(SSU-rRNA, 5.8S rRNA, LSU-rRNA)
25	0	11803	3869 GO:0001671	ATPase activator activity
25	0	11803	3869 GO:0005689	U12-type spliceosomal complex
25	0	11803	3869 GO:0008137	NADH dehydrogenase (ubiquinone) activity
25	0	11803	3869 GO:0034661	ncRNA catabolic process
25	0	11803	3869 GO:0090140	regulation of mitochondrial fission
175	32	11653	3837 GO:0007265	Ras protein signal transduction
51	4	11777	3865 GO:0016278	lysine N-methyltransferase activity
51	4	11777	3865 GO:0016279	protein-lysine N-methyltransferase activity
117	18	11711	3851 GO:0019838	growth factor binding
496	119	11332	3750 GO:0040008	regulation of growth negative regulation of ubiquitin-dependent protein catabolic process
45	3	11783	3866 GO:2000059	catabolic process

90	12	11738	3857 GO:0000781	chromosome, telomeric region
90	12	11738	3857 GO:0055037	recycling endosome
56	5	11772	3864 GO:2000378	negative regulation of reactive oxygen species metabolic process
537	131	11291	3738 GO:0048646	anatomical structure formation involved in morphogenesis
71	8	11757	3861 GO:0016571	histone methylation
66	7	11762	3862 GO:0000723	telomere maintenance
66	7	11762	3862 GO:0032200	telomere organization
66	7	11762	3862 GO:0032507	maintenance of protein location in cell
554	136	11274	3733 GO:0120035	regulation of plasma membrane bounded cell projection organization
201	39	11627	3830 GO:0060090	molecular adaptor activity
32	1	11796	3868 GO:0001103	RNA polymerase II repressing transcription factor binding
32	1	11796	3868 GO:1905898	positive regulation of response to endoplasmic reticulum stress
32	1	11796	3868 GO:0004601	peroxidase activity
32	1	11796	3868 GO:0006303	double-strand break repair via nonhomologous end joining
50	4	11778	3865 GO:0009205	purine ribonucleoside triphosphate metabolic process
153	27	11675	3842 GO:0043903	regulation of symbiosis, encompassing mutualism through parasitism
157	28	11671	3841 GO:0000287	magnesium ion binding
128	21	11700	3848 GO:0006470	protein dephosphorylation
24	0	11804	3869 GO:0016180	snRNA processing
24	0	11804	3869 GO:0071782	endoplasmic reticulum tubular network
24	0	11804	3869 GO:0097346	INO80-type complex
24	0	11804	3869 GO:0005158	insulin receptor binding
24	0	11804	3869 GO:0030687	preribosome, large subunit precursor
24	0	11804	3869 GO:0006984	ER-nucleus signaling pathway
70	8	11758	3861 GO:1903312	negative regulation of mRNA metabolic process
115	18	11713	3851 GO:0009266	response to temperature stimulus
38	2	11790	3867 GO:0019213	deacetylase activity
38	2	11790	3867 GO:1900087	positive regulation of G1/S transition of mitotic cell cycle
38	2	11790	3867 GO:0051539	4 iron, 4 sulfur cluster binding
38	2	11790	3867 GO:0010883	regulation of lipid storage
60	6	11768	3863 GO:1903670	regulation of sprouting angiogenesis
60	6	11768	3863 GO:0006906	vesicle fusion
65	7	11763	3862 GO:0072331	signal transduction by p53 class mediator
238	49	11590	3820 GO:0030031	cell projection assembly
172	32	11656	3837 GO:0043547	positive regulation of GTPase activity
156	28	11672	3841 GO:0030427	site of polarized growth
442	105	11386	3764 GO:0051272	positive regulation of cellular component movement

203	40	11625	3829 GO:0006631	fatty acid metabolic process
226	46	11602	3823 GO:0120031	plasma membrane bounded cell projection assembly
427	101	11401	3768 GO:0034097	response to cytokine
256	54	11572	3815 GO:0005789	endoplasmic reticulum membrane negative regulation of proteasomal protein catabolic process
49	4	11779	3865 GO:1901799	ATPase binding
74	9	11754	3860 GO:0051117	ATPase binding
31	1	11797	3868 GO:0016469	proton-transporting two-sector ATPase complex
31	1	11797	3868 GO:0045070	positive regulation of viral genome replication
114	18	11714	3851 GO:0090316	positive regulation of intracellular protein transport
101	15	11727	3854 GO:0043244	regulation of protein-containing complex disassembly
147	26	11681	3843 GO:1905475	regulation of protein localization to membrane
163	30	11665	3839 GO:0070507	regulation of microtubule cytoskeleton organization
69	8	11759	3861 GO:0046332	SMAD binding
69	8	11759	3861 GO:0033613	activating transcription factor binding
54	5	11774	3864 GO:0046324	regulation of glucose import
54	5	11774	3864 GO:0140034	methylation-dependent protein binding
54	5	11774	3864 GO:0035064	methylated histone binding
433	103	11395	3766 GO:0010564	regulation of cell cycle process
59	6	11769	3863 GO:0006637	acyl-CoA metabolic process
59	6	11769	3863 GO:0035383	thioester metabolic process
43	3	11785	3866 GO:0016706	2-oxoglutarate-dependent dioxygenase activity
43	3	11785	3866 GO:0045333	cellular respiration
43	3	11785	3866 GO:0006289	nucleotide-excision repair RNA polymerase II regulatory region sequence-specific
517	127	11311	3742 GO:0000977	DNA binding
23	0	11805	3869 GO:0071108	protein K48-linked deubiquitination vesicle-mediated transport between endosomal compartments
23	0	11805	3869 GO:0098927	compartments
23	0	11805	3869 GO:0000407	phagophore assembly site
23	0	11805	3869 GO:0000469	cleavage involved in rRNA processing
23	0	11805	3869 GO:0031954	positive regulation of protein autophosphorylation
23	0	11805	3869 GO:0008535	respiratory chain complex IV assembly
23	0	11805	3869 GO:0060148	positive regulation of posttranscriptional gene silencing platelet-derived growth factor receptor signaling pathway
37	2	11791	3867 GO:0048008	pathway
37	2	11791	3867 GO:0050873	brown fat cell differentiation
37	2	11791	3867 GO:0002181	cytoplasmic translation
37	2	11791	3867 GO:0060147	regulation of posttranscriptional gene silencing
37	2	11791	3867 GO:0010762	regulation of fibroblast migration
37	2	11791	3867 GO:0060966	regulation of gene silencing by RNA
78	10	11750	3859 GO:0000792	heterochromatin
78	10	11750	3859 GO:0009791	post-embryonic development

113	18	11715	3851 GO:0006260	DNA replication
335	76	11493	3793 GO:0004674	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
1888	541	9940	3328 GO:0032879	regulation of localization
73	9	11755	3860 GO:0035258	steroid hormone receptor binding
313	70	11515	3799 GO:0051640	organelle localization
48	4	11780	3865 GO:0031113	regulation of microtubule polymerization
2518	738	9310	3131 GO:0048583	regulation of response to stimulus
82	11	11746	3858 GO:0010595	positive regulation of endothelial cell migration
557	139	11271	3730 GO:0031344	regulation of cell projection organization
104	16	11724	3853 GO:0010212	response to ionizing radiation
185	36	11643	3833 GO:0046578	regulation of Ras protein signal transduction
327	74	11501	3795 GO:0051301	cell division
				negative regulation of cellular response to transforming
53	5	11775	3864 GO:1903845	growth factor beta stimulus
53	5	11775	3864 GO:0004722	protein serine/threonine phosphatase activity
53	5	11775	3864 GO:0006446	regulation of translational initiation
63	7	11765	3862 GO:1902117	positive regulation of organelle assembly
30	1	11798	3868 GO:0042974	retinoic acid receptor binding
30	1	11798	3868 GO:0050686	negative regulation of mRNA processing
30	1	11798	3868 GO:0006505	GPI anchor metabolic process
30	1	11798	3868 GO:0006998	nuclear envelope organization
30	1	11798	3868 GO:0009225	nucleotide-sugar metabolic process
58	6	11770	3863 GO:0045171	intercellular bridge
145	26	11683	3843 GO:0016054	organic acid catabolic process
145	26	11683	3843 GO:0046395	carboxylic acid catabolic process
42	3	11786	3866 GO:0001046	core promoter sequence-specific DNA binding
36	2	11792	3867 GO:0017069	snRNA binding
36	2	11792	3867 GO:0046854	phosphatidylinositol phosphorylation
72	9	11756	3860 GO:1903313	positive regulation of mRNA metabolic process
				modification of morphology or physiology of other
72	9	11756	3860 GO:0051817	organism involved in symbiotic interaction
124	21	11704	3848 GO:0010970	transport along microtubule
22	0	11806	3869 GO:0045022	early endosome to late endosome transport
				positive regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase I
22	0	11806	3869 GO:0045943	positive regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase I
22	0	11806	3869 GO:2000637	positive regulation of gene silencing by miRNA
22	0	11806	3869 GO:0000178	exosome (RNase complex)
22	0	11806	3869 GO:1905354	exoribonuclease complex
22	0	11806	3869 GO:0031365	N-terminal protein amino acid modification
22	0	11806	3869 GO:0035327	transcriptionally active chromatin
22	0	11806	3869 GO:0035561	regulation of chromatin binding
				RNA phosphodiester bond hydrolysis, endonucleolytic
22	0	11806	3869 GO:0090502	RNA phosphodiester bond hydrolysis, endonucleolytic
47	4	11781	3865 GO:0006661	phosphatidylinositol biosynthetic process
52	5	11776	3864 GO:0007569	cell aging
306	69	11522	3800 GO:0001558	regulation of cell growth

29	1	11799	3868 GO:0016242	negative regulation of macroautophagy
29	1	11799	3868 GO:0043330	response to exogenous dsRNA
29	1	11799	3868 GO:0072599	establishment of protein localization to endoplasmic reticulum
29	1	11799	3868 GO:1902186	regulation of viral release from host cell
29	1	11799	3868 GO:0000387	spliceosomal snRNP assembly
29	1	11799	3868 GO:0002262	myeloid cell homeostasis
29	1	11799	3868 GO:0006414	translational elongation
29	1	11799	3868 GO:0006506	GPI anchor biosynthetic process
29	1	11799	3868 GO:0060260	regulation of transcription initiation from RNA polymerase II promoter
29	1	11799	3868 GO:0010939	regulation of necrotic cell death
41	3	11787	3866 GO:0090199	regulation of release of cytochrome c from mitochondria
135	24	11693	3845 GO:0006302	double-strand break repair
80	11	11748	3858 GO:0046474	glycerophospholipid biosynthetic process
559	141	11269	3728 GO:0007049	cell cycle
35	2	11793	3867 GO:0043531	ADP binding
35	2	11793	3867 GO:0018208	peptidyl-proline modification
35	2	11793	3867 GO:0071326	cellular response to monosaccharide stimulus
35	2	11793	3867 GO:0005778	peroxisomal membrane
35	2	11793	3867 GO:0031463	Cul3-RING ubiquitin ligase complex
35	2	11793	3867 GO:0031903	microbody membrane
35	2	11793	3867 GO:0010613	positive regulation of cardiac muscle hypertrophy
35	2	11793	3867 GO:0014742	positive regulation of muscle hypertrophy
178	35	11650	3834 GO:0007015	actin filament organization
114	19	11714	3850 GO:0036064	ciliary basal body
118	20	11710	3849 GO:0044262	cellular carbohydrate metabolic process
212	44	11616	3825 GO:0071407	cellular response to organic cyclic compound hydrolase activity, acting on carbon-nitrogen (but not peptide) bonds, in linear amides
61	7	11767	3862 GO:0016811	positive regulation of DNA repair
61	7	11767	3862 GO:0045739	cell leading edge
61	7	11767	3862 GO:0031252	Rac GTPase binding
56	6	11772	3863 GO:0048365	regulation of cell-substrate junction organization
56	6	11772	3863 GO:0150116	cortical cytoskeleton organization
51	5	11777	3864 GO:0030865	growth cone
150	28	11678	3841 GO:0030426	cis-regulatory region sequence-specific DNA binding
411	99	11417	3770 GO:0000987	K63-linked polyubiquitin modification-dependent protein binding
21	0	11807	3869 GO:0070530	response to mitochondrial depolarisation
21	0	11807	3869 GO:0098780	cytoplasmic sequestering of protein
21	0	11807	3869 GO:0051220	oxidative phosphorylation
21	0	11807	3869 GO:0006119	RNA localization
21	0	11807	3869 GO:0006403	protein exit from endoplasmic reticulum
21	0	11807	3869 GO:0032527	exon-exon junction complex
21	0	11807	3869 GO:0035145	

21	0	11807	3869 GO:0062098	regulation of programmed necrotic cell death
278	62	11550	3807 GO:0010035	response to inorganic substance
79	11	11749	3858 GO:0042641	actomyosin
442	108	11386	3761 GO:0043086	negative regulation of catalytic activity
109	18	11719	3851 GO:1902806	regulation of cell cycle G1/S phase transition
92	14	11736	3855 GO:0045017	glycerolipid biosynthetic process
28	1	11800	3868 GO:1903421	regulation of synaptic vesicle recycling
28	1	11800	3868 GO:0006482	protein demethylation
28	1	11800	3868 GO:0006754	ATP biosynthetic process
28	1	11800	3868 GO:0008214	protein dealkylation
28	1	11800	3868 GO:0010390	histone monoubiquitination
28	1	11800	3868 GO:0035967	cellular response to topologically incorrect protein
299	68	11529	3801 GO:0045786	negative regulation of cell cycle
342	80	11486	3789 GO:0031346	positive regulation of cell projection organization
74	10	11754	3859 GO:0001726	ruffle
34	2	11794	3867 GO:0016592	mediator complex
34	2	11794	3867 GO:0071331	cellular response to hexose stimulus
34	2	11794	3867 GO:0031369	translation initiation factor binding
34	2	11794	3867 GO:0006261	DNA-dependent DNA replication
34	2	11794	3867 GO:0006458	'de novo' protein folding
34	2	11794	3867 GO:0032781	positive regulation of ATPase activity
45	4	11783	3865 GO:0031047	gene silencing by RNA
45	4	11783	3865 GO:0006893	Golgi to plasma membrane transport
104	17	11724	3852 GO:0046822	regulation of nucleocytoplasmic transport
168	33	11660	3836 GO:0006520	cellular amino acid metabolic process
55	6	11773	3863 GO:0045814	negative regulation of gene expression, epigenetic regulation of telomere maintenance via telomere
55	6	11773	3863 GO:1904356	lengthening
55	6	11773	3863 GO:0032387	negative regulation of intracellular transport
352	83	11476	3786 GO:0014070	response to organic cyclic compound chromatin organization involved in negative regulation of
50	5	11778	3864 GO:0097549	transcription
108	18	11720	3851 GO:1905952	regulation of lipid localization
78	11	11750	3858 GO:1902936	phosphatidylinositol bisphosphate binding
78	11	11750	3858 GO:0051651	maintenance of location in cell
958	261	10870	3608 GO:0080134	regulation of response to stress
156	30	11672	3839 GO:2000377	regulation of reactive oxygen species metabolic process
415	101	11413	3768 GO:0035326	cis-regulatory region binding
116	20	11712	3849 GO:0071478	cellular response to radiation
239	52	11589	3817 GO:0014069	postsynaptic density
272	61	11556	3808 GO:0098589	membrane region
95	15	11733	3854 GO:0004519	endonuclease activity
95	15	11733	3854 GO:0007568	aging
82	12	11746	3857 GO:1901657	glycosyl compound metabolic process
64	8	11764	3861 GO:0018022	peptidyl-lysine methylation

64	8	11764	3861 GO:0001889	liver development
64	8	11764	3861 GO:0006664	glycolipid metabolic process
64	8	11764	3861 GO:0007266	Rho protein signal transduction
279	63	11549	3806 GO:0009314	response to radiation
99	16	11729	3853 GO:2000278	regulation of DNA biosynthetic process
167	33	11661	3836 GO:0016042	lipid catabolic process
				energy coupled proton transport, down electrochemical
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0015985	gradient
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0015986	ATP synthesis coupled proton transport
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0016226	iron-sulfur cluster assembly
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0017049	GTP-Rho binding
20	0	11808	3869 GO:2000209	regulation of anoikis
				RNA polymerase II general transcription initiation factor
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0001091	binding
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0051291	protein heterooligomerization
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0030662	coated vesicle membrane
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0031065	positive regulation of histone deacetylation
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0031163	metallo-sulfur cluster assembly
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0006383	transcription by RNA polymerase III
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0032365	intracellular lipid transport
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0032806	carboxy-terminal domain protein kinase complex
20	0	11808	3869 GO:0033617	mitochondrial respiratory chain complex IV assembly
39	3	11789	3866 GO:0070534	protein K63-linked ubiquitination
39	3	11789	3866 GO:0070849	response to epidermal growth factor
39	3	11789	3866 GO:0055038	recycling endosome membrane
39	3	11789	3866 GO:0009201	ribonucleoside triphosphate biosynthetic process
39	3	11789	3866 GO:0090317	negative regulation of intracellular protein transport
201	42	11627	3827 GO:0097190	apoptotic signaling pathway
				chromatin organization involved in regulation of
59	7	11769	3862 GO:0034401	transcription
27	1	11801	3868 GO:0070536	protein K63-linked deubiquitination
27	1	11801	3868 GO:1902555	endoribonuclease complex
27	1	11801	3868 GO:1903649	regulation of cytoplasmic transport
27	1	11801	3868 GO:0006354	DNA-templated transcription, elongation
				endosome transport via multivesicular body sorting
27	1	11801	3868 GO:0032509	pathway
27	1	11801	3868 GO:0033119	negative regulation of RNA splicing
27	1	11801	3868 GO:0034260	negative regulation of GTPase activity
278	63	11550	3806 GO:0032956	regulation of actin cytoskeleton organization
90	14	11738	3855 GO:1903076	regulation of protein localization to plasma membrane
1264	355	10564	3514 GO:0045595	regulation of cell differentiation
413	101	11415	3768 GO:0099513	polymeric cytoskeletal fiber
				positive regulation of blood vessel endothelial cell
49	5	11779	3864 GO:0043536	migration

33	2	11795	3867 GO:0042149	cellular response to glucose starvation
33	2	11795	3867 GO:0051084	'de novo' posttranslational protein folding
33	2	11795	3867 GO:0007044	cell-substrate junction assembly
33	2	11795	3867 GO:0032506	cytokinetic process
33	2	11795	3867 GO:0032786	positive regulation of DNA-templated transcription, elongation
33	2	11795	3867 GO:0060840	artery development
33	2	11795	3867 GO:0150115	cell-substrate junction organization
263	59	11565	3810 GO:0098857	membrane microdomain
241	53	11587	3816 GO:0099572	postsynaptic specialization
81	12	11747	3857 GO:0060998	regulation of dendritic spine development
98	16	11730	3853 GO:0007623	circadian rhythm
63	8	11765	3861 GO:0009749	response to glucose
412	101	11416	3768 GO:0061024	membrane organization
102	17	11726	3852 GO:0006282	regulation of DNA repair
146	28	11682	3841 GO:0046677	response to antibiotic
262	59	11566	3810 GO:0045121	membrane raft
122	22	11706	3847 GO:0001667	ameboidal-type cell migration
89	14	11739	3855 GO:1900006	positive regulation of dendrite development
2124	623	9704	3246 GO:0048856	anatomical structure development
38	3	11790	3866 GO:0030866	cortical actin cytoskeleton organization
76	11	11752	3858 GO:0043502	regulation of muscle adaptation
76	11	11752	3858 GO:0046165	alcohol biosynthetic process
76	11	11752	3858 GO:0005884	actin filament
67	9	11761	3860 GO:0034644	cellular response to UV
53	6	11775	3863 GO:0043542	endothelial cell migration
53	6	11775	3863 GO:0051893	regulation of focal adhesion assembly
53	6	11775	3863 GO:0005080	protein kinase C binding
53	6	11775	3863 GO:0090109	regulation of cell-substrate junction assembly
393	96	11435	3773 GO:0000978	RNA polymerase II cis-regulatory region sequence-specific DNA binding
308	72	11520	3797 GO:0009725	response to hormone
43	4	11785	3865 GO:0046834	lipid phosphorylation
43	4	11785	3865 GO:0061014	positive regulation of mRNA catabolic process
43	4	11785	3865 GO:0090311	regulation of protein deacetylation
149	29	11679	3840 GO:0030832	regulation of actin filament length
48	5	11780	3864 GO:0006342	chromatin silencing
48	5	11780	3864 GO:0008023	transcription elongation factor complex
48	5	11780	3864 GO:0035306	positive regulation of dephosphorylation
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0042975	peroxisome proliferator activated receptor binding
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0070300	phosphatidic acid binding
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0070971	endoplasmic reticulum exit site
19	0	11809	3869 GO:1900101	regulation of endoplasmic reticulum unfolded protein response
19	0	11809	3869 GO:2000641	regulation of early endosome to late endosome transport

19	0	11809	3869 GO:0000460	maturation of 5.8S rRNA
				regulation of production of miRNAs involved in gene
19	0	11809	3869 GO:1903798	silencing by miRNA
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0140223	general transcription initiation factor activity
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0031082	BLOC complex
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0006353	DNA-templated transcription, termination
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0006783	heme biosynthetic process
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0010485	H4 histone acetyltransferase activity
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0035329	hippo signaling
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0061912	selective autophagy
19	0	11809	3869 GO:0038084	vascular endothelial growth factor signaling pathway
517	132	11311	3737 GO:0051223	regulation of protein transport
				endoribonuclease activity, producing 5'-
26	1	11802	3868 GO:0016891	phosphomonoesters
26	1	11802	3868 GO:0018126	protein hydroxylation
26	1	11802	3868 GO:0001223	transcription coactivator binding
26	1	11802	3868 GO:0031063	regulation of histone deacetylation
26	1	11802	3868 GO:0031440	regulation of mRNA 3'-end processing
26	1	11802	3868 GO:0032469	endoplasmic reticulum calcium ion homeostasis
26	1	11802	3868 GO:0008156	negative regulation of DNA replication
26	1	11802	3868 GO:0034394	protein localization to cell surface
26	1	11802	3868 GO:0090312	positive regulation of protein deacetylation
32	2	11796	3867 GO:0016504	peptidase activator activity
32	2	11796	3867 GO:0042162	telomeric DNA binding
32	2	11796	3867 GO:0071333	cellular response to glucose stimulus
32	2	11796	3867 GO:0097718	disordered domain specific binding
32	2	11796	3867 GO:0051019	mitogen-activated protein kinase binding
				RNA polymerase II core promoter sequence-specific DNA
32	2	11796	3867 GO:0000979	binding
				negative regulation of proteasomal ubiquitin-dependent
32	2	11796	3867 GO:0032435	protein catabolic process
32	2	11796	3867 GO:0009409	response to cold
71	10	11757	3859 GO:0003730	mRNA 3'-UTR binding
62	8	11766	3861 GO:0004553	hydrolase activity, hydrolyzing O-glycosyl compounds
62	8	11766	3861 GO:0010507	negative regulation of autophagy
62	8	11766	3861 GO:0009755	hormone-mediated signaling pathway
183	38	11645	3831 GO:0001101	response to acid chemical
117	21	11711	3848 GO:0023014	signal transduction by protein phosphorylation
430	107	11398	3762 GO:0010975	regulation of neuron projection development
175	36	11653	3833 GO:1901215	negative regulation of neuron death
57	7	11771	3862 GO:0031023	microtubule organizing center organization
3071	924	8757	2945 GO:0032502	developmental process
148	29	11680	3840 GO:0008064	regulation of actin polymerization or depolymerization
310	73	11518	3796 GO:0097435	supramolecular fiber organization

66	9	11762	3860 GO:0034284	response to monosaccharide
37	3	11791	3866 GO:2000142	regulation of DNA-templated transcription, initiation
37	3	11791	3866 GO:0030119	AP-type membrane coat adaptor complex
37	3	11791	3866 GO:0009145	purine nucleoside triphosphate biosynthetic process
132	25	11696	3844 GO:0045931	positive regulation of mitotic cell cycle
52	6	11776	3863 GO:0005546	phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate binding
128	24	11700	3845 GO:0071229	cellular response to acid chemical
116	21	11712	3848 GO:0010634	positive regulation of epithelial cell migration
47	5	11781	3864 GO:0004860	protein kinase inhibitor activity
47	5	11781	3864 GO:0009142	nucleoside triphosphate biosynthetic process
42	4	11786	3865 GO:0051879	Hsp90 protein binding
42	4	11786	3865 GO:0005844	polysome
42	4	11786	3865 GO:0120163	negative regulation of cold-induced thermogenesis
61	8	11767	3861 GO:2001021	negative regulation of response to DNA damage stimulus
319	76	11509	3793 GO:0045860	positive regulation of protein kinase activity
91	15	11737	3854 GO:0032231	regulation of actin filament bundle assembly
74	11	11754	3858 GO:0042542	response to hydrogen peroxide negative regulation of reactive oxygen species
31	2	11797	3867 GO:1903427	biosynthetic process
31	2	11797	3867 GO:0001885	endothelial cell development
31	2	11797	3867 GO:0030134	COPII-coated ER to Golgi transport vesicle
31	2	11797	3867 GO:0006623	protein targeting to vacuole
31	2	11797	3867 GO:0032355	response to estradiol
31	2	11797	3867 GO:0032728	positive regulation of interferon-beta production
31	2	11797	3867 GO:0009060	aerobic respiration
31	2	11797	3867 GO:0036002	pre-mRNA binding
95	16	11733	3853 GO:0032273	positive regulation of protein polymerization
25	1	11803	3868 GO:0016577	histone demethylation
25	1	11803	3868 GO:0042168	heme metabolic process
25	1	11803	3868 GO:0070076	histone lysine demethylation
25	1	11803	3868 GO:0045047	protein targeting to ER
25	1	11803	3868 GO:0070979	protein K11-linked ubiquitination
25	1	11803	3868 GO:0032452	histone demethylase activity
25	1	11803	3868 GO:0035904	aorta development RNA polymerase II general transcription initiation factor
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0016251	activity
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0016514	SWI/SNF complex
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0042274	ribosomal small subunit biogenesis phosphotransferase activity, for other substituted
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0016780	phosphate groups
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0042982	amyloid precursor protein metabolic process
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0070131	positive regulation of mitochondrial translation
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0045324	late endosome to vacuole transport
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0045722	positive regulation of gluconeogenesis

18	0	11810	3869 GO:0071616	acyl-CoA biosynthetic process
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0097602	cullin family protein binding
18	0	11810	3869 GO:1902236	negative regulation of endoplasmic reticulum stress-induced intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0050435	amyloid-beta metabolic process
18	0	11810	3869 GO:1903599	positive regulation of autophagy of mitochondrion
18	0	11810	3869 GO:1904262	negative regulation of TORC1 signaling
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0140102	catalytic activity, acting on a rRNA
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0031167	rRNA methylation
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0005666	RNA polymerase III complex
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0005686	U2 snRNP
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0005740	mitochondrial envelope
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0032239	regulation of nucleobase-containing compound transport
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0006743	ubiquinone metabolic process
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0008139	nuclear localization sequence binding
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0008649	rRNA methyltransferase activity
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0034472	snRNA 3'-end processing
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0060544	regulation of necroptotic process
18	0	11810	3869 GO:0035384	thioester biosynthetic process
65	9	11763	3860 GO:0019003	GDP binding
65	9	11763	3860 GO:0010631	epithelial cell migration
65	9	11763	3860 GO:0009746	response to hexose
103	18	11725	3851 GO:0017124	SH3 domain binding
184	39	11644	3830 GO:0032886	regulation of microtubule-based process
51	6	11777	3863 GO:2001238	positive regulation of extrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway
51	6	11777	3863 GO:0008286	insulin receptor signaling pathway
69	10	11759	3859 GO:0071453	cellular response to oxygen levels
36	3	11792	3866 GO:0016879	ligase activity, forming carbon-nitrogen bonds
36	3	11792	3866 GO:0071364	cellular response to epidermal growth factor stimulus
36	3	11792	3866 GO:0072666	establishment of protein localization to vacuole
36	3	11792	3866 GO:0031985	Golgi cisterna
36	3	11792	3866 GO:0009206	purine ribonucleoside triphosphate biosynthetic process
36	3	11792	3866 GO:0035307	positive regulation of protein dephosphorylation
60	8	11768	3861 GO:0002039	p53 binding
296	70	11532	3799 GO:0005543	phospholipid binding
46	5	11782	3864 GO:0032481	positive regulation of type I interferon production
46	5	11782	3864 GO:0010656	negative regulation of muscle cell apoptotic process
41	4	11787	3865 GO:0070988	demethylation
41	4	11787	3865 GO:0071322	cellular response to carbohydrate stimulus
41	4	11787	3865 GO:0051402	neuron apoptotic process
41	4	11787	3865 GO:0030331	estrogen receptor binding
106	19	11722	3850 GO:1900180	regulation of protein localization to nucleus

110	20	11718	3849 GO:0030496	midbody
216	48	11612	3821 GO:0032535	regulation of cellular component size
428	108	11400	3761 GO:0051347	positive regulation of transferase activity
452	115	11376	3754 GO:0010720	positive regulation of cell development
245	56	11583	3813 GO:0040013	negative regulation of locomotion
77	12	11751	3857 GO:1901888	regulation of cell junction assembly
64	9	11764	3860 GO:1903509	liposaccharide metabolic process
55	7	11773	3862 GO:0022625	cytosolic large ribosomal subunit
55	7	11773	3862 GO:0060999	positive regulation of dendritic spine development
				positive regulation of DNA-templated transcription,
30	2	11798	3867 GO:2000144	initiation
30	2	11798	3867 GO:0046320	regulation of fatty acid oxidation
30	2	11798	3867 GO:0071985	multivesicular body sorting pathway
30	2	11798	3867 GO:0051059	NF-kappaB binding
				positive regulation of microtubule polymerization or
30	2	11798	3867 GO:0031112	depolymerization
30	2	11798	3867 GO:0006900	vesicle budding from membrane
186	40	11642	3829 GO:0007507	heart development
621	165	11207	3704 GO:0003700	DNA-binding transcription factor activity
85	14	11743	3855 GO:0000149	SNARE binding
129	25	11699	3844 GO:0004721	phosphoprotein phosphatase activity
68	10	11760	3859 GO:0019217	regulation of fatty acid metabolic process
50	6	11778	3863 GO:0042770	signal transduction in response to DNA damage
50	6	11778	3863 GO:0070997	neuron death
24	1	11804	3868 GO:0042026	protein refolding
24	1	11804	3868 GO:0016866	intramolecular transferase activity
24	1	11804	3868 GO:0000030	mannosyltransferase activity
24	1	11804	3868 GO:1903671	negative regulation of sprouting angiogenesis
				negative regulation of telomere maintenance via
24	1	11804	3868 GO:1904357	telomere lengthening
24	1	11804	3868 GO:0030660	Golgi-associated vesicle membrane
24	1	11804	3868 GO:0032373	positive regulation of sterol transport
24	1	11804	3868 GO:0032376	positive regulation of cholesterol transport
24	1	11804	3868 GO:0007031	peroxisome organization
				regulation of establishment or maintenance of cell
24	1	11804	3868 GO:0032878	polarity
167	35	11661	3834 GO:0030100	regulation of endocytosis
89	15	11739	3854 GO:2001022	positive regulation of response to DNA damage stimulus
89	15	11739	3854 GO:0030097	hemopoiesis
536	140	11292	3729 GO:0090087	regulation of peptide transport
				negative regulation of DNA-binding transcription factor
121	23	11707	3846 GO:0043433	activity
				regulation of transcription from RNA polymerase II
45	5	11783	3864 GO:0043618	promoter in response to stress
45	5	11783	3864 GO:0045599	negative regulation of fat cell differentiation

45	5	11783	3864 GO:0031648	protein destabilization
45	5	11783	3864 GO:0032206	positive regulation of telomere maintenance
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0043574	peroxisomal transport
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0045259	proton-transporting ATP synthase complex
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0070822	Sin3-type complex
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0071359	cellular response to dsRNA
17	0	11811	3869 GO:2000001	regulation of DNA damage checkpoint
17	0	11811	3869 GO:1900363	regulation of mRNA polyadenylation
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0022624	proteasome accessory complex
17	0	11811	3869 GO:1901524	regulation of mitophagy
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0000028	ribosomal small subunit assembly
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0000380	alternative mRNA splicing, via spliceosome
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0001522	pseudouridine synthesis
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0051895	negative regulation of focal adhesion assembly
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0002098	tRNA wobble uridine modification
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0004602	glutathione peroxidase activity
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0030150	protein import into mitochondrial matrix
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0031231	intrinsic component of peroxisomal membrane
				mitochondrial proton-transporting ATP synthase
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0005753	complex
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0006448	regulation of translational elongation
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0034389	lipid droplet organization
				negative regulation of cell-substrate junction
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0150118	organization
17	0	11811	3869 GO:0015035	protein disulfide oxidoreductase activity
35	3	11793	3866 GO:0004712	protein serine/threonine/tyrosine kinase activity
40	4	11788	3865 GO:2000725	regulation of cardiac muscle cell differentiation
40	4	11788	3865 GO:0007029	endoplasmic reticulum organization
76	12	11752	3857 GO:0120162	positive regulation of cold-induced thermogenesis
				nucleobase-containing small molecule biosynthetic
63	9	11765	3860 GO:0034404	process
732	199	11096	3670 GO:0060284	regulation of cell development
177	38	11651	3831 GO:0104004	cellular response to environmental stimulus
177	38	11651	3831 GO:0071214	cellular response to abiotic stimulus
84	14	11744	3855 GO:0055076	transition metal ion homeostasis
67	10	11761	3859 GO:0019209	kinase activator activity
246	57	11582	3812 GO:0062012	regulation of small molecule metabolic process
				regulation of DNA-templated transcription in response to
49	6	11779	3863 GO:0043620	stress
49	6	11779	3863 GO:0001678	cellular glucose homeostasis
267	63	11561	3806 GO:1901214	regulation of neuron death
58	8	11770	3861 GO:0070373	negative regulation of ERK1 and ERK2 cascade
58	8	11770	3861 GO:0000077	DNA damage checkpoint
968	271	10860	3598 GO:0042592	homeostatic process
				negative regulation of blood vessel endothelial cell
29	2	11799	3867 GO:0043537	migration

29	2	11799	3867 GO:1900181	negative regulation of protein localization to nucleus
29	2	11799	3867 GO:0080008	Cul4-RING E3 ubiquitin ligase complex
				DNA damage response, signal transduction by p53 class
29	2	11799	3867 GO:0030330	mediator
29	2	11799	3867 GO:0009161	ribonucleoside monophosphate metabolic process
44	5	11784	3864 GO:0044042	glucan metabolic process
				intrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway by p53 class
44	5	11784	3864 GO:0072332	mediator
44	5	11784	3864 GO:0006073	cellular glucan metabolic process
44	5	11784	3864 GO:0005977	glycogen metabolic process
44	5	11784	3864 GO:0034446	substrate adhesion-dependent cell spreading
				establishment of protein localization to plasma
44	5	11784	3864 GO:0061951	membrane
123	24	11705	3845 GO:0035303	regulation of dephosphorylation
79	13	11749	3856 GO:0050772	positive regulation of axonogenesis
79	13	11749	3856 GO:0051492	regulation of stress fiber assembly
79	13	11749	3856 GO:0010660	regulation of muscle cell apoptotic process
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0016556	mRNA modification
				modification by symbiont of host morphology or
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0044003	physiology
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0070584	mitochondrion morphogenesis
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0097352	autophagosome maturation
				vascular endothelial growth factor receptor signaling
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0048010	pathway
23	1	11805	3868 GO:1902414	protein localization to cell junction
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0050687	negative regulation of defense response to virus
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0031529	ruffle organization
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0033522	histone H2A ubiquitination
				positive regulation of transcription initiation from RNA
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0060261	polymerase II promoter
23	1	11805	3868 GO:0090181	regulation of cholesterol metabolic process
34	3	11794	3866 GO:0000422	autophagy of mitochondrion
				negative regulation of cardiac muscle tissue
34	3	11794	3866 GO:0055026	development
34	3	11794	3866 GO:0005547	phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate binding
34	3	11794	3866 GO:0061726	mitochondrion disassembly
				regulation of cell migration involved in sprouting
34	3	11794	3866 GO:0090049	angiogenesis
				regulation of extrinsic apoptotic signaling pathway via
39	4	11789	3865 GO:1902041	death domain receptors
39	4	11789	3865 GO:1903293	phosphatase complex
39	4	11789	3865 GO:0031902	late endosome membrane
39	4	11789	3865 GO:0008287	protein serine/threonine phosphatase complex
39	4	11789	3865 GO:0010828	positive regulation of glucose transmembrane transport
53	7	11775	3862 GO:0016835	carbon-oxygen lyase activity

53	7	11775	3862 GO:1903008	organelle disassembly
53	7	11775	3862 GO:0000381	regulation of alternative mRNA splicing, via spliceosome
53	7	11775	3862 GO:0031122	cytoplasmic microtubule organization
53	7	11775	3862 GO:0034968	histone lysine methylation
87	15	11741	3854 GO:0015078	proton transmembrane transporter activity
153	32	11675	3837 GO:0051604	protein maturation
103	19	11725	3850 GO:0012505	endomembrane system
134	27	11694	3842 GO:0043122	regulation of I-kappaB kinase/NF-kappaB signaling
398	101	11430	3768 GO:0050769	positive regulation of neurogenesis
130	26	11698	3843 GO:0033500	carbohydrate homeostasis
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0016075	rRNA catabolic process
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0016854	racemase and epimerase activity
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0043149	stress fiber assembly
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0070932	histone H3 deacetylation
16	0	11812	3869 GO:1900037	regulation of cellular response to hypoxia
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0046831	regulation of RNA export from nucleus
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0046933	proton-transporting ATP synthase activity, rotational mechanism
16	0	11812	3869 GO:1901663	quinone biosynthetic process
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0098974	postsynaptic actin cytoskeleton organization
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0099188	postsynaptic cytoskeleton organization
16	0	11812	3869 GO:1903358	regulation of Golgi organization
16	0	11812	3869 GO:1903513	endoplasmic reticulum to cytosol transport
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0001056	RNA polymerase III activity
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0030014	CCR4-NOT complex
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0030038	contractile actin filament bundle assembly
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0030970	retrograde protein transport, ER to cytosol
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0005662	DNA replication factor A complex
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0005779	integral component of peroxisomal membrane
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0005852	eukaryotic translation initiation factor 3 complex
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0006089	lactate metabolic process
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0006744	ubiquinone biosynthetic process
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0006896	Golgi to vacuole transport
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0032986	protein-DNA complex disassembly
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0034399	nuclear periphery
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0034979	NAD-dependent protein deacetylase activity
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0010888	negative regulation of lipid storage
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0035459	vesicle cargo loading
16	0	11812	3869 GO:1990868	response to chemokine
16	0	11812	3869 GO:1990869	cellular response to chemokine
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0090069	regulation of ribosome biogenesis
16	0	11812	3869 GO:0090151	establishment of protein localization to mitochondrial membrane
160	34	11668	3835 GO:0030674	protein binding, bridging
70	11	11758	3858 GO:0097517	contractile actin filament bundle

70	11	11758	3858 GO:0001725	stress fiber
70	11	11758	3858 GO:0032479	regulation of type I interferon production
70	11	11758	3858 GO:0090630	activation of GTPase activity
48	6	11780	3863 GO:0043462	regulation of ATPase activity
48	6	11780	3863 GO:0061001	regulation of dendritic spine morphogenesis
74	12	11754	3857 GO:0005798	Golgi-associated vesicle
137	28	11691	3841 GO:0034330	cell junction organization
196	44	11632	3825 GO:0006066	alcohol metabolic process
86	15	11742	3854 GO:0045177	apical part of cell
148	31	11680	3838 GO:0072659	protein localization to plasma membrane
174	38	11654	3831 GO:0048511	rhythmic process
28	2	11800	3867 GO:0043631	RNA polyadenylation
28	2	11800	3867 GO:0071889	14-3-3 protein binding
28	2	11800	3867 GO:0051085	chaperone cofactor-dependent protein refolding
28	2	11800	3867 GO:0007097	nuclear migration
28	2	11800	3867 GO:0009262	deoxyribonucleotide metabolic process
43	5	11785	3864 GO:1903533	regulation of protein targeting
129	26	11699	3843 GO:0042593	glucose homeostasis
159	34	11669	3835 GO:0048732	gland development
306	75	11522	3794 GO:0032970	regulation of actin filament-based process
52	7	11776	3862 GO:0006090	pyruvate metabolic process
65	10	11763	3859 GO:0016052	carbohydrate catabolic process
38	4	11790	3865 GO:0046825	regulation of protein export from nucleus
38	4	11790	3865 GO:0000152	nuclear ubiquitin ligase complex
267	64	11561	3805 GO:0010976	positive regulation of neuron projection development
33	3	11795	3866 GO:0045601	regulation of endothelial cell differentiation
33	3	11795	3866 GO:0098531	ligand-activated transcription factor activity
69	11	11759	3858 GO:0043230	extracellular organelle
22	1	11806	3868 GO:0045292	mRNA cis splicing, via spliceosome
22	1	11806	3868 GO:0045648	positive regulation of erythrocyte differentiation
22	1	11806	3868 GO:2000765	regulation of cytoplasmic translation
22	1	11806	3868 GO:0046931	pore complex assembly
22	1	11806	3868 GO:0048025	negative regulation of mRNA splicing, via spliceosome
22	1	11806	3868 GO:0051457	maintenance of protein location in nucleus
22	1	11806	3868 GO:0051537	2 iron, 2 sulfur cluster binding
22	1	11806	3868 GO:0051787	misfolded protein binding
22	1	11806	3868 GO:0032968	positive regulation of transcription elongation from RNA polymerase II promoter
22	1	11806	3868 GO:0009299	mRNA transcription
113	22	11715	3847 GO:0006575	cellular modified amino acid metabolic process
56	8	11772	3861 GO:0051702	interaction with symbiont
47	6	11781	3863 GO:0071156	regulation of cell cycle arrest
47	6	11781	3863 GO:2000134	negative regulation of G1/S transition of mitotic cell cycle

47	6	11781	3863 GO:0032648	regulation of interferon-beta production
47	6	11781	3863 GO:0009185	ribonucleoside diphosphate metabolic process
47	6	11781	3863 GO:0009247	glycolipid biosynthetic process
47	6	11781	3863 GO:0061515	myeloid cell development
227	53	11601	3816 GO:0045765	regulation of angiogenesis
97	18	11731	3851 GO:0045807	positive regulation of endocytosis
209	48	11619	3821 GO:2000146	negative regulation of cell motility
85	15	11743	3854 GO:0048145	regulation of fibroblast proliferation
89	16	11739	3853 GO:0046434	organophosphate catabolic process
438	114	11390	3755 GO:0004672	protein kinase activity phosphotransferase activity, phosphate group as acceptor
42	5	11786	3864 GO:0016776	acceptor
42	5	11786	3864 GO:0097581	lamellipodium organization
42	5	11786	3864 GO:1905515	non-motile cilium assembly
42	5	11786	3864 GO:0006487	protein N-linked glycosylation
321	80	11507	3789 GO:0045666	positive regulation of neuron differentiation
112	22	11716	3847 GO:0000904	cell morphogenesis involved in differentiation transferase activity, transferring alkyl or aryl (other than methyl) groups
51	7	11777	3862 GO:0016765	methyl) groups
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0015919	peroxisomal membrane transport
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0042255	ribosome assembly
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0017136	NAD-dependent histone deacetylase activity
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0044068	modulation by symbiont of host cellular process
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0043981	histone H4-K5 acetylation
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0043982	histone H4-K8 acetylation
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0044827	modulation by host of viral genome replication
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0071004	U2-type prespliceosome
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0070897	transcription preinitiation complex assembly
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0071010	prespliceosome
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0071392	cellular response to estradiol stimulus
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0046755	viral budding
15	0	11813	3869 GO:2000811	negative regulation of anoikis positive regulation of double-strand break repair via nonhomologous end joining
15	0	11813	3869 GO:2001034	nonhomologous end joining
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0072662	protein localization to peroxisome
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0072663	establishment of protein localization to peroxisome
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0048038	quinone binding
15	0	11813	3869 GO:1902188	positive regulation of viral release from host cell
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0051290	protein heterotetramerization
15	0	11813	3869 GO:1904263	positive regulation of TORC1 signaling regulation of protein localization to chromosome, telomeric region
15	0	11813	3869 GO:1904814	telomeric region
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0080009	mRNA methylation
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0140053	mitochondrial gene expression
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0005671	Ada2/Gcn5/Ada3 transcription activator complex
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0005682	U5 snRNP

15	0	11813	3869 GO:0005797	Golgi medial cisterna
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0006474	N-terminal protein amino acid acetylation
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0006625	protein targeting to peroxisome
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0033202	DNA helicase complex
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0008432	JUN kinase binding
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0034236	protein kinase A catalytic subunit binding
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0035102	PRC1 complex
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0035196	production of miRNAs involved in gene silencing by miRNA
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0062099	negative regulation of programmed necrotic cell death
15	0	11813	3869 GO:0090141	positive regulation of mitochondrial fission
748	207	11080	3662 GO:0045597	positive regulation of cell differentiation
705	194	11123	3675 GO:0051093	negative regulation of developmental process
27	2	11801	3867 GO:0000027	ribosomal large subunit assembly
27	2	11801	3867 GO:0050681	androgen receptor binding
27	2	11801	3867 GO:0051205	protein insertion into membrane
27	2	11801	3867 GO:1904292	regulation of ERAD pathway
27	2	11801	3867 GO:1905476	negative regulation of protein localization to membrane
27	2	11801	3867 GO:0031116	positive regulation of microtubule polymerization
27	2	11801	3867 GO:0006099	tricarboxylic acid cycle
27	2	11801	3867 GO:0006739	NADP metabolic process
27	2	11801	3867 GO:0090568	nuclear transcriptional repressor complex
37	4	11791	3865 GO:2000008	regulation of protein localization to cell surface
37	4	11791	3865 GO:0010824	regulation of centrosome duplication
72	12	11756	3857 GO:0045069	regulation of viral genome replication
72	12	11756	3857 GO:0031110	regulation of microtubule polymerization or depolymerization
100	19	11728	3850 GO:0098727	maintenance of cell number
123	25	11705	3844 GO:1902904	negative regulation of supramolecular fiber organization
691	190	11137	3679 GO:0008092	cytoskeletal protein binding
484	128	11344	3741 GO:0008289	lipid binding
138	29	11690	3840 GO:0030307	positive regulation of cell growth
32	3	11796	3866 GO:0072523	purine-containing compound catabolic process
32	3	11796	3866 GO:0004879	nuclear receptor activity
32	3	11796	3866 GO:0031124	mRNA 3'-end processing
32	3	11796	3866 GO:0061980	regulatory RNA binding
55	8	11773	3861 GO:0071897	DNA biosynthetic process
55	8	11773	3861 GO:0010633	negative regulation of epithelial cell migration
80	14	11748	3855 GO:0016798	hydrolase activity, acting on glycosyl bonds
84	15	11744	3854 GO:0019751	polyol metabolic process
200	46	11628	3823 GO:0030336	negative regulation of cell migration
134	28	11694	3841 GO:0051100	negative regulation of binding
46	6	11782	3863 GO:0032210	regulation of telomere maintenance via telomerase

527	141	11301	3728 GO:0045664	regulation of neuron differentiation
59	9	11769	3860 GO:0005089	Rho guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity
130	27	11698	3842 GO:0007163	establishment or maintenance of cell polarity
21	1	11807	3868 GO:0019320	hexose catabolic process
21	1	11807	3868 GO:0097502	mannosylation
				negative regulation of protein localization to plasma
21	1	11807	3868 GO:1903077	membrane
21	1	11807	3868 GO:0005849	mRNA cleavage factor complex
				proteasomal ubiquitin-independent protein catabolic
21	1	11807	3868 GO:0010499	process
21	1	11807	3868 GO:0035162	embryonic hemopoiesis
107	21	11721	3848 GO:1904375	regulation of protein localization to cell periphery
63	10	11765	3859 GO:0022406	membrane docking
63	10	11765	3859 GO:0046916	cellular transition metal ion homeostasis
63	10	11765	3859 GO:1901983	regulation of protein acetylation
298	74	11530	3795 GO:0098657	import into cell
837	235	10991	3634 GO:0048513	animal organ development
217	51	11611	3818 GO:0003924	GTPase activity
50	7	11778	3862 GO:0019210	kinase inhibitor activity
50	7	11778	3862 GO:1902807	negative regulation of cell cycle G1/S phase transition
50	7	11778	3862 GO:0030145	manganese ion binding
41	5	11787	3864 GO:0042625	ATPase-coupled ion transmembrane transporter activity
41	5	11787	3864 GO:0010596	negative regulation of endothelial cell migration
41	5	11787	3864 GO:0090342	regulation of cell aging
639	175	11189	3694 GO:0050767	regulation of neurogenesis
87	16	11741	3853 GO:0042692	muscle cell differentiation
83	15	11745	3854 GO:0032984	protein-containing complex disassembly
213	50	11615	3819 GO:0042623	ATPase activity, coupled
318	80	11510	3789 GO:0071900	regulation of protein serine/threonine kinase activity
129	27	11699	3842 GO:0044309	neuron spine
54	8	11774	3861 GO:0019005	SCF ubiquitin ligase complex
4736	1475	7092	2394 GO:0016020	membrane
36	4	11792	3865 GO:0033013	tetrapyrrole metabolic process
173	39	11655	3830 GO:0060828	regulation of canonical Wnt signaling pathway
345	88	11483	3781 GO:1903047	mitotic cell cycle process
26	2	11802	3867 GO:0016417	S-acyltransferase activity
26	2	11802	3867 GO:0043015	gamma-tubulin binding
26	2	11802	3867 GO:0071480	cellular response to gamma radiation
26	2	11802	3867 GO:1902653	secondary alcohol biosynthetic process
26	2	11802	3867 GO:0006378	mRNA polyadenylation
26	2	11802	3867 GO:0061003	positive regulation of dendritic spine morphogenesis
26	2	11802	3867 GO:0061462	protein localization to lysosome
45	6	11783	3863 GO:0048592	eye morphogenesis

102	20	11726	3849 GO:0033135	regulation of peptidyl-serine phosphorylation
31	3	11797	3866 GO:2000781	positive regulation of double-strand break repair
31	3	11797	3866 GO:0006778	porphyrin-containing compound metabolic process
31	3	11797	3866 GO:0008180	COP9 signalosome
31	3	11797	3866 GO:0015030	Cajal body
121	25	11707	3844 GO:0048568	embryonic organ development
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0015936	coenzyme A metabolic process
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0016441	posttranscriptional gene silencing
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0016442	RISC complex
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0042407	cristae formation
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0016881	acid-amino acid ligase activity
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0042776	mitochondrial ATP synthesis coupled proton transport
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0042800	histone methyltransferase activity (H3-K4 specific)
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0043024	ribosomal small subunit binding
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0043248	proteasome assembly
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0043555	regulation of translation in response to stress
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0045647	negative regulation of erythrocyte differentiation
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0071426	ribonucleoprotein complex export from nucleus
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0071428	rRNA-containing ribonucleoprotein complex export from nucleus
14	0	11814	3869 GO:2000232	regulation of rRNA processing
14	0	11814	3869 GO:1901836	regulation of transcription of nucleolar large rRNA by RNA polymerase I
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0098799	outer mitochondrial membrane protein complex
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0098847	sequence-specific single stranded DNA binding
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0000054	ribosomal subunit export from nucleus
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0000176	nuclear exosome (RNase complex)
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0000291	nuclear-transcribed mRNA catabolic process, exonucleolytic
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0000963	mitochondrial RNA processing
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0000974	Prp19 complex
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0051131	chaperone-mediated protein complex assembly
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0051645	Golgi localization
14	0	11814	3869 GO:1904923	regulation of autophagy of mitochondrion in response to mitochondrial depolarization
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0002161	aminoacyl-tRNA editing activity
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0030127	COPII vesicle coat
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0030479	actin cortical patch
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0005161	platelet-derived growth factor receptor binding
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0031011	Ino80 complex
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0031083	BLOC-1 complex
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0031332	RNAi effector complex
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0006103	2-oxoglutarate metabolic process
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0006337	nucleosome disassembly
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0031937	positive regulation of chromatin silencing

14	0	11814	3869 GO:0006862	nucleotide transport
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0006999	nuclear pore organization
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0033276	transcription factor TFII complex
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0033750	ribosome localization
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0009226	nucleotide-sugar biosynthetic process regulation of nuclear-transcribed mRNA poly(A) tail
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0060211	shortening
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0060546	negative regulation of necroptotic process
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0061645	endocytic patch
14	0	11814	3869 GO:1990404	protein ADP-ribosylase activity
14	0	11814	3869 GO:0038201	TOR complex
117	24	11711	3845 GO:0010675	regulation of cellular carbohydrate metabolic process
132	28	11696	3841 GO:0030833	regulation of actin filament polymerization
520	140	11308	3729 GO:0006468	protein phosphorylation
201	47	11627	3822 GO:0046982	protein heterodimerization activity
86	16	11742	3853 GO:0110020	regulation of actomyosin structure organization
86	16	11742	3853 GO:0006275	regulation of DNA replication
70	12	11758	3857 GO:0035304	regulation of protein dephosphorylation
74	13	11754	3856 GO:0009743	response to carbohydrate
78	14	11750	3855 GO:0015399	primary active transmembrane transporter activity
49	7	11779	3862 GO:0046605	regulation of centrosome cycle
49	7	11779	3862 GO:0001085	RNA polymerase II transcription factor binding
49	7	11779	3862 GO:0006112	energy reserve metabolic process
40	5	11788	3864 GO:0016860	intramolecular oxidoreductase activity cellular response to transforming growth factor beta stimulus
40	5	11788	3864 GO:0071560	regulation of pri-miRNA transcription by RNA polymerase II
40	5	11788	3864 GO:1902893	II
40	5	11788	3864 GO:0003707	steroid hormone receptor activity
40	5	11788	3864 GO:0009166	nucleotide catabolic process
124	26	11704	3843 GO:0015630	microtubule cytoskeleton
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0016578	histone deubiquitination
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0017025	TBP-class protein binding
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0043153	entrainment of circadian clock by photoperiod
20	1	11808	3868 GO:1900242	regulation of synaptic vesicle endocytosis
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0046965	retinoid X receptor binding
20	1	11808	3868 GO:1902410	mitotic cytokinetic process
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0000313	organellar ribosome
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0000413	protein peptidyl-prolyl isomerization
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0050750	low-density lipoprotein particle receptor binding
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0002097	tRNA wobble base modification
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0030371	translation repressor activity
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0030904	retromer complex
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0005761	mitochondrial ribosome

20	1	11808	3868 GO:0031306	intrinsic component of mitochondrial outer membrane
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0008171	O-methyltransferase activity
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0034593	phosphatidylinositol bisphosphate phosphatase activity
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0034620	cellular response to unfolded protein
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0009648	photoperiodism
20	1	11808	3868 GO:0035268	protein mannosylation
53	8	11775	3861 GO:0071479	cellular response to ionizing radiation
53	8	11775	3861 GO:0051058	negative regulation of small GTPase mediated signal transduction
57	9	11771	3860 GO:0036294	cellular response to decreased oxygen levels
93	18	11735	3851 GO:0010906	regulation of glucose metabolic process
35	4	11793	3865 GO:0016893	endonuclease activity, active with either ribo- or deoxyribonucleic acids and producing 5'-phosphomonoesters
35	4	11793	3865 GO:0043044	ATP-dependent chromatin remodeling
35	4	11793	3865 GO:2000279	negative regulation of DNA biosynthetic process
35	4	11793	3865 GO:1901505	carbohydrate derivative transmembrane transporter activity
35	4	11793	3865 GO:0031057	negative regulation of histone modification
35	4	11793	3865 GO:0007098	centrosome cycle
301	76	11527	3793 GO:0005874	microtubule
44	6	11784	3863 GO:1902808	positive regulation of cell cycle G1/S phase transition
44	6	11784	3863 GO:0006111	regulation of gluconeogenesis
61	10	11767	3859 GO:0032465	regulation of cytokinesis
564	154	11264	3715 GO:0022402	cell cycle process
138	30	11690	3839 GO:0120032	regulation of plasma membrane bounded cell projection assembly